

**Empirical Examination of the Impact of Gender,
Affiliation to a Political Party, Insider Ownership, and
Narcissism of Top Executives on Firm Risk Taking**

BBA-A

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Table of Contents

Introduction.....	1
1.1. Background.....	1
1.2. Theoretical Justification.....	2
1.3. Problem Statement.....	2
1.4. Research Questions.....	2
1.5. Objectives.....	3
1.6. Significance.....	3
Literature Review.....	4
2.1. Gender and Risk:.....	4
2.2. Affiliation to a Political Individual or Party.....	9
2.3. Risk and Insider Ownership.....	19
2.4. Narcissism and Risk.....	28
Methodology.....	39
3.1. Data collection and variables.....	39
3.2. Independent variables.....	39
3.3. Control variables.....	41
3.4. Dependent variables.....	41
3.5. Model.....	41
Results and Discussion.....	43
4.1. Correlation.....	43
4.2. Descriptive Statistics.....	49
4.3. Likelihood test.....	53
4.4. Hausman test.....	59
4.5. Regression: Common, Fixed & Random Effect Model.....	73
Pakistan.....	73
India.....	81
China.....	88
Bangladesh.....	95
Vietnam.....	99
Malaysia.....	106
Conclusion.....	113
References.....	115

Introduction

This study aims to examine the role played by gender, affiliation to a political party, insider ownership, and narcissism of top executives i.e., chief executive officer (CEO) and chief financial officer (CFO) on the three firm risk-taking measures, namely total risk, systematic risk, and idiosyncratic risk. In the context of our study, we define the political affiliation of an individual as having a direct or indirect connection to a government, a government officer, a political party, or a politician. Insider ownership is the proportion of stock held directly by company directors, managers, and other management personnel through exercising employee stock options or through private corporations (Bauer et al., 2021). Lastly, the American Psychiatric Association defines narcissism as “a persistent pattern of need for admiration, lack of empathy, and grandiosity” (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

1.1. Background

Anecdotal evidence and general psychology, thinking patterns would lead one to believe that gender, political affiliations, ownership of the company's shares, and narcissistic behavior of top executives (CEOs and CFOs) would influence these individuals' risk preferences, tolerance, and self-interests in the organization. However, do these variances depending on gender affect the riskiness of a corporation, as well as the professionalism and corporate decision-making ability of these top executives?(Peltomäki et al., 2021) Furthermore, in a country with a competent and enforced legal structure, one would think that these corporations are not expected to use their political power to gain a competitive edge over firms in the same industry. This is because these government officials do not want to risk the heavy penalties and sanctions that would be imposed on them if they used their political influence to assist these corporations for illegal and counterproductive reasons (Goldman et al., 2009). Finally, the fact that these top executives possess a percentage of the firm's stock and have a narcissistic personality leads one to conclude that these individuals will make decisions that align with their personal aims rather than those of the public interest or the other shareholders in the organization. As a result, the purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of a firm's top executives (CEO and CFO) gender, political affiliation, ownership, and narcissism on market-based measures of firm risk. Data from listed Asian enterprises from 2012 to 2021 will be used for this purpose.

1.2. Theoretical Justification

This study's justifications are based on the upper echelon theory and the agency theory.

Our study is based on the notion that the chief executive officer's (CEO's) and chief financial officer's (CFO's) different personality traits, viewpoints, and personal inclinations may be a hindrance to their unbiased and effective decision-making, negatively affecting the company's soundness and integrity. According to the upper echelons theory by (Hambrick & Mason, 1984) and extensive research, these characteristics have a significant impact on the company's business strategies they devise, the financial and investment policies that they enact, as well as the overall performance of the firm and the managerial decisions made by these top executives. Refer to the work done by (Bertrand & Schoar, 2003; Cline & Yore, 2016; Graham et al., 2013; Hrazdil et al., 2020; Hu et al., 2020; Malmendier et al., 2011; Malmendier & Tate, 2005).

There has been an increase in the development of some financial systems that have advanced from the status of NEST to the status of EAGLE, resulting in the development of extended associations between groups, political associations, and power being concentrated in a few hands, which has resulted in a significant increase in interest in this area among researchers worldwide. Agency theory, among other key theoretical justifications, has been utilized to explain these affiliations, and studies with a primary focus on these affiliations have been developed to safeguard and distinguish these agents from narcissistic top executives. (Rajagopalan & Zhang, 2008)

1.3. Problem Statement

There has been extensive research on the age and gender of the CEO having a significant impact on the risk of a firm. However, there is a gap in whether insider ownership, political party affiliation, and narcissism of top executives, i.e., CEO and CFO, influence a firm's total, systemic, and idiosyncratic risk, particularly in the six major Asian Eagle economies.

1.4. Research Questions

The research questions for this study are as follows:

1. Whether the total risk of the firm is affected by gender, political affiliation, percentage of shares held, or narcissistic behavior of the CEO and CFO or not?
2. Whether the systematic risk of the firm is affected by gender, political affiliation, percentage of shares held, or narcissistic behavior of the CEO and CFO or not?

3. Whether the idiosyncratic risk of the firm is affected by the gender, political affiliation, percentage of shares held, or narcissistic behavior of the CEO and CFO or not?

1.5. Objectives

1. To examine the impact of gender, political affiliation, percentage of shares held, and narcissistic behavior of CEO and CFO on the Total Risk of the Firm.

2. To investigate the effect of gender, political affiliation, percentage of shares held, narcissistic behavior of CEO and CFO, and Systematic Risk of the Firm.

3. To determine the influence of gender, political affiliation, percentage of shares held, and narcissistic behavior of CEO and CFO on the Idiosyncratic risk of the Firm.

1.6. Significance

We contribute to current knowledge for multiple reasons. To begin, our study is unique because it analyses market-based measures of the three firm-based risks. 1) Total Firm Risk, 2) Systematic Firm Risk, and 3) Idiosyncratic Firm Risk these risks are not studied in detail for the Asian Markets considered in our study, which are members of the Eagle economies, including Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Malaysia, China, and Vietnam from 2010 to 2022. Because these countries belong to the same economic category, i.e., Eagle economies, discrepancies in their economic dynamics will be analyzed. Secondly, there is less prior literature available, particularly regarding the impact of chief financial officer (CFO) political affiliation and narcissism on corporate risk-taking and their effects on the investment behavior of various stakeholders. Furthermore, the relationships between age, gender, political affiliation, percentage of shares held, narcissistic behavior of these top executives, and the risk-taking of the firms are less examined in the case of Asia. Moreover, novel approaches may be followed to measure narcissism or other independent variables. Finally, our research aligns with the 4th, 8th, and 10th Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and would aid in achieving those targets, for e.g., the 4th goal of providing inclusive and equitable quality education, which would be accomplished by uncovering the discrepancies that raise a firm's risk; this would help investors be aware of these factors, and if a risk exists, they should be fully aware of it before making their investment. This study also coincides with an equally vital, 10th goal of minimizing disparities within and between countries. This would be accomplished by comparing the different eagle economies of our research and lowering any differences based on dynamics. Finally, decreasing inequalities and giving quality information would result in the fulfillment of the 8th goal of providing decent work and economic growth.

Aside from that, the results of this study will assist investors to make a decision on which firm to invest in based on the characteristics being studied in this research as investors have different preferences for the degree of risk-taking. If a company intends to change its strategy, this study will assist in predicting how risky a strategy will the top management choose to pursue. Moreover, if a firm intends to change its executive, the results of this study will help to predict the future risk-taking behavior of the new executive. Lastly, if the relationships hold true, our research will assist companies to make better-informed decisions on the preferable characteristics of an executive it wants to hire in order to maintain their risk appetite.

Literature Review

This section contains a review of previous studies performed in economies that are developed and developing economies. The relationships of different traits and factors including gender, insider ownership, political affiliation, and narcissism with three different types of risks i.e. total risk, idiosyncratic risk, and systematic risk is identified. It examines the impact of these factors of the CEO and CFO on different risks of the firm.

2.1. Gender and Risk:

Psychological and Biological Evidence:

Extensive research in experimental economics and psychology documents the behavioral differences of gender on financial decisions. The risk-averse behavior of women can be reflected in different areas of life. The vast amount of literature on psychology provides evidence that women are less prone to risk-taking (Hersch, 1996) e.g., they are less probable to smoke and are probable to wear seat belts. Two major schools of thought were used by (Felton, Gibson, & Sanbonmatsu, 2003) to describe gender differences toward risk. The first school included biological and genetic evidence, i.e., biological research provides explanations for the dissimilarities in risk tolerance among females and males. The female produces a high level of monoamine oxidase, which reduces sensation-seeking and risk-taking (Zuckerman, 1994). Evolution also explains this behavior as women have adopted risk aversion due to the greater duty of reproduction and parenting (Witt, 1994). The second school of thought involves socio-cultural evidence. Researchers report different findings that led to developing risk aversion among females, for instance, girls being forced to play stereotypical female roles (Slovic, 1996), restraining monitoring by parents during childhood (Byrnes, 2013), and women who took risks being disdained (Tuddenham, 1952). Culture pressurizes males to take more risks and discourages this behavior in females (Johnson & Powell, 1994).

Field studies' results support the argument that women have risk aversion compared to men (Eckel & Grossman, 2008). Certain elements, including personality traits, the threat of stereotypes, a stronger aversion to gambling among women, and the area of the decision, have been found to predict differences in decision-making involving risk between both genders (Demaree, DeDonno, Burns, Feldman, & Everhart, 2009; Carr & Steele, 2010; Vlaev, Kusev, Stewart, Aldrovandi, & Chater, 2010; Wieland, Sundali, Kimmelmeier, & Sarin, 2014). When women have the threat of stereotyping leads to the depletion of ego that eventually results in increased risk aversion. The same stereotype positively affects behavior involving more risk in their financial decisions (Carr & Steele, 2010). The endowment effect also serves to explain gender differences in aversion to risk. It was found that women did not show many differences in risk aversion in activities involving willing-to-accept. However, the differences in risk aversion were high in gambling activities that included willing-to-pay gambles (Wieland, Sundali, Kimmelmeier, & Sarin, 2014). However, previous literature on economics on the association among risk and gender was proved to be influenced by confirmation bias, stereotyping, and essentialist prior belief (Nelson, 2014).

Effect of Gender on Risk:

Some previous studies contradict the stereotype of high aversion in females and report no gender differences in risk-taking behavior (Arenson, 1978; Montgomery & Landers, 1974). While, later on, research provided empirical evidence of high-risk aversion among females towards gambles. The females were also not influenced by the framing effect and were careful while making the decision (Levin, Snyder, & Chapman, 1988). A similar study was conducted to examine the perception of both males and females regarding risk. It was reported that females view risk as a threat, while males perceive it as a challenge that they need to undertake (Arch, 1993). The differences in gender in risk-taking behavior were identified through the examination of 150 research studies. It was found that males exhibit high risk-taking in 14 out of 16 tasks (James P. Byrnes & Schafer, 1999). An experiment has proven that cohabiting and married men and women have differing risk-taking attitudes. According to the findings, males who have a partner or spouse who is willing to take risks are more likely to invest their pension funds in stocks. On the other hand, a female having a spouse or partner who is eager to take risks will cause the female to make fewer pension investments in stocks (Bernasek & Shwiff, 2001). One explanation for female risk aversion was provided that they have a higher perception of unfavorable outcomes and a lower enjoyment of taking risks (Harris & Jenkins, 2006). Males, when evaluating financial decisions, prefer high-risk ways of recovering losses

compared to means involving no risk with the same expected value. They are highly influenced by peer pressure from other males and financial pressure (Ermer, Cosmides, & Tooby, 2008). The risk-taking behavior of females is also reflected in their career paths, as they choose less risky jobs (Croson, Rachel, & Gneezy, 2009). The shift in perception in both genders has a significant impact on both personal and professional life. To compare the risk aversion among males and females, an experiment was conducted on students who were presented with various urns and were asked to bet. The results strongly supported the argument that there is high-risk aversion among females (Borghans, Heckman, Golsteyn, & Meijers, 2009). Experimental evidence exhibits the influence of soap operas involving financial scandals on males and females. Soap opera had a significant impact on formal borrowing, which was seen among males, however, minor effects were observed in females. This striking gender difference is due to their aversion to borrowing and a lower likelihood of borrowing (Berg & Zia, 2013). Furthermore, it was found that high education does not mitigate gender differences in risk aversion. Males who were highly educated were less risk averse relative to females who were highly educated. However, the risk aversion was found to be the same among males and females who had acquired financial education. Both genders had the same willingness to make risky asset investments and include risky assets in their portfolios (Hibbert, Lawrence, & Prakash, 2013). An experiment with the Dutch population and a student sample provides evidence that women are more temperate and prudent than men. Since there is a positive correlation between risk aversion and these two factors, it consequently results in high-risk aversion among women (Noussair, Trautmann, & Kuilen, 2014). An experiment on betting on real-life situations exhibited that aversion to risk is the same among both men and women, depicting no gender differences involving actual events (Sarin & Wieland, 2015).

Total and Market-based Risk and Gender:

Males are less risk tolerant than females, according to various researchers (Croson, Rachel, & Gneezy, 2009; Jianakoplos, Ammon, & Bernasek, 1998), and are more probable to invest in assets that are has less risk than stocks (Black, Devereux, Lundborg, & Majlesi, 2015; Oehler, Wendt, Wedlich, & Horn, 2018). The experiment also gives evidence of high investor confidence among males. It was found that males were more confident about their decision than females when both males and females were given financial statements and asked to choose the amount that would be invested (Estes & Hosseini, 1988). While making decisions regarding asset allocation, women tend to be risk-tolerant (Riley Jr & Chow, 1992). Expected utility theory explains the reason women have less wealth, which is that they hold less risky

investment portfolios that provide low returns (Bajtelsmit & Bernasek., 1996). This was confirmed by further research, which found that women generally hold fewer portfolios with less risky assets, which have lower expected returns compared to those held by their counterparts (Hinz, McCarthy, & Turner, 1997). Previous research reasserts that men are more risk tolerant compared to females and have a high propensity to select investment options that are most risk-tolerant (Barsky, Juster, Kimball, & Shapiro, 1997). A significant association was found between asset allocation and sex (Sunden & Surette, 1998). The study from Dutch households reported that women tend to have more interest in matters related to finances. It was also proved that women are inclined to make investments in safe assets as compared to high-return investments (Donkers & Soest, 1999). One reason for the risk-taking tendency in males is their overconfidence, which leads them to trade more often than females. It was reported that males trade forty-five percent more than females, and they receive more annual returns from risk adjustment (Barber & Odean, 2000). It was also found that while making a portfolio, females try to mitigate the risk (Olsen & Cox, 2001). While selecting mutual funds, women have a tendency to exhibit a high risk-tolerant attitude in contrast to men, which can be partially explained by knowledge discrepancies (Dwyer, Gilkeson, & List, 2002). Women have a propensity towards investment strategies that are conservative, and the low projected benefits of retirement can be attributed to low-risk preferences (Watson & McNaughton, 2007). As a result, the impact of the spouse determines how retirement assets are allocated based on gender. It was found that low-risk aversion is more common among male spouses compared to female spouses (Arano, Parker, & Terry, 2010). Investors who are females are less probable to make investments in firms with high risks (Mohammadi & Shafi, 2018). There is a low probability of women holding assets that are riskier than those held by men due to the possibility of lower self-confidence among them (Cup, Fessler, & Schneebaum, 2020).

Apart from other investment decisions, pension plans are also influenced by gender. Research has proved that risk aversion was higher among males as compared to females when they reach their retirement age. This influences the wealth accumulation of an individual, so it can be inferred that females accumulate less wealth due to less risk appetite and having assets of fewer returns (Hariharan, Chapman, & Domian, 2000). Women near retirement are apt to make investments that are more conservative compared to men (Papke, 2004). In an experiment, it was observed that risk-averse women chose annuities for their retirement plans (Agnew, Anderson, Gerlach, & Szykman, 2008).

Idiosyncratic Risk and Gender:

According to prior research, top management's gender affects the risk taken by the firm. It was reported that the quality of financial decisions and risk propensity of male and female management do not differ to a great extent (Johnson & Powell, 1994). However, subsequent research contradicted the findings and concluded that risk aversion exists among female managers, possibly due to differences in decision-making strategies (Powell & Ansic, 1997). Gender disparity in decision-making was also evident for professional investment managers, even after having the same experience and expertise. When female investors experience technological and social jeopardy, they show risk tolerance. They also give significant weight to factors associated with risk, for instance, the probability of uncertainty and loss (Olsen & Cox, 2001). Several pieces of research suggest that women tend to reduce risk by avoiding risky but value-increasing policies (Khan & Vieito, 2013; Palvia, Vähämaa, & Vähämaa, 2020). Vast literature focuses on observing the differences of gender among top executives in their financial decisions and risk attitude. Regarding executive gender, prior research has shown that organizations having female CEOs and CFOs are inclined to employ financial reporting practices that are more conservative, have larger cash holdings, and have a lower probability of issuing debt and making acquisitions than companies with male CEOs and CFOs (Francis, Hasan, Park, & Wu, 2015; Barua, Davidson, Rama, & Thiruvadi, 2010). Male-controlled SMEs generate higher profits than SMEs controlled by females. A lower variation in profits is observed for SMEs controlled by females. This concluded that profit generation was related to the risk taken by SME owners, and since male owners have a high-risk appetite, they took more risk (Watson & Robinson, 2003). The gender of the CEO does not have an impact on management quality. However, a more conservative type of financial reporting is used by female CFOs (Peni & Vähämaa, 2010). On the contrary, (Barua, Davidson, Rama, & Thiruvadi, 2010) found that gender affected discretionary accruals, indicating less absolute discretionary accruals for females. Discretionary accruals are not affected by the gender of the CFO (Ge, Matsumoto, & Zhang, 2011). Financial reporting was found to be more conservative for female CFOs and various firm risks, such as systematic risk, default risk, and litigation risk. Financial reporting is positively affected by gender-diverse senior management (Krishnan & Parsons, 2008; Srinidhi, Gul, & Tsui, 2011). There is a higher probability that executives who are male will issue debt and undertake acquisitions compared to executives who are female (Huang & Kisgen, 2013). Risk aversion and conservatism, depending on gender, result in different corporate decisions. Risks specific to CEOs impacts this conservatism (Francis, Hasan, Park, & Wu, 2015). Earning quality is not influenced by the gender of the CFO and auditor (Nasution & Jonnergård, 2017). Male CFOs are less risk tolerant in making operational

decisions and financial reporting than female CFOs (Liu, Wei, & Xie, 2016). On the contrary, evidence shows that risky activities undertaken by female bank directors were almost the same as those undertaken by male bank directors (Mukarram, Ajmal, & Saeed, 2018)). Female executives were found to have a negative relationship with idiosyncratic and total risk, supporting previous research (Peltomäki, Sihvonen, Swidler, & Vähämaa, 2021). Gender differences were evident among male and female CEOs when cash policies were studied. It was found that female CEOs try to mitigate the risk of the company by holding a large amount of physical cash, and they also adopt policies that decrease their risk (Sah, Adhikari, Krolkowski, Malm, & Nguyen., 2022). This research will study the impact of CEO and CFO gender on a firm's idiosyncratic, systematic, and total risk. The hypothesis for the proposed research are as follows:

H₄: Female CEOs and CFOs negatively affect the total risk of a firm.

H₅: Female CEOs and CFOs have a negative impact on the systematic risk of a firm.

H₆: Female CEOs and CFOs negatively influence the idiosyncratic risk of a firm.

2.2. Affiliation to a Political Individual or Party

Defining Political Connections

According to (Faccio & Lang, 2002), a firm is politically affluent if it has connections with some politicians or even a single politician, and that individual/individuals has large stakes in the company or belongs to a top managerial position such as the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and is (i) a parliamentarian themselves, (ii) a minister, or (iii) related to a government official.

I. Relations with Parliamentary Representatives

There are two ways a company could be linked to a parliamentarian. At least one of their senior executives is a member of the country's parliament. (Claessens et al., 2000) and (Faccio & Lang, 2002) describe top executives as the company's president, vice president, or CEO. Second, corporations are considered affluent if at least one of their key shareholders is a parliamentarian. A person is said to be a substantial shareholder in a company if they can control at least 10% of the firm's shareholder votes, either directly or indirectly.

II. Relationships with a Minister or the President

There are three ways in which a company might be linked to a minister or the president. To begin with, the minister is a top executive, such as a CEO. Second, that minister

may be a substantial stakeholder with 10% or more of the company's stock. Finally, any minister's family member may be the firm's senior executive or main shareholder.

III. Firms with Close Ties to a Prominent Government Official

These forms of political ties are difficult to define since they do not fit into a single category and lack the definitional impartiality outlined in the first two situations. These are thus classified as a separate category and include ties sought through (i) Alliances that are considered if they are highlighted in the Economist, Forbes, or Fortune (ii) Former presidents and ministers (including relationships with their relatives), (iii) senior executive positions held by current politicians who have now left the firm, (iv) relationships with out-of-country politicians, and (v) finally, firm's known alliances with political parties.

Implications of Political Connections

The economic-political works have extensively observed that political connections are precious capital to distinct enterprises which have a beneficial influence on economic success (Faccio, 2010; R. Fisman, 2001a; Saeed et al., 2015). Political ties can provide a variety of benefits, such as privileged access to government subsidies or special handling by government-owned businesses (Backman, 2001; Dinç, 2005a; Faccio, 2010; Infante & Piazza, 2014; Li et al., 2008; Shleifer & Vishny, 1993, 1994a), proclivity in the award of government contracts (Tahoun, 2014), decreased regulation of firms or negative regulatory verdicts for competitors (Stigler, 2021), enhanced performance (Boubakri et al., 2012; Du & Girma, 2010), greater chances of bail-out (Faccio, 2006), and a better probability of firm securing government subsidies (Zhang et al., 2014). Saeed et al. (2019) discover that political ties made through firm owners are more advantageous for firms. Similarly, Agrawal & Knoeber (2001a) show that US firms with strong political agendas recruit directors whose political credentials will assist the firms in dealing with bureaucracy and politicians. Ding et al. (2015) state that board chairpersons close to retirement age are more conservative and therefore less driven by political or economic objectives.

The study by Goldman, E., Rocholl, & So, (2009) placed a lot of emphasis on the political relationships of the board of directors. The authors claim that these political relationships provide advantages that benefit everyone and cause no damage, such as offering knowledge about how government bureaucracy should be operated. It is critical to examine the effects of ubiquitous connectivity on the value of publicly traded US enterprises, particularly those that

are less favorable. As a result, the purpose of their research was to determine if the examples are merely a small number of unusual occurrences in which politically linked boards may have had an influence on value, or if they are the start of a much larger, more prevalent problem. Their investigation identified a favorable anomalous stock return following the announcement of the nomination of a person with political ties to the board.

Politically connected enterprises enjoy extensive government support and protection from the consequences of economic downturns, including investment failure. This may lead to the corporation engaging in high-risk operations.

Executives and board members with political links may be more ready to take risks because they anticipate receiving government support. Because the company's profitability is often the major aim in its evaluation, it may place a specific emphasis on achieving attractive artificial performance indicators by taking on excessive risk (Park et al., 2006). Younger CEOs are more inclined to operate firms with stronger political links because they are aware of the growing government support associated with their companies' political stance. Similarly, (Boubakri, Mansi, et al., 2013) indicated that risk-taking is higher for politically connected corporations and tougher firms over weaker ones. Opponents who are not politically linked ought to incur fewer risks, in accordance (Otchere et al., 2020). A lack of clear and tacit assurances from the government might influence competitors in other sectors to take a cautious approach to invest. However, Boubakri, Cosset, et al. (2013) emphasize that the government's control over firms reduces their inclination to take risks. According to (Hleifer et al. (1996), the government's objectives are economic growth and maintaining its electoral dominance, hence it is less probable that it will make hazardous investments. With the government engaged, businesses would likely adopt a more cautious stance (Fogel et al., 2008).

Theoretical Background

Managers may strive to redirect company resources away from the interests of shareholders if there are no incentives to do so, according to Jensen & Meckling (2019b)'s agency theory. Because their investment horizon is shorter than that of shareholders and their wealth is less diverse, these private advantages influence managers' investment risk decisions (John et al., 2008), forcing them to skip initiatives with a positive net value (Wright et al., 1996).

Along with these agency concerns, current research has revealed a possible link between political institutions and managers' investment risk decisions. In his "twin agency model," (Stulz, 2005) proposes a theoretical framework to explain the link between management

decision-making, managerial distraction, and government takeover (predation). Stulz argues that government activities such as excessive regulation, bribery requests, and asset seizures have a considerable influence on management decision-making by modifying the business environment. Managers may become more risk-averse in situations where governmental expropriation is common (under permissive political constraints). Durnev & Fauver (2008) present a global study that captures the multifaceted nature of state interference (including elements such as the risk of expropriation, the extent of property rights, political constraints on policymakers, and corrupt practices), and they show how government predatory policies (such as profit expropriation and bribe extraction) interact with managerial incentives to shape firms' policies and influence managerial risk-taking behavior (John et al., 2008). Caprio et al. (2013) use firm-level data from 109 different nations to provide more evidence on the effects of government expropriation on enterprises' inclination to maintain liquid assets. They demonstrate that company owners are more willing to invest in less liquid assets such as real estate, equipment, and plants to raise the cost of political and administrative exploitation. Corporate executives are more prone to avoid taking risks under these circumstances.

The Motivation for Corporate Political Involvement

Given the pervasiveness of corporate politics, it is legitimate to start studying it from the scratch. Existing research has identified four major kinds of corporate political action (CPA) antecedents: business, industry, issue, and institutional influences (Hillman et al., 2004).

Our primary focus is on managerial influence. Another antecedent of CPA with a behavioral focus is senior management's political position. In (Blumentritt, 2003)'s words, "managerial attitude may be more essential than the number of resources maintained for negotiation." Similarly, the findings of Cook & Barry (1995)'s study on CPAs in small enterprises provide weight to management theories on the vital role of CPAs. "We were particularly astonished by how large a role subjective, cognitive element played in impact processes," they remark. Burris (2001) explored whether an organization's contribution patterns mirrored those of its top managers to further study the subject of managerial influence. Based on 1980 election data, she determines that business PACs support both parties, but senior managers are more likely to favor the Republican Party. She concludes that when managers are compelled to play the cards handed to them by shareholders under a fiduciary commitment, they are more motivated to do so as individuals than as corporate entities.

Past Literature

There has been little research on the relevance of political relationships and their implications on firm value. Three studies show how political ties affect firm value in nations with loose legal systems: (Faccio, 2006, 2007; R. Fisman, 2001a). R. Fisman (2001b) examines Suharto-related enterprises in Indonesia and finds that their value declined after frequent assertions about the president's poor health. According to Faccio (2006)'s research on political relationships across numerous nations, the bulk of politically related enterprises is listed in countries with high levels of corruption and an ineffective judicial system. She goes on to show how the worth of these corporations rises when their CEOs enter politics. She learns, however, that this latter assertion is supported by a sample of companies from corrupt countries. According to research by Faccio (2007), local businesses become less valuable when news of a politician's untimely death is made public. The last example of how relationships create value is provided by (Faccio, 2006), Masulis, and McConnell (2006) who show that businesses with political links are more likely to receive government bailouts.

There is no evidence of political bias in the United States, according to several types of research. For instance, Roberts (1990a) shows that the value of enterprises located in the senator's home state declined following the death of a senator who served as the senior Democrat on the Senate Armed Services Committee. But he shows that this holds true for companies that gave to the senator's campaign as well as those that didn't. According to Kroszner & Stratmann (1998a), interest-group political action committees (PACs) contribute more to members on relevant House committees than competitor PACs. According to Agrawal & Knoeber (2001a), firms with deeper links to the government often have more political directors. Furthermore, Moskowitz & Benmelech (2007) found evidence that incumbents with political influence exploited legislation against usury to keep their rivals out of the market in research that examined usury laws in the nineteenth century across numerous American states.

This claim cannot be supported by three donor data-based research. Among these are papers by (Knight, 2006; Shon, 2006a; Stratmann & Verret, 2015). Stratmann & Verret (2015) analyze Senator Jim Jeffords' choice to leave the Republican Party and join the Independent Party in 2001. She offers an illustration of how this incident damages companies that back Republicans. According to her research, it is unclear if the relationship is casual—that is, whether corporations support politicians whose fundamental beliefs align with their own—or whether contributions have any effect on the behavior of elected officials.

Knight (2006) investigates many stocks that analysts say would thrive in the years after the 2000 presidential election under the Bush and Gore administrations. His purpose is to show how stock prices accurately represent the worth of policy platforms. The key conclusion of Knight (2006) is that firms in sectors that stand to gain from a Bush administration would contribute more money to the Bush campaign. Knight also utilizes the information given by these companies to help the industry classification used by financial analysts. As a result, his data cannot be utilized to indicate that links produce or contribute to future financial benefits. Conversely, Shon (2006a) investigates donations just at the sector level and concludes that corporations in Republican-donating industries saw a rise in stock prices following Bush's election victory in 2000.

State owners may have tremendous incentives to falsify financial documents to conceal information about how their enterprises are operated. To privatize big SOEs, governments often issue shares with offer conditions based on political purposes. Even though the transactions incur some costs, Jones et al. (1999) and Keloharju et al., (2008) discover that privatizing governments rely on these securities to fulfill political goals such as winning over middle-class voters. This data adds credence to Perotti (1995)'s and Biais & Perotti, (2002) underpricing theories. Furthermore, when large-scale share-issuance privatization programs first debut, national stock markets are usually opaque and illiquid, allowing state owners to conceal firm-specific information (Megginson & Netter, 2001). According to Megginson et al. (2004), governments with greater economic control are more likely to divest state-owned enterprises in order to broaden the pool of investors in the public capital market through equity issues rather than negotiating asset sales to a chosen group of buyers who are unwilling to buy a sizable stake unless "there is a stronger commitment that they will be able to maintain ownership...without undue government intervention." Furthermore, they found that privatized governments generally sell more profitable industries by issuing a share offering to get political support.

Many authors, including Lindbeck, (1976), North, (1990), and Olson (1993) have suggested that economic policies are a mirror of politicians' goals to obtain power and resources. According to previous research, governments want control over businesses so they may give above-market wages, favoritism, subsidies, and other perks to their followers in exchange for their support, votes, and political contributions e.g., (la Porta et al., 2002; Shleifer & Vishny, 1994b).

According to Chaney et al. (2011) research, politically prominent enterprises have worse quality earnings than other companies. Leuz & Oberholzer-Gee, (2006) emphasize the same point, claiming that "high levels of openness and public attention may reveal political favors of questionable legality." Companies operating in places with lax rules, for example, frequently have access to related-party transactions that benefit prominent insiders and political supporters. According to Shleifer & Vishny, (1994b) and la Porta et al., (2002), among others, the expropriation of minority investors by dominant owners remains the primary agency conflict in enterprises outside of the United States and the United Kingdom.

As politics becomes increasingly important on corporate boards, the value of independent directors with legal and political expertise will surge. According to Agrawal & Knoeber, (2001b), attorneys and individuals with political expertise assist the firm with their understanding of governmental procedures and insight into anticipating governmental operations. Furthermore, they may work more proactively to urge the government to support the firm's interests or to avoid measures that would be damaging to the organization. In other words, they contend that these directors are politically accountable. Politics plays a significant role when trade policy opens previously closed foreign markets, the government is a significant customer, and regulatory actions by the Food and Drug Administration, the Environmental Protection Agency, or the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission may have serious repercussions. These are only a few instances of how politics plays a role in these circumstances.

According to the literature on international business (IB), political ties not only impact the performance of the company and integrity, but also go in conjunction with immorality, which "tends to produce inefficiencies, elevates ambiguity, and raises costs" for cross-border corporate activities (Habib & Zurawicki, 2002). Additionally, the IB literature has demonstrated how politics in general, and corporate political interactions, regularly influence global business practices (Smith-Hillman & Omar, 2005). This is concerned with how political factors influence multinational businesses' (MNEs') strategic decisions (Faccio et al., 2006; Habib & Zurawicki, 2002; Simon, 1984).

Even though corporate political links are a worldwide phenomenon and the IB literature has acknowledged the complex relationship between MNEs and society, research on the interaction of MNEs and politics, corrupt practices, and corporate social responsibility is still in its early stages (Rodriguez et al., 2006).

According to Shleifer & Vishny, (1997), large shareholders have the incentive to maximize their own earnings at the expense of other owners. Fama & Jensen (1983) and Morck et al. (1988) provide theoretical and empirical support for the claim that mixed ownership and control increase agency conflicts. However, because large shareholders may closely oversee management, concentrated ownership may have advantages Shleifer & Vishny (1997). According to Demsetz & Lehn (1985), controlling owners have a strong motivation to reduce agency difficulties and increase firm value. To put it another way, consolidated ownership balances the interests of controlling and noncontrolling shareholders. According to S. J. Grossman & Hart (1986), moving business ownership away from managers enhances transaction costs since management ownership has the ability to eliminate agency conflicts.

The relationship between founding family ownership and profits quality, as well as agency theory, in which family members rob other shareholders of money by falsifying accounting results, may be relevant Jensen & Meckling (2019a). Previous research looked at the relationship between various aspects of ownership structure and profitability standards. Earnings are especially useful for East Asian companies with less concentrated ownership (Fan & Wong, 2002). Francis et al. (2005) find lower earnings response coefficients (ERCs) for corporations with uneven voting rights in the United States. According to Warfield et al. (1995) study of the relationship between management ownership and earnings quality, managers are less likely to declare accounting results that deviate from the real terms of underlying economic transactions when managerial ownership is larger. The centralization and direction impact of founding family ownership is expected to have two opposing effects on the supply and demand for high-quality profitability. Family members will almost certainly exploit revenues for their personal benefit to the detriment of other proprietors.

Bertrand et al. (2004) give a different viewpoint on the types of interactions that may exist between politicians and corporations. They look at whether the politically connected business elite takes various actions in order to win over politicians. The key argument of this alternate view is that, just as firms may win financially from political favors, politicians' chances of (re)election can be positively impacted by favorable economic occurrences.

According to Nordhaus (1975), there is a substantial body of research on political business cycles that has called attention to the ability of incumbent governments that may employ economic policy instruments in order to influence election outcomes. For instances, see to (A. F. Alesina & Sachs, 1986) or (A. Alesina & Rosenthal, 1995). While incumbent politicians

may utilize their financial clout to boost their prospects of being re-elected, they may also stand to gain from corporate business decisions. Employment is one such company decision that might have an influence on numerous re-election results. Voters assess the overall job situation substantially when selecting whether or not to reappoint an incumbent legislator, as per prior studies (see for example (Wolfers, 2002)). As a result, a company executive who wishes to keep an incumbent politician in office may postpone big layoffs or facility closures until after the election or increase recruiting in the final weeks before the election.

Shleifer & Vishny (1994c) have only a tenuous link with the assumption that corporations and politicians trade favors. Shleifer & Vishny (1994c), on the other hand, introduced this notion in the context of state-owned firms. Bertrand et al. (2004) concentrate their research on publicly listed companies whose CEOs may have personal ties to politicians but are not directly controlled by the government. According to Khawaja & Mian (2004), who agree with Shleifer & Vishny (1994c), corruption exists in government-controlled firms (including banks), which enriches well-connected politicians.

Several studies have been conducted on political donations and election outcomes e.g., (Coate, 2004; G. M. Grossman & Helpman, 1996; Snyder Jr, 1990). It has been difficult for such research to distinguish between politicians' motivations to do particular favors for their contributions and their alignment of political beliefs with business organizations. Given this and simultaneity bias e.g., (Grenzke, 1989; Silberman & Durden, 1976), it has been difficult to determine whether donations have a significant influence on political decision-making because politicians adhere to their ideology e.g., (Chappell, 1982) or because contributions are used to forge "comforting" connections between politicians and specific donors e.g., (Kroszner & Stratmann, 1998b; Stratmann, 1995). Event research strategies have been employed to answer these challenges in academia, with varying degrees of success e.g., (Ansolabehere et al., 2004; D. Fisman et al., 2012; Roberts, 1990b; Shon, 2006b; Stratmann, 1995).

The second group of research examines how special interests influence economic results rather than specifically political donations. According to the findings, firms have tremendous incentives to interact with politicians, and these ties have an impact on economic results by influencing the institutional environment e.g., (Acemoglu, 2005; Krueger, 1974; Morck et al., 2005). There are very certainly many more ways to influence politics. For example, incumbents have the motivation to resist financial growth since it increases competition (Rajan & Zingales,

2003). In order to secure their rents, they would use political channels to hinder financial progress.

In addition, there is proof that individuals with political clout may be given preference when applying for loans in developing nations. Khwaja & Mian (2005) discovered that politically connected enterprises—those with an active director—borrow twice as much and have default rates that are 50% higher than control firms. They did this using loan-level data for Pakistan. Additionally, linked businesses only take out loans from banks that the government owns. For Thai lending trends, Charumilind et al. (2006) provide similar findings. Cole (2009) discovered that politicians frequently exert influence on state-owned banks, and Dinç (2005b) discovered the same thing in the case of India for a broader population of developing nations.

Political institutions impact corporate governance and company ownership arrangements, which has a secondary effect of encouraging risk-taking. Roe (2005), for example, indicates that when there are few checks and balances in existence, ownership concentration increases. As a result, controlling shareholders will put more pressure on management to take more risks. Furthermore, managers are likely to take more chances in more autocratic regimes because labor unions and other interest organizations may impose less risk-taking on managers, and because these interest groups have less sway under more constrained governments e.g., (Pagano & Volpin, 2005; Roe, 2005). These reasons support the view that political institutions and economic risk-taking are incompatible.

Hypotheses:

In this analysis, we look at the link between firm risk and political party affiliation among CEOs and CFOs of listed firms in EAGLE economies. Given the preceding literature, we may assume that there is a strong link between firm risk and CEO and CFO political party affiliation.

H₇: There exists a significant relationship between affiliation to a political party of CEOs and CFOs and a firm's total risk.

H₈: There exists a significant relationship between affiliation to a political party of CEOs and CFOs and a firm's systematic risk.

H₉: There exists a significant relationship between affiliation to a political party of CEOs and CFOs and a firm's idiosyncratic risk.

There is no literature on the association between systemic risk and political party affiliation. Systematic risk is the risk inherent in the entire market, and its link with an individual (CEO or CFO) is, in our opinion, invalid.

2.3. Risk and Insider Ownership

In the following section, we present literature on the association between risk and insider ownership. We provide a theoretical background on the relation and the subjective conclusions reached by researchers. Afterward, we note the studies done by researchers using non-market-based measures of firm risk and its relation with insider ownership. Subsequently, we review the analyses done by researchers using market-based measures of firm risk (total risk & idiosyncratic risk). Lastly, we present the hypotheses keeping in view all the facts from the literature presented.

Theoretical Background

The separation of ownership and control, in accordance with agency-based models, encourages managers to utilize firm resources in ways that benefit them at the expense of external shareholders (Ghosh et al., 2007). The cost to a "principal" (a corporation, individual, or collection of people) when the principal chooses or contracts an "agent" to act on its behalf is known as agency cost. Since the two parties have distinct interests and the agent has access to more information, the principal cannot directly ensure that its agent always acts in the principal's best interests.

It is worth pointing out that Means (2017) originally suggested a relation between ownership structure and risk, and Mosen Jr and Downs (1965) and Mosen et al. (1968) hypothesized the association. They contend that due to the asymmetry between risk-taking and rewards, the ability of owners and managers to pursue divergent goals is made possible by the separation of ownership and management. When it comes to taking risks, this asymmetry manifests as larger incentives and expectations for the owners than for the management. Managers opt to involve in low-risk ventures in order to safeguard the non-diversifiable capital they have put in the company. On the other hand, owners choose riskier projects to increase the value of the call option built into their share ownership.

Insider ownership is the proportion of stock held directly by company directors, managers, and other management personnel through exercising employee stock options or through private corporations (Bauer et al., 2021). The compatibility of managers' and shareholders' interests determines how much risk an organization will take (Chen et al., 1998). The greater the

managers' ownership of a firm, the more closely their interests coincide with those of the shareholders, giving them a strong incentive to take on additional risk in order to maximize the value of their call and put options. To increase the value of their stakes, managers could opt for riskier investment options or underinvest in initiatives with positive net present values (Jensen & Meckling, 2019; Myers, 1977). Unless they are properly motivated or are subject to adequate monitoring, such as pressure from managerial labor markets, managers may opt for non-value-maximizing strategies (Fama, 1980). Mid-sized blockholders may appear to lessen the conflict of interests between one significant shareholder, who favors less risky investments, and small, non-voting owners when a part of small, diverse shareholders abstain from voting. (Dhillon & Rossetto, 2015).

On the other hand, Chun and Lee (2017) state that managers frequently have the freedom and motivation to implement policies and procedures that favor them at the expense of shareholders. Therefore, in the absence of monitoring and alignment of incentives, managers with employment stability and income connected to a single company would act in a risk-averse manner. Smith and Stulz (1985) contend that managers become more risk-averse and more inclined to employ hedging and other risk-reduction methods as their ownership grows. This is because the managers may not possess well-diversified portfolios and will, therefore, have inducements to decrease the riskiness of the company's returns. Meanwhile, Vishny (1988) states that agency costs like management entrenchment typically result in reduced company profitability and less risk-taking by the firm. When ownership is dispersed, managers may have encouragement to follow strategies that do not capitalize on stockholders' wealth. Such actions will have an impact on both the financial risk and the operating risk (by employing resources inefficiently). Barton and Gordon (1987) proclaim that "top managers would prefer to finance a firm's need from internally generated funds rather than from external creditors." Chaganti and Damanpour (1991) result back this statement.

Owners of private companies may invest a significant percentage of their own wealth in only one private company. Large investments give them a sizable ownership share, which lowers agency costs but also subjects them to the idiosyncratic risk of the firm. Rational owners will expect larger returns on their investments to compensate for this risk exposure (Müller, 2011). Bitler et al. (2005) show that owner-managers in riskier businesses and those with less wealth assume a smaller ownership stake. The ownership structure is a key factor in business performance and growth thus it is crucial to understand how different ownership structures impact corporate risk-taking behavior (John et al., 2008).

Han and Suk (1998) discovered that managerial ownership is positively correlated with stock returns, contrary to Chaganti and Damanpour (1991)'s finding that there is no association between managerial ownership and stock returns. According to Panousi and Papanikolaou (2012), the financial crisis that occurred between 2008 and 2009 may have been significantly influenced by managerial risk aversion. Investment decreased far more in companies with more insider ownership, despite the fact that the rise in company-centered uncertainty was equivalent across the board. If the investment-risk relationship is the result of inadequate managerial stock diversity, managers may be eroding stockholder value by rejecting high idiosyncratic risk but positive present value ventures.

Wright et al. (2002) argue that when managers increase their equity ownership, non-value-maximizing, risk-reducing methods may be pushed in addition to lucrative risk-expanding company tactics. Agrawal and Mandelker (1987) have similarly suggested that risk-reducing corporate tactics may be adopted by managers with small equity holdings since they may well benefit their own personal interests. However, with ownership incentives, managers could be more inclined to acquire businesses that increase risk. Compared to managers with a more diverse investment portfolio, those who hold a large portion of their portfolio in the shares of their bank are likely to be more conservative (Smith & Stulz, 1985).

Although Agent CEOs personal investment portfolios may be well diversified, they put more human capital at risk when funding risky ventures (Eisenmann, 2002). Graham et al. (2013) use psychometric tests given to executives to show that personality qualities including risk aversion, impatience, and optimism are connected to company policy. Agent CEOs confront the likelihood of discharge if they aid risky ventures that flop, even if their choices were logical unlike owner-managers, who usually confront no actual risk of being fired because they hold enough shares to nominate loyal board members (Salancik & Pfeffer, 1980). When a risky investment succeeds, agent CEOs experience different outcomes than owner-managers. The value of the agent CEOs' stock holdings, including any options, and incentive payments will rise as a result of their firms' increased financial success.

If the corporate control markets operate properly, managers should be encouraged to act in the owners' best interests (Gürsoy & Aydođan, 2002). Shleifer and Vishny (1986) argue that managerial operations can be monitored and controlled by large shareholders. Therefore, they are responsible to contribute to firm operations. Demsetz and Lehn (1985) argue that insiders' actions are harder to track in companies operating in unpredictable conditions, which increases

the advantages of ownership. Wright et al. (1996) hypothesize that due to their motivation to boost company value through the encouragement of risk-taking activities, institutional owners have a significantly positive impact on risk-taking. Himmelberg et al. (2000) document that even in publicly listed companies, insiders own a sizable portion of the company. They also conduct a cross-country investigation and discover that insider ownership is lower in nations with better investor protection standards.

It is difficult to predict how ownership concentration affects risk-taking since the best balance between the benefits and drawbacks of greater ownership must be struck (Paligorova, 2010). According to many studies, the concentration of ownership results in the majority of stockholders expropriating wealth (La Porta et al., 1999). In a country where the legislative framework is insufficient to protect minority shareholders' rights, controlling owners may use company resources for their own gain (Li et al., 2015). Supposing the common stock of a company as a call option, shareholders are more likely to engage in higher risk-taking behavior at the toll of creditors if they cannot scrutinize shareholders (Jahmani & Ansari, 2006). Large stock possession may levy possible costs on the business too (Gürsoy & Aydoğan, 2002). A deficiency of diversification on the part of a substantial stock owner will endanger him to needlessly high risks. As he controls the tactical decisions of the business, he may decide against lucrative ventures on the basis of total risk, instead of simply assessing the projects in terms of their systematic risk. To the degree they can diversify, owners are more likely to accept comparatively higher risks than managers.

Wright et al. (1996) made the argument that large stockholders may influence a company's risk-taking behavior, which may have an impact on the firm's capacity to contend and ultimately its endurance. In this context, Whitley (2000) argues that variations in corporate governance significantly affect a company's willingness to take risks and, as a result, its capacity to innovate. Stockholders are more motivated to boost a firm's profit by embarking on riskier ventures as their ownership grows (Paligorova, 2010). Focusing a large amount of their capital on one company may compel large stock owners to operate their business from a more conservative stance than if they had a diversified collection of companies' stocks.

Some studies have used non-market-based measures of risk to assess the association between insider ownership and risk. According to many studies, businesses with less concentrated ownership fund riskier initiatives, such as R&D and high-ability demanding operations (Carlin & Mayer, 2000; John et al., 2008; Laeven & Levine, 2009). Kim and Lu (2011) inspect the

R&D of firms because it is risky and discretionary as a measure of risk and to recognize a route through which CEO ownership impacts firm value. They find that except if alleviated by robust External Governance, large share ownership can lower the value of the company by preventing the CEO from taking risks and enforcing his position. Jahmani and Ansari (2006) find no substantial correlation between management ownership, taking risks, and company performance using thirty randomly chosen businesses from four industries and accounting indicators for risk. Using a sample of 137 manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, Erkaningrum (2013) discovers that insider ownership is negatively impacted by business risk, which they defined as the standard deviation of the difference between operating income divided by total assets. Additionally, they claim that insider ownership and financial policy optimization reduce firm risk.

The market-based measure of risks and Insider Ownership

The other strand of literature uses the market-based metrics of firm risk known as total risk and idiosyncratic risk. The relationship among insider ownership with risk-taking at financial holding firms was examined by Belkhir (2005). He contends that insider ownership and firm risk are negatively correlated at low levels and a positive correlation exists at greater ones. The linear formulation demonstrates that overall risk rises as insider ownership does and according to the piecewise linear specification, insider ownership levels above 25% are the only levels at which there is an increase in bank risk. According to Gadhoum and Ayadi (2003), the ownership structure has a complex and non-linear connection that is negatively associated with risk-taking. According to McConnell and Servaes (1990), the risk-taking of a company increases till insider ownership goes to roughly 40% to 50% of outstanding shares. Meanwhile, Morck et al. (1988) state that as insider ownership surges up to 5%, risk-taking of a firm increases, then reduces as insider ownership approaches 25%, and again rises at greater insider ownership levels.

Hill and Snell (1988) show a positive connection between the total risk and insider ownership of a firm. While Glosten and Harris (1988) claim there is an insignificant correlation between insider ownership and stock volatility, Chiang and Venkatesh (1988) find a positive link between the two. Sarin et al. (1996) note that wider stock returns volatility and less quoted depth are both related to a larger insider and institutional ownership. John et al. (2008) contend that projects with lower risk are preferred by undiversified large owners who are thought to prevail in countries with insufficient investor protection. In their study of the relationship between board size and future firm risk in Chinese companies, Haider and Fang (2016)

examined the role that large shareholders played. They came to the conclusion that, regardless of board size, large stockholders directly influence management's choices with regard to future firm risk. Furthermore, they found no evidence that ownership concentration had a moderating effect in the relationship between board size and future firm risk.

According to Chun and Lee (2017)'s analysis of the connection between ownership structure and corporate risk-taking in Japan over the study period of 2000–2010, when a company has growth potential, concentrated ownership or ownership by strongly connected groups influences the company's risks in a convex manner and encourages management to take a greater risk. Although, it doesn't appear as though ownership by financial organizations like insurance firms and banks has an effect on corporate risk. Moreover, in contrast to the traditional entrenchment argument, they state that as management ownership increases, managers take more risks. In an effort to maximize their short-term gains, foreign investors continually support business risk-taking and do not lead corporate investment in a conservative path in an effort to maximize their short-term benefits. Additionally, they point out that local institutions like investment trusts and pension funds have little bearing on the firm's level of risk or value.

Wright et al. (2002) use listed companies that are making large acquisitions and focus on management preferences, ownership incentives, and changes in firm risk brought on by takeovers. They assert that CEO option holdings may be continuously and directly associated with risk-enhancing acquisition tactics, but there may be a non-linear link across CEO equity and risk-changing corporate strategy. According to Eisenmann (2002), the tendency of risk-taking and CEO stock ownership are positively correlated.

Aside from that, Saunders et al. (1990) observe that banks that are administered by stockholders are more inclined to take chances than banks that are run by managers. Lee (2002) used a sample of 65 bank holding firms and find significant and consistent evidence that stockholder-managed banks with bigger assets size and lower stock-return volatility have more risk-taking incentives relative to banks that are managed by managers. Sullivan and Spong (2007) find that when an individual has a significant amount of his money connected to the bank, he has a strong incentive to supervise the bank's management, making hired-manager institutions less risky. Furthermore, they discover that hired managers who own equity in the bank boost the bank's total risk. Laeven and Levine (2009) also record a positive connection between risk-taking and ownership in banks.

According to Gürsoy and Aydoğan (2002) research on the risk-taking practices of non-financial businesses listed on the Istanbul Stock Exchange, ownership structure, ownership concentration, and ownership mix significantly influence company risk and corporate performance. They reveal that very concentrated and less diversified companies have a greater risk. They also show that government-owned firms in their sample have a higher risk, although they are on average greater in size, meanwhile, family-owned businesses have a lower risk. Using a wide cross-country sample, Paligorova (2010) discovers a positive link between firm risk-taking and stock ownership of the largest shareholder. He also finds that family stockholders refrain from engaging in risky conduct as their ownership rises, unlike financial and industrial firms. Investors with diversified portfolios are the only drivers of this outcome. Sakawa et al. (2021) study the relationship in Japan over the period 2007 and 2019 and the reason that foreign stockholders encourage corporate risk-taking while relational shareholders do not.

Amihud and Lev (1981) report that when assessing merger probability, inside managers with significant company capital holdings are less driven by risk aversion factors. Chen et al. (1998) propose an inverse association between managerial ownership and firm risk. Chen and Steiner (1999) discover that management ownership has a considerably positive influence on the level of risk. Downs and Sommer (1999) state that the risk-taking tendency of managers may be determined by how close managers' interests line up with those of the owners. They examine the link between insider ownership and risk-taking in the homeowner's insurance sector and conclude that the association among firm risk and insider ownership deteriorates at a greater amount of ownership, providing evidence for the risk subsidy and monitoring premises. Demsetz and Villalonga (2001) note that greater market and firm-specific risk, indicates greater chances to profit from the use of inside knowledge, and, consequently, a superior causation effect that runs from differences in predicted business performance to variations in managers' equity ownership.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Glover and Levine (2017) document that the majority of pay agreements employed by businesses provide that the management must keep a sizeable amount of their wealth in stock and options of their own firm. This compromises the manager's decision-making related to investment and financial policies, exposes him or her to idiosyncratic risk, and harms shareholder value. According to Himmelberg et al. (1999), idiosyncratic risk is reduced when

managers have a significant ownership stake. Exposure to idiosyncratic risk is increased by managerial ownership which renders their portfolios under-diversified. Müller (2011) conducted a study on firms in the US and measure 'exposure' to idiosyncratic risk as the proportion of the owner's total wealth that is invested in the business. They demonstrate that exposure has a notably positive effect on idiosyncratic risk.

Moreover, Florackis et al. (2014) show that management ownership significantly increases firm value for firms with little idiosyncratic risk and no major risk substitution concerns. Meanwhile, there is no such relationship for firms with significant idiosyncratic risk, which is often characterized by larger risk-substitution incentives. Hence they conclude that the usefulness of management ownership as a tool to solve agency issues is minimal for businesses having greater levels of idiosyncratic risk. A study by Florackis et al. (2020) back the argument that the alignment effect of managerial ownership, which is only noticeable in a sample of low idiosyncratic firms, is balanced out by the risk substitution effect in high idiosyncratic firms, which often have more severe risk substitution issues. According to Panousi and Papanikolaou (2012) analysis of publicly listed US corporations, high-powered incentives may encourage managers to exert more effort in their management, but they also expose them to idiosyncratic risk. When idiosyncratic risk increases, risk-averse managers have a tendency to make inferior investment decisions from the standpoint of well-diversified shareholders. If executives receive options as opposed to shares of stock as part of their compensation or if institutional investors make up a sizeable portion of the investor base, the adverse impact of management risk aversion on investments is reduced. Additionally, they empirically show that the relationship between investment and idiosyncratic risk is higher when managers own a greater portion of the company equity.

Institutional owners make the greatest use of the tools at their disposal to mitigate idiosyncratic risks since a lot of them often maintain a sizable number of shares for long-term profits. This enables a company to enhance its future corporate social performance (Oikonomou et al., 2020). Institutional ownership affects market returns and stock volatility. For instance, Sayim and Rahman (2015) found that individual investors do not have as much of a spillover effect on the stock return and variance of the Istanbul Stock Exchange as institutional owners do. Campbell et al. (2001) and Xu and Malkiel (2003) note that there is a connection between idiosyncratic risk and institutional ownership. While Li and Zhang (2021) document that there is a negative correlation between idiosyncratic risk and institutional ownership. Duppati et al. (2022) use a large sample of data from NYSE and NASDAQ listed companies to study the

relationship of innovation and institutional ownership on idiosyncratic risk. They observe that greater level of institutional ownership decreases idiosyncratic risk and the interactions between shareholders who hold large amount of stock and institutional owners significantly reduce idiosyncratic risk.

Ghafoor et al. (2019) investigate companies listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange and approach corporate governance in the framework of internal governance control, based on the composition, structure, and quality of the board, as well as ownership and ownership structure. Their main finding is that idiosyncratic risk and corporate governance are clearly related to one another. Boubaker et al. (2014) examine Cash and voting rights as two facets of corporate governance using ownership concentration as a metric and they discover that while synchronization in French stock returns reduces as large owners' cash flow rights grow, it increases when large shareholders' control rights increase.

Abu-Ghunmi et al. (2015) employ data from Jordan, a nation with insufficient investor protection, and observe that companies with larger ownership concentration have a lower idiosyncratic risk. Their findings demonstrate that the overall effect of higher levels of ownership on idiosyncratic risk is not unconditional. Nguyen et al. (2021) conduct their research in Vietnam and conclude that businesses which are largely government-owned often have lesser idiosyncratic risk reflecting the state's function as a monitor and the managers' lack of risk-taking due to financial and political backing from the state. Additionally, they show that idiosyncratic risk and board size are positively correlated and that there is not a significant relation between idiosyncratic risk and CEO duality or CEO ownership..

Family members frequently hold important executive positions in family-owned businesses and have a strong influence on business strategies. Their sizeable capital encourages them to monitor the firm's performance and thus, greater interest alignment enables them to take calculated risks (Geeta & Prasanna, 2016). Yet so, family businesses face higher systematic and idiosyncratic risk due to their lower level of diversification (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). Rajverma et al. (2019) look at how a firm's profitability, value, and idiosyncratic risk are affected by its ownership structure and dividend distributions. Their findings demonstrate the dominance of family-owned businesses with concentrated ownership. The management's smaller dividend payment results in a decrease in value and an increase in idiosyncratic risk. The study goes on to show that family ownership concentration and family control have an effect on firm performance and risk.

Hypotheses

For our study, we analyze the relationship between firm risk and insider ownership of CEOs and CFOs of listed firms in EAGLE economies. Keeping in view the above literature, we can hypothesize that there is a significant relationship between firm risk and ownership of CEOs and CFOs of the firm.

H₁₀: There exists a significant relationship between CEOs' and CFOs' ownership and total risk

H₁₁: There exists a significant relationship between CEOs' and CFOs' ownership and idiosyncratic risk

H₁₂: There exists a significant relationship between CEOs' and CFOs' ownership and systematic risk

2.4. Narcissism and Risk

In 1898, British psychologist and physician Havelock Ellis became the first to explain the condition of narcissism (Aabo & Eriksen, 2018). The Greek story of Narcissus by Ovid served as an inspiration for this clinical state of obdurate self-love (Rosenthal & Pittinsky, Narcissistic leadership, 2006) in which a young man who becomes obsessed with his reflection ultimately decides that death is the only option (Aabo & Eriksen, 2018). Sigmund Freud further advanced this concept by identifying three main personality types of narcissism which include obsessive personality, narcissistic personality, and erotic personality (Maccoby, 2000). In his article "On Narcissism: An Introduction (1914)," Sigmund Freud said that every person needs a certain amount of narcissism (Rijsenbilt & Commandeur, 2012).

In 1994, narcissism was classified by the American Psychiatric Association as a complex clinical personality condition (Campbell & Foster, 2007). American Psychiatric Association (2013) defines a narcissistic personality disorder as "a persistent pattern of need for admiration, lack of empathy, and grandiosity". Psychologists Raskin & Hal (1979) were the first to develop a psychometric scale called Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI) (Brouwer, 2018). The NPI, a questionnaire containing 54 items, allowed researchers to measure narcissism personality as a metric where people can range from low to high scores, instead of a binary state of an extreme clinical disorder case (Brouwer, 2018). Later, Emmons (1984) condensed the 54 items to 4 robust items using factor analysis of the scale (Brouwer, 2018). People who are viewed as narcissists may not actually have a narcissistic personality disorder, according to

clinical diagnoses. But these people frequently have personality characteristics that match the clinical definition of NPD (Perez, 2017). Typically, NPD patients struggle with intense emotions of low confidence and self-esteem and attempt to make up for it by being important and having a demeaning attitude. Additionally, NPD patients are unable to accept criticism or rejection, which negatively impacts both their ability to function in society and the people around them, especially given their general disregard for others (Ronningstam & Weinberg, 2013).

In line with earlier research in the field of behavioral corporate finance, this study uses subclinical narcissism which is stated as a personality dimension as a measure on which every individual can be exhibited (Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2007; Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2011; Aktas, Bodt, & Bollaert, 2016). Brown (1997) defines narcissism as “a state of being the center of a loving world in which the individual could act spontaneously and purely out of a desire”, with the dominant concept that “individuals have a need to maintain a positive sense of self, and they engage in ego-defensive behavior in order to preserve self-esteem”. Campbell et al. (2004) states “Narcissism is the degree to which an individual has an inflated sense of self and is preoccupied with having that self-view continuously reinforced”. Rosenthal & Pittinsky, 2006 refer to narcissism as the extent to which a person has magnified self-absorption and self-admiration. Amesa, Rose, & Andersonc (2006) outline narcissism as an exaggerated feeling of one's own importance, a need to be in charge, and a craving for attention. Chatterjee & Hambrick (2007) defines narcissism as “[...] a coherent but multifaceted personality dimension that can be defined as the degree to which an individual has an inflated sense of self and is preoccupied with having that self-view continually reinforced”. Campbell and Foster (2007) highlight the three main features of narcissism: disregarding and having less or nearly no empathy for others, engaging in activities that determine superiority over others, and exaggerated self-opinion and overstated idea of self. Campbell, Hoffman, & Marchisio (2011); Roberts, Woodman, & Sedikides (2018); Rosenthal & Pittinsky (2006) describe narcissism as a personality trait that causes a person's decisions, judgment and aspirations to be motivated by uncompromising arrogance, self-indulgence, and voracious desire for attention and power. Campbell, Hoffman, & Marchisio, (2011) explain narcissism as a multi-contextual, multidimensional, and multilayered concept that is a personality disorder in psychiatry and much of the organizational behavior and social psychology literature examines narcissism as a personality trait that differs among people. The strong urge for self-improvement that

narcissists experience shows up as excessive optimism, self-entitlement, and exaggerated self-promotion (Tamborski, Brown, & Chowning, 2012).

Grandiose views of oneself held by narcissists make them think that they are superior in terms of intelligence, leadership potential, skills, and attractiveness (Gabriel et al., 1994; Farwell & Wohlwend-Lloyd, 1998). Such individuals rely on applause and confirmation for reinforcement of their good self-view along with other people's perceptions of them as superior in addition to their own, as this trait makes them constantly crave attention and adoration (Bogart, Wallace & Baumeister, 2002; Benotsch, & Pavlovic, 2004). According to Brummelman, Thomaes, & Sedikides (2016), narcissists need to be validated since they have a fragile feeling of superiority. According to Bogart, Benotsch, & Pav (2004), narcissism is linked to heightened sensitivity to information about social comparisons. According to Campbell (1999), narcissism is constituted by a need to be among people who are thought to have a high social standing in order to boost one's self-esteem to the point where it gives one a feeling of importance and popularity.

The narcissistic personality, according to Chatterjee & Hambrick, (2011), is paradoxical as narcissistic people admire themselves and yet always need to have this positive self-view reinforced (Aabo & Eriksen, 2018). According to Raskin, Novacek, & Hogan (1991), the defensive competitive component of narcissism contributes to the narcissist's intense demand for outside approval. In addition, narcissists lack compassion and fail to acknowledge or relate to the needs and feelings of other individuals (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). They employ self-control techniques to feel significant and accomplished. Some intrapersonal techniques entail dreaming about power and attributing successful outcomes to one's own actions and talents (Raskin & Novacek, 1991; Campbell & Foster, 2007). Other tactics are interpersonal and making use of other individuals to improve one's perception of oneself. Examples include self-promotional behaviors like boasting, proclaiming oneself, and attracting attention, as well as associating with powerful people and those who look up to them (Chiodo & Buss, 1991; Campbell W. K., 1999). To state their constant, want for attention and acclaim from others, they act impulsively, bravely, and richly (Wallace & Baumeister, 2002). The most significant source of narcissistic supply is admiration, attention, and the confirmation of one's own superiority (Wallace & Baumeister, 2002). The narcissistic individual themselves may be the source of the narcissistic supply, as seen by their exhibitionism and diminution of others (Bogart et al., 2004). Although narcissistic people come across as conceited "on the outside," their grandiose beliefs and actions may really serve as a type of self-protection from ingrained

unfavorable self-evaluations (Rosenthal & Pittinsky, 2006). The public persona that narcissists frequently project may be a cover for their underlying lack of self-regard and insecurities (Kets de Vries, 2004). When a person is of this mindset, it is possible to feel attacked by even the smallest disapproval and they act with denial and irritation to the criticism (Kernis & Sun, 1994; Rhodewalt & Morf, 1998). They struggle to build relationships that go beyond satisfying one's own attention-seeking needs. These characteristics can, in extreme cases, point to a clinical disorder form (Brouwer, 2018). The fact that one's level of narcissism is relatively fixed over time is an important trait of the narcissistic personality (John & Robins, 1994; Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2007).

Overconfidence and hubris, which are both characterized as an overinflated feeling of self-confidence brought on by power and a tendency to probabilistically overestimate one's abilities and knowledge, respectively, are related qualities but are not the same as narcissism (Campbell, Foster, & Goodie, 2004; Galasso & Simcoe, 2011). In contrast to narcissism, which is a comprehensive personality trait that encompasses both behavioral and cognitive components, overconfidence is only related to how reality is perceived (Aktas et al., 2016). Narcissism, according to Chatterjee & Hambrick (2007), consists of "both a cognitive frame and a motivational mechanism - consisting simultaneously of a belief in one's superior skills and an obsessive, continual desire for reinforcement". In addition to having a strong sense of self-importance, narcissistic people are known for using techniques to maintain and improve their sense of superiority (Campbell, Goodie, & Foster, 2004). Despite the differences between narcissism and overconfidence, there are some similarities (Aktas et al., 2016). Narcissism should be considered the more ingrained personality feature because it fosters hubris or overconfidence (Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2007). Campbell, Goodie, & Foster (2004) found that narcissism is connected to overconfidence in a group of university students using a computer-based question test. The idea of narcissism has been philosophically linked to overconfidence and hubris, which are described as exaggerated or extreme overconfidence (Perez, 2017).

According to prior studies, individuals with more narcissistic tendencies may become leaders because of their dominance and heightened drive for social status. Their narcissistic method appears to be effective based on the correlation between narcissism and leadership (Brunell, et al., 2008). Kets de Vries & Miller (1985) explain narcissism in people is what motivates their desire to hold a leadership position. Resick et al. (2009) state that CEO narcissism is a persistent personality trait that describes how much a CEO romanticizes their sense of self-worth and pursues vanity-driven strategic goals in an effort to gain attention and social approval. Leaders

who are narcissists appear to advance rapidly and successfully (Brouwer, 2018). According to Kets de Vries (2004), narcissism "lies at the heart of leadership" and a healthy amount of it is necessary to ascend to the executive level of a firm. One of the least studied, though most complicated, personality traits among executives are narcissism (Brouwer, 2018). The significance of studying CEO narcissism has been emphasized in earlier research (Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2007; Chatterjee & Pollock, 2017). One needs to have a somewhat high level of narcissism in order to become a great leader since narcissistic features might cause someone to believe that they are right (Kets de Vries, 2004). According to Campbell et al. (2004), CEOs with high levels of narcissism are those that have exaggerated self-perceptions and are obsessed with having these perceptions constantly cemented. Carlson et al. (2011) indicate that narcissistic CEOs act in ways that may get praise and appreciation in order to demonstrate their superiority over others and reinforce their exaggerated self-views. "Narcissism conveys a tremendous need to have one's superiority validated on the motivational side," according to their study. The term "CEO narcissism" has the potential to be useful since it connects what we previously thought to be dissimilar features of CEO conduct in business decision-making, such as CEO domination, self-attribution, empire building, etc (Liu & Taffler, 2008). Since CEOs are viewed as special and renowned individuals and hold the top position inside a firm, it is possible that they develop biases in favor of self-worth. A continual stream of affirmation and praise is also given to CEOs, due to which their narcissistic needs are met (Rijsenbilt & Commandeur, 2012). Due to their overwhelming optimism, self-confidence, and an intense need for recognition and adulation, CEOs may do spectacular and attention-getting moves like mergers and acquisitions (Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2007). A high level of narcissism fosters a CEO's subjectively believed desire to pursue personal ambitions in with respect to making strategic decisions (Aggarwal & Samwick, 2003). According to March and Shapira (1987), a CEO's attitude toward risk is influenced by a variety of personality traits, with narcissism being a key factor.

There is still much to learn about the psychological developments that associate CEO personality with strategic impact and performance. Scientists have been proclaiming for the past few years that we are currently experiencing an extraordinarily narcissistic era in which narcissism is spreading like an "epidemic." Recent studies demonstrate a connection between millennials' higher levels of narcissism and social media's continued rise (Twenge & Campbell, 2009; Bergman, Fearington, Davenport, & Bergman, 2011). The Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI) ratings of college students climbed 30% more rapidly between 2002 and 2007

than they did between 1982 and 2007 (Twenge, Konrath, Foster, Campbell, & Bushman, 2008). Nearly 35,000 individuals from a nationally representative sample were questioned by Stinson, et al. (2008) regarding the signs and symptoms of narcissistic personality disorder (NPD). According to statistics, since older persons have lived longer, one could anticipate that they would score higher on prior NPD symptoms. However, scientists discover that NPD declines sharply after age 29, with an inverse association between NPD and age. Twenge & Campbell (2009) stress the significance of comprehending the narcissistic "epidemic" we might be experiencing because of its potential long-term negative effects on society. The amount of confidence in society is rising from a healthy amount to narcissistic self-interest (Brouwer, 2018). A significant issue that requires to be spoken about in light of the rise in narcissism among individuals, in general, is CEO narcissism. The majority of literature focuses on executives' effective leadership, but it is equally important to comprehend the damaging leadership behavior that can result from narcissism (Brouwer, 2018). More recent events, such as the disaster of companies like Enron, Tyco, and Worldcom, have sparked the discussion and consideration of destructive leadership behavior. The need for more empirical research to examine the causes, effects, and potential antecedents of this behavior (Higgs, 2009) is highlighted by these events

The strategic decisions made by managers are interpretations that are modeled as the outcomes of the organization. Due to the complexity of these settings and cognitive limitations, managers' perception is restricted to specific environmental and organizational cues. Cognitive footing and the perception of reality affect decision-making and understanding of the problems. Because of this, the strategic decisions taken reflect the personality of the management; this highly individualized interpretation directs executives' activities. Background characteristics are utilized to forecast and gauge the managers' cognitive foundation and values. For instance, empirical research has demonstrated that Top management team characteristics impact corporate transformation (Wiersema & Bantel, 1992), supporting the claim made by Hambrick and Mason (1984) that manager attributes are predictors of the potential management behavior in a given context. The majority of studies using the "upper echelons" paradigm focus on how executives' typical demographic characteristics affect organizational results (e.g., age or tenure). Therefore, it seems suitable to advance this line of inquiry and incorporate more complex facets of CEO personality (Gerstner et al., 2013; Resick et al., 2009). Researchers have examined personality traits like overconfidence or hubris (Chen, Crossland, & Luo, 2015), narcissism (Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2007; Zhu & Chen, 2015), locus of control (Miller

& Toulouse, 1986), regulatory attention (Gamache, McNamara, Mannor, & Johnson, 2015), temporal attention (Nadkarni & Chen, 2014), and discovered that these qualities significantly influence the outcomes for their firm. The most recent field of study in the higher echelons is the influence of narcissism on a manager's behavior. Recently the concept has been utilized more frequently to characterize management behavior in businesses (e.g., Campbell, Goodie, & Foster, 2004; Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2007; Gerstner et al., 2013). Campbell et al. (2004), in multiple laboratory trials involving university researchers, confirmed that narcissism is a robust indicator of overconfidence. The upper-echelon literature understands narcissism as a central personality feature possessed by CEOs that affects firm results (Kashmiri et al., 2017; Ham et al., 2018). The relationship between CEO characteristics and organizational outcomes is highlighted by the upper-echelon theory (Finkelstein & Hambrick, 1996). According to the notion, a CEO's personality traits serve as cognitive grounds that influence how they absorb information, manage teams, and ultimately relate to strategic decision-making (Hambrick & Mason, 1984).

Successful leadership requires a good degree of narcissism, and managerial narcissism has many desirable qualities (Maccoby, 2007), but it can also have harmful effects if in excess. CEOs having narcissistic personality traits can result in both positive and negative outcomes, according to UE academics (Abatecola and Cristofaro, 2019; Back et al., 2013; Resick et al., 2009). Lubit (2002) made the distinction between "healthy" and "destructive" narcissism. He lists entitlement, lack of lasting attachment to a set of principles, devaluing others, an internal hollowness that motivates them to search for excitement in spite of high risks, lack of apprehension for others, and grandiosity as the defining characteristics of the "destructive narcissist" (Liu & Taffler, 2008). Leaders that are narcissistic often get fixated on acquiring power, position, reputation, and superiority at all costs. They choose to surround themselves with team members who would share their beliefs because they would prefer not to share any authority or face any criticism. Because of this, narcissistic CEOs prefer to blame the organization when anything goes wrong rather than learn much from it. When things don't go their way, they can become angry and be foul and insulting. Given their position of authority, narcissistic leaders have the potential to negatively affect their surroundings and organizations (Kets de Vries, 2004). According to Campbell, Hoffman, Campbell, & Marchisio (2011), narcissistic executives have a chance to succeed in a shorter tenure but are expected to damage their organization's worth in a longer tenure. Additionally, according to Rijsenbilt & Commandeur (2012), CEO narcissism and fraud have a positive association which suggests

the CEO might be capable of influencing the firm's ethical standards and behavior. Narcissists are more likely to transgress moral norms, be strict with their staff, and make hazardous judgments that may be harmful to the firm (O'Reilly III, Doerr, Caldwell, & Chatman, 2014). According to the most recent study, a CEO's level of identification with their organization plays a major role in the linkage between firm performance and CEO narcissism (Reina, Zhang, & Peterson, 2014). The authors contend that CEOs' narcissism will favorably affect business performance when they identify with various components of their corporation, and vice versa. Overconfidence among narcissistic CEOs may lead to systematic underestimation of the worth of the firm they oversee and the returns of their investment ventures. When they have gained sufficient finances, they tend to overinvest, and when they don't, they tend to underinvest (Malmendier & Tate, 2008). Additionally, they can be less willing to issue fresh shares since they believe the market has undervalued their stock (Malmendier & Tate, 2005). Two-thirds of the CFOs that Graham & Harvey (2001) polled claimed that their stock was undervalued. On the plus side, narcissists are innovative, creative, and challenge-seeking individuals (Brouwer, 2018).

Narcissism and Firm Risk

CEO narcissism effects on strategic outcomes have been previously studied, including innovation (Kashmiri et al., 2017), acquisition importance, international modification (Zhu & Chen, 2015), fierceness in accepting technology (Gerstner et al., 2013), and risk-taking (Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2011; Aabo & Eriksen, 2018). Strategic choices and performance outcomes are formally linked to CEO narcissism by Chatterjee & Hambrick (2007). Strategic leadership literature's basic concept is that organizations reflect the unique backgrounds and personalities of their top executives (Finkelstein, Hambrick, and Cannella, 2009). CEOs have special functions; therefore, their personality qualities may show up in their personal preferences and actions. They may influence the firm's risk-taking, together with idiosyncratic risk, total risk, and systematic risk (Brouwer, 2018). Gerstner et al. (2013) provide evidence that this personality trait affects CEOs' willingness to take risks by demonstrating the connection between destructive investment actions and narcissism in relation to innovative technologies.

Various parties involved in a firm have different attitudes on risk, which has been a primary focus of business-related theories (March & Shapira, 1987). The agency theory prominently addresses the topic of risk (Barney & Hesterly, 1996; Beatty & Zajac, 1994). The assumption is that managers are risk-averse, whereas owners seem to view risk in a neutral manner

(Eisenhardt, 1989). Therefore, there is a considerable chance that managers do not act in the manner that owners would desire regarding risk issues (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). However, managers exhibit a high level of risk-taking because they have minimal fear of failing and believe they can control at least some aspects of the risk, conferring the conclusions of empirical studies (Campbell et al., 2004). They believe that taking risks is an essential component of their work and that their abilities and skills allow them to successfully manage risk. Some academics even argue that managers actively manage risk as opposed to merely accepting it as a characteristic of the environment. As a result, managers occasionally accept business offers with a high risk but the potential for a good return (March & Shapira, 1987). Evidently, in this situation, subjective risk assessments are less significant than managers' individual views of danger (March & Shapira, 1987). Recent studies have shown how narcissism affects managerial decision-making on risk-taking actions (Gerstner et al., 2013). The narcissism agency model confirms that narcissists are approach-oriented and are actively seeking out lucrative chances in their surrounding situations (Finkel, et al., 2006) while giving less attention to avoidance strategies that could lessen the likelihood of unfavorable outcomes (Foster, Reidy, & Misra, 2009). Because they have low avoidance motivation and strong approach motivation, narcissism leads to "myopic concentration on reward" (Lakey, Rose, & Goodie, 2008). Their disregard for the potential for significant losses and openness to a wide range of potential outcomes (Campbell, Foster, & Goodie, Narcissism, confidence, and risk attitude, 2004) probably enhance riskier managerial choices (Sanders & Hambrick, 2007). Contrarily, less narcissistic business managers take less risk than narcissistic CEOs and are more likely to focus on lowering discrepancies in results and preventing a possible drop in returns (Lewellen, 2006). A current study followed participants' fictitious investments during the 2008 stock market meltdown and discovered that narcissistic people made riskier decisions and faced bigger losses (Foster, Reidy, & Misra, 2009).

CEO narcissism is becoming more prevalent as data shows that hazardous tactics and investments are more likely to be used by a business when the CEO is more narcissistic, or self-loving and self-appreciative (Wales, Patel, & Lumpkin, 2013; Zhu & Chen, 2015). They engage in risky and bold behaviors and produce extreme performance results (Campbell and Miller, 2011; Emmons, 1987; Judge et al., 2006; Raskin and Terry, 1988) because they have a magnified self-perception and want it to be continually reinforced. Additionally, UE researchers have discovered consistently that narcissistic CEOs are more daring and have riskier tactics, believing higher risk led to higher rewards. The association between risky

methods and CEO narcissism is typically highlighted using three lines of argument based on results from the psychological literature (Emmons, 1987). First, very narcissistic CEOs are driven by an intense urge to command attention by evoking awe and respect (Wales, Patel, & Lumpkin, 2013). This motivates them to follow methods and actions that will gain the attention and admiration of the audience and also serve as a demonstration of leadership (Gerstner, König, Enders, & Hambrick, 2013) (Wales, Patel, & Lumpkin, 2013). Second, extreme self-confidence and superiority in narcissists (Emmons, 1987) cause them to have positively skewed expectations about the results of their decisions (Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2011; Gerstner, König, Enders, & Hambrick, 2013; Wales, Patel, & Lumpkin, 2013). Thirdly, narcissistic CEOs display a high level of self-centeredness and self-interest (Emmons, 1987). Because of this, they are more concerned with obtaining personal gains (Patel & Cooper, 2014) and less concerned with how their choices may affect other people, such as employees or other shareholders (O'Reilly III, Doerr, Caldwell, & Chatman, 2014). There is less possibility that they will serve as "a careful steward of organizational resources," (Patel & Cooper, 2014) which is consistent with the description of narcissists as having a weak avoidance motivation but strong approach motivation (Foster, Reidy, Misra, & Goff, 2011). They exaggerate a project's advantages and underestimate its risks (Gerstner, König, Enders, & Hambrick, 2013).

Narcissistic CEOs overestimate their skills and think their judgments are considerably superior to others (Campbell & Foster, 2007). They are unwilling to take into account disagreements or opposing viewpoints from others due to their high confidence (Kausel, Culbertson, Slaughter, & Leiva, 2015). Campbell, Goodie, & Foster (2004) found that narcissism is linked to both overconfidence and taking risks when they used a computer-based interrogation on a collection of students in a university. According to Campbell et al. (2004), narcissism is a major predictor of arrogance and risk-taking. According to behavioral decision theory, CEOs who are overconfident are more likely to take risky decisions (Nosic and Weber, 2010; Gao and Sudarsanam, 2005). According to the theory, there are three mechanisms that connect CEO overconfidence and risk-taking levels: firstly, an overvaluation of the CEO's own problem-solving abilities (Camerer and Lovallo, 1999); secondly, an underestimation of the firm's resource grants (Shane and Stuart, 2002); and thirdly, an underestimation of the uncertainties the firm is dealing (Kahneman and Lovallo, 1993; March and Shapira, 1987). An overconfident CEO may use these three techniques to perceive riskier decision-making situations than they are (Sitkin and Pablo, 1992). According to Ben-David et al. (2013), CEOs are likewise miscalibrated in the narrow term. According to Malmendier and Tate (2005), overconfidence

is a self-centered bias that causes people to overemphasize their abilities to produce results. In contrast, dispositional optimism, which is applied in a behavioral economics framework, is more related to an optimistic attitude toward life in general (Puri and Robinson (2007)).

In the literature on behavioral finance, the phrases overconfidence and optimism are frequently used virtually interchangeably. So, Campbell et al. (2011) use the term "optimism" and measure it using the Malmendier and Tate (2005) paradigm. Goel and Thakor (2008) contend that the intra-firm competition that encourages (extreme) risk-taking on the part of CEO candidates is the cause of the overrepresentation of overconfidence in the upper echelons. Therefore, overconfident CEOs are more prone to overestimate investment returns and underestimate related hazards (Hirshleifer et al., 2012; Malmendier and Tate, 2005, 2008). In light of this, CEO overconfidence is linked to increased corporate risk-taking (Bharati et al., 2016; Billett and Qian, 2008; Campbell et al., 2007; Galasso and Simcoe, 2011; Hirshleifer et al., 2012; Malmendier and Tate, 2008).

Narcissistic CEOs might expose their confidence and strategic vision by investing in these risky measures in order to draw a "social stage" (Wales, Patel, & Lumpkin, 2013). Due to their higher average rates of delinquency and default, all of these plans have previously been described as bearing higher levels of systemic risk (Black & Hazelwood, 2013) (Young & Torna, 2013). However, narcissistic CEOs are convinced that they can make these policies successful due to their overinflated feeling of self-confidence and superiority (Emmons, 1987) and will therefore pay less attention to the potential dangers and drawbacks. In a similar manner, narcissistic CEOs tend to focus (only) on the possibility of receiving large rewards for themselves while becoming insensitive to the potential negative effects of increasing the inherent riskiness (Foster, Reidy, Misra, & Goff, 2011; Patel & Cooper, 2014). This is because they are self-centered and have strong approaches and weak avoidance motivations (Buyl, Boone, & Wade, 2019). This argument resembles an often made (but unproven) assertion in the literature on CEO narcissism: narcissistic CEOs frequently pursue risky short-term advantages at the price of long-term success (O'Reilly III, Doerr, Caldwell, & Chatman, 2014). CEO reputation, a trait unique to managers, has an impact on the firm's willingness to take risks. These findings are in line with prior research showing how the traits of individual managers influence business results. Both systematic and idiosyncratic risks are positively correlated with CEO reputation (Buyl, Boone, & Wade, 2019). Research findings show that CEOs who have a better reputation take greater risks, particularly idiosyncratic risks. Across all risk indicators (total risk, systematic risk, idiosyncratic risk, levered risk, unlevered risk),

the correlation between CEO reputation and risk-taking is still very strong (Buyl, Boone, & Wade, 2019). This leads to the following three hypotheses:

H₁₃: The narcissism of CEOs and CFOs has a positive relationship with the firm's total risk.

H₁₄: The narcissism of CEOs and CFOs has a positive relationship with the firm's systematic risk.

H₁₅: The narcissism of CEOs and CFOs has a positive relationship with the firm's idiosyncratic risk.

Methodology

This section covers the methodology that is used to perform our research to determine the impact of the aforementioned factors associated with the CEO and CFO on different types of risk. The specification of variables, data, measurement, and model is explained thoroughly.

3.1. Data collection and variables

The required dataset for our study is collected from 50 firms each in the stock market of six Asian countries which include Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Malaysia, China, and Vietnam. To construct our sample, we collect data from the following sources: (i) the data for gender, affiliation to a political party, insider ownership, and financial statements will be obtained from the annually published report of each firm, (ii) the stock price data used for calculating market-based measures of firm risk will be taken from Yahoo Finance, and (iii) the executive data to assess narcissistic personality traits will be collected from annual reports, available executive's speech on the annual report, and public interactions. While collecting our data, we excluded firms with insufficient or missing executive data, penny stocks.

3.2. Independent variables

The independent variables include a firm Executive's gender, affiliation to a political party, inside ownership, and narcissism.

Gender

Gender variable includes the firms' CEO and CFO gender. It is measured as a binary variable by coding it as a 0-1 dummy variable. A firm having a Male CEO and CFO will be coded as 0 and a female CEO and CFO will be coded as 1 at the end of the year.

Affiliation to a political party

Annually published reports of each firm are used to identify their CEO and CFO. The identified executive information was then be compared to other databases which contain politician information. A firm is considered to be affiliated with a political party if its CEO or CFO has any sort of political connections. The variable is then coded as a dummy variable. It will be coded as 0 if there is no affiliation to a political party and 1 if there is affiliation to a political party.

Insider ownership

Insider Ownership represents the number of stocks held by a firm's CEO and CFO. This variable is measured using the information obtained from the annual report of each firm as it mentions the number of firms' stocks in possession of the executives.

Narcissism

Standard questionnaire surveys developed to evaluate personality traits cannot be used to measure narcissism in company executives. Information related to higher management in companies is sensitive and difficult to obtain, therefore other approaches are developed to assess the personality traits of such individuals. The first approach is the Narcissism Score approach, which is related to the narcissistic personality inventory score, as shown by Raskin & Shaw (1988) research. Capalbo, Frino, Lim, Mollica, & Palumbo (2017) also employed this instrument to recognize CEOs with narcissism. This approach evaluates the executive's speech on their yearly report and public dealings, to note the pronouns used by them. The use of pronouns like I, me, myself, and mine indicates that the CEO links the company's accomplishment entirely with his/her own personal efforts. The use of we, us, ours, and ourselves pronouns suggests that the CEO sees the company's accomplishment as a group effort. The following formula will be used to calculate the Narcissism score:

$$Narcissim\ Score = \sum n \frac{(i, me, myself, mine)}{(we, us, ours, ourselves)}$$

The second approach is signature-based in which an individual's signature is used to determine the personality of that individual. Existing psychological literature establishes a relationship between personality and signature area. For example, in 1973, weigenhaft and Marlowe carried out a study where they learned that individuals with a higher sense of privilege, greater self-perception, and extra aspects of the personality aspects we are attracted to typically have larger

signatures (Zweigenhaft & Marlowe, 1973). In the context of our study, the size of the signatures of CFOs and CEOs available from the annual reports are used to determine whether the executive is a narcissist.

3.3. Control variables

To get more accurate results, we controlled for certain variables which are firm-specific controls that include firms' financial characteristics. The firms' financial characteristics are evaluated using the following variables: Growth is the logarithm of the growth rate of sales at year-end; Size of the firm is measured as the logarithm of total assets at year-end; Leverage is measured as the logarithm of debt to equity ratio at year-end; Market-to-book is the logarithm of the market value of equity divided by the book value of equity at year-end; Profitability will be the gain on assets at year-end; Cash Holdings are the logarithm of the cash equivalents and cash divided by the total assets at year-end; and Firm age is the of the number of years from the firm's founding date.

3.4. Dependent variables

Total risk

Total risk includes both Systematic risk (market risk) and idiosyncratic risk. It is calculated as the yearly variance of the every day stock returns for a company over a given year.

Systematic risk

Systematic risk is measured using Scholes & Williams (1977) work on betas estimations from nonsynchronous data. The beta factor for a business is calculated using the everyday surplus returns on the value-balanced market portfolio evaluates the systematic risk.

Idiosyncratic risk

Idiosyncratic risk is determined using the yearly standard deviation of the remainder of Scholes & Williams (1977) estimators for a corporation at a certain period.

3.5. Model

This applied co-relational research uses a non-experimental approach and is a quantitative study based on secondary data. The theoretical framework can be seen in *Figure 1*. The unit of analysis for this empirical research will be the market-based firm risk estimates. The primary goal of the research will be to investigate the link between the dependent and independent variables.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

The study applies panel regression to examine the influence of a company executive's gender, affiliation to a political party, insider ownership, and narcissism on the firm risk estimates. The main analysis uses substitute forms of the following subsequent equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Firm\ risk_{j,t} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 CEO\ Gender_{j,t} + \beta_2 CFO\ Gender_{j,t} + \beta_3 CEO\ Affiliation_{j,t} \\
 & + \beta_4 CFO\ Affiliation_{j,t} + \beta_5 CEO\ Ownership_{j,t} + \beta_6 CFO\ Ownership_{j,t} \\
 & + \beta_7 CEO\ Narcissism_{j,t} + \beta_8 CFO\ Narcissism_{j,t} + \beta_9 Control\ Variables_{j,t} \\
 & + \varepsilon_{j,t}
 \end{aligned}$$

- $Firm\ risk_{j,t}$ = 3 market-based firm risk measures
- j = Firm
- t = Time (year)

The dependent variable $Firm\ risk_{j,t}$ will be one of three firm risk measures (Total risk, Systematic risk, Idiosyncratic risk) for firm j at year t .

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the empirical results of the relationship between the market-based risk measures and the independent variables. In the first section we discuss the correlation results of the variables, followed by descriptive statistics. We test the regression using likelihood ratio and hausman test. Finally, we analyze the regression results by using common effect, fixed effect, and random effect. The discussion is segregated country wise.

4.1. Correlation

Pakistan

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Idio_Risk	1.00									
2	Syst_Risk	-.998**	1.00								
3	Total_Risk	0.01	0.05	1.00							
4	G_CEO	0.02	-0.01	0.08	1.00						
5	G_CFO	0.08	-0.08	0.02	-0.01	1.00					
6	Pol_Affil	0.02	-0.02	-0.04	-0.06	.121**	1.00				
7	IO	0.05	-0.04	0.06	-0.05	-0.03	-.143**	1.00			
8	Nar_SCR_CEO	-0.01	0.01	0.03	-0.04	0.00	0.02	-0.08	1.00		
9	NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.01	0.02	0.06	-0.06	-0.06	-0.07	0.08	.251**	1.00	
10	NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.00	0.01	.092*	-0.07	-0.06	-.150**	0.02	0.00	-.135**	1.00

Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, Total_Risk: Total Risk, G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, IO: Insider Ownership, Nar_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissim Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissim Signature Score of CFO

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The CFO narcissism signature variable has a very weak significantly positive correlation of 0.92. Political affiliation and the gender of the CFO also have a significantly weak positive correlation of 0.121. The test suggests that insider ownership and political affiliation and has a significantly weak negative correlation of 0.143. The CEO narcissism signature and CEO narcissism score has mildly weak significant positive correlation. The correlation values of other variables suggest a weak insignificant correlation. Aside from that, firm size and political affiliation have moderately significant positive correlations. CEO narcissism signature and

leverage have a moderately significant negative correlation of 0.276. Political affiliation and firm age also have a mildly weak significant positive correlation of 0.214.

India

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Total_Risk	1.00									
2	Idio_Risk	1.000**	1.00								
3	Syst_Risk	-0.03	-0.04	1.00							
4	G_CEO	-0.01	-0.02	.144**	1.00						
5	G_CFO	0.00	0.00	0.07	-0.02	1.00					
6	Pol_Affil	-0.03	-0.04	.193**	.145**	-0.04	1.00				
7	IO	-0.01	-0.01	0.05	-0.04	-0.01	.250**	1.00			
8	Nar_SCR_CEO	-0.02	-0.02	-0.03	-0.05	0.09	.133**	-0.06	1.00		
9	NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.03	-0.03	.184**	-0.03	-0.04	-0.05	-0.08	.231**	1.00	
10	NAR_SIGN_CFO	-0.01	-0.02	.243**	-0.07	-0.02	-.111*	-0.02	-0.04	.343**	1.00

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, IO: Insider Ownership, Nar_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissim Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissim Signature Score of CFO

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Systematic risk has significantly weak positive correlation with gender of CEO, political affiliation, and CEO narcissism signature and a mildly weak positive correlation with CFO narcissism signature. Political affiliation has a moderately weak significant positive correlation with insider ownership and firm size. The CEO score narcissism and CEO signature narcissism has mildly weak significant positive correlation. Insider ownership and firm size has significantly weak positive correlation and CEO narcissism score and firm size also has a weak positive significant correlation. The CEO narcissism score has moderately significant negative correlation with cash holdings having value of 0.308. The gender of CEO has weak significant positive correlation with market to book ratio whereas gender of CFO has weak significantly negative correlation with market to book ratio.

China

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	Total_Risk	1.00								
2	Idio_Risk	-0.04	1.00							
3	Syst_Risk	0.00	.710**	1.00						
4	G_CEO	-0.04	.114*	0.03	1.00					
5	G_CFO	-.100*	0.07	.101*	-0.03	1.00				
6	Pol_Affil	0.00	.097*	0.06	-0.05	-.099*	1.00			
7	IO	-0.01	-0.03	-0.06	.203**	-0.05	-.307**	1.00		
8	Nar_SCR_CEO	-.097*	0.05	0.08	0.07	-.182**	0.06	0.06	1.00	
9	NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.08	0.01	.132*	.218**	.285**	-0.06	0.07	.147*	1.00

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, IO: Insider Ownership, Nar_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissim Signature Score of CEO

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Total risk has a weak significant negative correlation with the gender of the CFO having a value of 0.1 and the narcissism score of the CEO having a value of .097 whereas it has a weak significant positive correlation with the market-to-book ratio. Idiosyncratic risk has a weak positive correlation with the gender of the CEO and political affiliation. Likewise, systematic risk has significantly weak positive correlation with gender of CFO, CEO narcissism signature, and market-to-book ratio. Meanwhile, systematic risk also has a significantly weak negative correlation with firm size and cash holdings. Aside from that, gender of CEO and Insider Ownership has significantly weak positive correlation but insider ownership and political affiliation has moderately significant negative correlation. The gender of CFO and political affiliation has weak negatively significant correlation of 0.1. The CEO narcissism score and CEO narcissism signature have a weak positive significant correlation of 0.147. The Gender of CEO has weak significantly negative correlation with market to book ratio and firm age but it has weak positive significant correlation with firm size. Political affiliation has a weak negative significant correlation with growth, profitability, and cash holdings but it has a positive significant correlation with leverage, market-to-book ratio, and firm age.

Bangladesh

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Total_Risk	1.00									
2	Idio_Risk	0.08	1.00								
3	Syst_Risk	0.03	-.994**	1.00							
4	G_CEO	-0.03	0.07	-0.08	1.00						
5	G_CFO	-0.04	.105*	-.110*	.512**	1.00					
6	Pol_Affil	-0.04	-0.07	0.06	.177**	.282**	1.00				
7	IO	-0.01	-0.03	0.03	0.01	-0.03	0.08	1.00			
8	Nar_SCR_CEO	-0.02	0.01	-0.01	-.126*	0.00	0.10	0.09	1.00		
9	NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.07	-.115*	.104*	.123**	0.00	-0.02	-.089*	-0.10	1.00	
10	NAR_SIGN_CFO	-0.05	-0.05	0.04	-0.06	0.05	0.01	-0.04	-0.01	.203**	1.00

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, IO: Insider Ownership, Nar_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissim Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissim Signature Score of CFO

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Idiosyncratic risk has a weak significant positive correlation with the gender of the CFO and a weak significant negative correlation with the CEO narcissism signature. Systematic risk has weak significant negative correlation with gender of CFO but weak positive significant correlation with narcissism signature of CEO. The gender of the CEO has a significantly weak positive correlation with political affiliation and CEO narcissism score. The gender of the CFO has a moderately significant positive correlation with political affiliation. Whereas, insider ownership has a weak negative significant correlation with CEO narcissism signature. The size of the firm has moderate significant negative correlation with with gender of CEO and CFO having value of 0.421 and 0.448 respectively. Political affiliation, insider ownership, and CEO narcissism score also have a significantly weak negative correlation with firm size. The gender of the CEO and market-to-book value has a weak significant negative correlation of 0.179. It should also be noted that political affiliation has a weak significant positive correlation with cash holding having a score of 0.188.

Vietnam

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Total_Risk	1.00									
2	Idio_Risk	.241**	1.00								
3	Syst_Risk	.232**	.342**	1.00							
4	G_CEO	-.182**	-.295**	-.186**	1.00						
5	G_CFO	-.332**	-.245**	-.216**	.170**	1.00					
6	Pol_Affil	0.00	.126**	.201**	-.092*	-.174**	1.00				
7	IO	.197**	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.01	-0.04	1.00			
8	Nar_SCR_CEO	.096*	0.06	0.02	-0.03	-0.04	0.04	0.01	1.00		
9	NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.05	-0.05	-.119*	0.08	0.00	-0.07	0.04	0.03	1.00	
10	NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.04	-0.08	-0.06	.105*	.149**	-.182**	-0.05	-0.02	-0.08	1.00

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, IO: Insider Ownership, Nar_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissim Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissim Signature Score of CFO

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Total risk has moderately negative significant correlation with gender of CFO but weak negative significant correlation with gender of CEO. Moreover, it also has a weak positive significant correlation with insider ownership and CEO narcissism score. Meanwhile, idiosyncratic risk has a moderately significant negative correlation with the gender of the CEO and CFO. It also has a significantly weak positive correlation with political affiliation. Systematic risk has a significantly weak negative correlation with the gender of the CEO, the gender of the CFO, and the CEO narcissism signature. It has a weak significant positive association with political affiliation. The gender of CEO and CFO have a weak negative significant correlation with political affiliation. The CFO narcissism signature has a weak significantly negative correlation with political affiliation. Aside from that, the gender of the CEO has a moderately significant positive association with firm size and the gender of the CFO has a weak significant positive association with firm size having scores of 0.326 and 0.183 respectively. Total risk has a significantly moderate negative correlation with firm size having a score of 0.302 and weak negative significant relation with leverage having a score of 0.142. Idiosyncratic risk has a weak significant negative correlation with firm size with a score of

0.163. Systematic risk has a weak significant positive relation with profitability and cash holding with values of 0.175 and 0.096.

Malaysia

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Total_Risk	1.00									
2	Idio_Risk	.152**	1.00								
3	Syst_Risk	-0.08	-.997**	1.00							
4	G_CEO	-0.01	0.01	-0.01	1.00						
5	G_CFO	-0.02	0.04	-0.05	.156**	1.00					
6	Pol_Affil	-0.06	-0.04	0.04	0.04	-0.08	1.00				
7	IO	-0.03	-0.05	0.04	.129**	-.090*	.237**	1.00			
8	Nar_SCR_CEO	.088*	-0.01	0.02	-0.02	0.02	-0.04	-.111*	1.00		
9	NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.01	0.02	-0.02	-0.04	-0.08	.173**	.116**	-0.01	1.00	
10	NAR_SIGN_CFO	-0.03	-.130**	.128**	0.06	-0.03	0.04	0.05	-0.02	.104*	1.00

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, IO: Insider Ownership, Nar_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissim Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissim Signature Score of CFO

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Total risk has a weak positive correlation with CEO narcissism score. Idiosyncratic risk has a significantly weak negative correlation with the CFO narcissism signature while systematic risk has a weak positive correlation with the CFO narcissism signature. The gender of the CEO has a weak significant positive correlation with insider ownership whereas the gender of the CFO has a weak negative significant correlation with insider ownership. Political affiliation and insider ownership also have a weak positive significant correlation. Idiosyncratic risk has a weak negative significant association with growth, market-to-book ratio, and cash holding having a value of 0.123, 0.115, and 0.09 respectively but it has a weak positive significant relation with the size of the firm with a score of 0.09.

4.2. Descriptive Statistics

Pakistan

Variables	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.
Total_Risk	0.041	0.034	0.191	0.000	0.029
Idio_Risk	-0.014	-0.006	3.907	-2.427	0.476
Syst_Risk	0.055	0.042	2.434	-3.865	0.476
IO	0.031	0.000	0.479	0.000	0.069
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.210	0.000	7.000	0.000	0.625
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.220	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.414
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.243	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.429

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, IO: Insider Ownership, Nar_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissim Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissim Signature Score of CFO

Observations: 500

The table above shows descriptive statistics of the variables for Pakistan. The average amount of shares of a firm owned by top executives is 3%, whereas the greatest ownership of any single firm is 47%. The largest narcissism score scored by an executive is 7 while the average is 0.2. The volatility in narcissism score and insider ownership is 0.625 and 6.8% respectively. Leverage is 0.08 indicating that a greater portion of assets is financed by equity. The data also suggests that Pakistani firms are on average undervalued. The average profit for the firms throughout the market is 10% and the average age of a company in Pakistan is 40 years. The average firm size in our sample is 18.5 with the smallest and largest size being 27 and 13 respectively.

India

Variables	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.
Total_Risk	0.82	0.02	0.26	0.01	0.14
Idio_Risk	0.60	-0.14	0.26	-0.98	0.25
Syst_Risk	0.22	0.16	1.00	-0.21	0.25
G_CEO	0.06	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.24
G_CFO	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.06
Pol_Affil	0.26	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.44
IO	0.04	0.00	0.75	0.0	0.39
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.10	0.00	3.33	0.00	0.28
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.21	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.41
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.05	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.22

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, IO: Insider Ownership, Nar_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissim Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissim Signature Score of CFO

Observations: 500

The average portion of shares owned by top executives of Indian firms is 4.4% while the greatest ownership in any firm is 74.8% of the total shares outstanding. The average narcissism score is 0.1 and the largest recorded is 3.33. The volatility in narcissism score is 0.27. The average leverage is 0.38 which indicates that a greater amount of equity financing is employed by Indian firms than liabilities. The average profitability of Indian firms is 9% and the most profitable is 108%. The average age of firms in our sample is 35 years. The average firm size in our sample is 26 and the smallest and largest size is 17.7 and 30 respectively.

China

Variables	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.
Total_Risk	0.04	0.02	0.76	0.01	0.08
Idio_Risk	0.44	0.44	1.59	0.01	0.22
Syst_Risk	0.20	0.18	1.65	0.00	0.16
IO	0.07	0.00	0.68	0.00	0.17
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.23	0.11	2.50	0.00	0.33

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, IO: Insider Ownership, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO

Observations: 500

The table above shows descriptive statistics of Chinese listed firms. The average narcissism score of CEOs for Chinese firms is 0.22 with the greatest score being 2.5. The mean ownership by the CEO and CFO of Chinese firms is 6.9% with the largest ownership being 62%. For Chinese companies, assets are financed by equity more than liabilities. The market-to-book value is 10.95 which means that Chinese firms are overpriced relative to their book value. Interestingly, in our sample, the average profitability of Chinese firms is 97%. The average age of firms is 34 years and the oldest firm is 159 years old. The average size of companies is 16 with the largest size being 25 and the smallest being 8.

Bangladesh

Variables	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.
Total_Risk	0.03	0.02	0.81	0.00	0.05
Idio_Risk	-0.21	-0.12	2.66	-3.90	0.46
Syst_Risk	0.24	0.14	3.91	-2.66	0.46
G_CEO	0.07	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.26
G_CFO	0.02	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.15
Pol_Affil	0.11	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.31
IO	0.09	0.00	0.30	0.00	0.51
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.27	0.15	3.00	0.00	0.35
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.35	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.48
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.50	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.50

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, IO: Insider Ownership, Nar_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissim Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissim Signature Score of CFO

Observations: 500

The average narcissism score for Bangladeshi companies is 0.265 and the greatest score is 3. Mean insider ownership is 8.8% and the largest is 30.81%. Leverage statistic of 0.075 signals that firms use equity more than liabilities to finance their assets. The market-to-book ratio has an average of 0.21 indicating firms are on average underpriced on the basis of book value. The average age of Bangladeshi firms is 32 years and the average size of firms in the sample is 22.7.

Vietnam

Variables	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.
Total_Risk	0.04	0.03	0.22	0.01	0.03
Idio_Risk	1.16	1.19	2.07	0.00	0.48
Syst_Risk	0.41	0.38	2.04	0.00	0.27
IO	0.15	0.07	0.80	0.00	0.17
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.50	0.27	6.00	0.00	0.74

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, IO: Insider Ownership, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO

Observations: 500

The average narcissism score is 0.5 with the largest score being 6 having a volatility of 0.7. On average CEO and CFO hold 15% of total outstanding shares and the greatest holding of a firm is 80%. In our sample, the greatest size of a firm is 33, and the smallest is 13. The leverage score is 0.34 meaning assets are largely financed by equity. The market-to-book statistic shows that Vietnamese firms are on average overpriced relative to their book value. Moreover, the profitability of these firms is on average 10%, similar to Pakistan. The average age of companies is 31 and the age has volatility of 13 years.

Malaysia

Variables	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.
Total_Risk	0.00	0.03	0.46	0.01	0.00
Idio_Risk	-0.27	-0.19	0.45	-1.35	0.35
Syst_Risk	0.31	0.22	1.38	-0.29	0.34
G_CEO	0.10	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.30
G_CFO	0.10	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.31
Pol_Affil	0.13	0.01	1.00	0.00	0.67
IO	0.26	0.00	0.93	0.00	0.44
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.05	0.04	0.13	0.00	0.03
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.49	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.50
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.37	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.48

Total_Risk: Total Risk, Idio_Risk: Idiosyncratic Risk, Syst_Risk: Systematic Risk, G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, IO: Insider Ownership, Nar_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissim Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissim Signature Score of CFO

Observations: 500

The average narcissism score of a CEO is 0.045 for Malaysian companies and the volatility in these scores is 0.031. On average, CEOs and CFOs hold 7.4% of outstanding shares of Malaysian firms, and the greatest portion owned by any executive is 93.5%. The volatility in insider ownership is 18.7%. Aside from that, the Average firm size in our sample is 16.8 with the largest being 26.4. The mean leverage is 0.34 meaning that firms are using equity more than liabilities to finance assets. The market-to-book ratio is good indicating that the market price of firms on average is greater than the book value. On average Malaysian firms have a profit of 43%. The average age of Malaysian companies in our sample is 42 with the oldest being 116 years old.

4.3. Likelihood test

Pakistan

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	11.17562	-50432	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	12.20063	-50433	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.731457	-50432	0.0022

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0.0022, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.48988	-50433	0.0206

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0.0206, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.768451	-50432	0.0015

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0.0015, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.526218	-50433	0.0151

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0.0151, this data indicates a fixed effect.

India

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	0.63116	-43358	0.9668

Since the P value is greater than 0.05 and is 0.9668, this data indicates a common effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	0.649734	-39341	0.9492

Since the P value is greater than 0.05 and is 0.9492, this data indicates a common effect.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	0.632543	-43358	0.9661

Since the P value is greater than 0.05 and is 0.9661, this data indicates a common effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	0.648166	-39341	0.9501

Since the P value is greater than 0.05 and is 0.9501, this data indicates a common effect.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	3.048524	-43358	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	2.293233	-39341	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

China

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	17.27751	-48402	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	26.48695	-30265	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	5.780097	-48402	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	6.41637	-30265	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	4.937229	-48402	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	4.715701	-30265	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Bangladesh

Total Risk

Measure: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	2.32105	-49417	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.396313	-49423	0.0457

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0.0457, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Systematic Risk

Measure: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.502481	-49417	0.0195

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0.0195, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Vietnam**Total Risk****Measure 1: Narcissism Score**

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	5.104674	-47369	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	5.014369	-46364	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Idiosyncratic Risk**Measure 1: Narcissism Score**

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	2.681292	-47369	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	2.76268	-46364	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Systematic Risk**Measure 1: Narcissism Score**

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.50317	-47368	0.022

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0.022, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.500494	-46363	0.024

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0.024, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Malaysia

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	0.906897	-49428	0.6536

Since the P value is greater than 0.05 and is 0.6536, this data indicates a common effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	0.913435	-49428	0.6414

Since the P value is greater than 0.05 and is 0.6414, this data indicates a common effect.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	0.910375	-49428	0.6471

Since the P value is greater than 0.05 and is 0.6471, this data indicates a common effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	0.915497	-49428	0.6375

Since the P value is greater than 0.05 and is 0.6375, this data indicates a common effect.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	3.369263	-49428	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	3.168382	-49428	0

Since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and is 0, this data indicates a fixed effect.

4.4. Hausman test

In this section, we will present the results of Hausman test for the regression. The results are segregated by country and each measure of market-based risks are discussed accordingly.

Pakistan

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	20.792336	12	0.0535

Hausman Test null hypothesis H_0 is that random effect model is suitable and consistent. While the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that random effect model is more consistent and suitable while fixed effect model is unsuitable and inconsistent. The below mentioned results indicates that probability is not significant, H_0 is accepted so fixed effect model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is rejected. The value of probability is slightly greater than 0.05, thus accepting H_0 . The results in the the table above that appropriate model to analyze total risk is common effect model. Therefore, total risk will be analyzed by common effect model.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	28.053695	13	0.0089

Hausman Test null hypothesis H_0 is that fixed effect model is suitable and consistent. While the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that fixed model is more consistent and suitable while random model is unsuitable and inconsistent. The below mentioned results indicates that probability is not significant, H_0 is rejected so fixed effect model is accepted and alternative hypothesis is accepted. The value of probability is less than 0.05, thus rejecting H_0 . The results in the table above show that appropriate model to analyze total risk is fixed effect model. Therefore, total risk will be analyzed by fixed effect model.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	10.795213	12	0.5465

Hausman Test null hypothesis H_0 is that random effect model is suitable and consistent. While the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that fixed model is more consistent and suitable while random model is unsuitable and inconsistent. The below mentioned results indicates that probability is not significant, H_0 is accepted so fixed effect model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is rejected. The value of probability is 0.5465 which is greater than significance accepting H_0 . The results in the table above shows that appropriate model to analyze idiosyncratic risk is common effect model. Therefore, idiosyncratic risk will be analyzed by random effect model.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	8.522284	13	0.808

Hausman Test null hypothesis H_0 is that random effect model is suitable and consistent. While the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that fixed model is more consistent and suitable while random model is unsuitable and inconsistent. The below mentioned results indicates that probability is not significant, H_0 is accepted so fixed effect model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is rejected. The value of p which is 0.808 in this case is greater than significance which is 0.05. The results in the table above show that appropriate model to analyze systemic risk is common effect model. Therefore, systemic risk will be analyzed by random effect model.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	10.723989	12	0.5527

Hausman Test null hypothesis H_0 is that random effect model is suitable and consistent. While the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that fixed model is more consistent and suitable while random

model is unsuitable and inconsistent. The below mentioned results indicates that probability is not significant, H_0 is accepted so fixed effect model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is rejected. The value of p which is 0.5527 in this case is greater than significance which is 0.05. The results in the table above show that appropriate model to analyze systemic risk is common effect model. Therefore, systemic risk will be analyzed by random effect model.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	8.376843	13	0.8182

Hausman Test null hypothesis H_0 is that random effect model is suitable and consistent. While the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that fixed model is more consistent and suitable while random model is unsuitable and inconsistent. The below mentioned results indicates that probability is not significant, H_0 is accepted so fixed effect model is rejected and alternative hypothesis is rejected. The value of p which is 0.8182 in this case is greater than significance which is 0.05. The results in the table above show that appropriate model to analyze systemic risk is common effect model. Therefore, systemic risk will be analyzed by random effect model.

4.4.2. India

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	2.151148	12	0.9991

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	3.838393	13	0.9928

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	2.073908	12	0.9993

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	3.837115	13	0.9928

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null

hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	43.590283	12	0

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is significant as it is less than 5%. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying fixed effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	31.502632	13	0.0028

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is significant as it is less than 5%. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying fixed effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

4.4.3. China

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	12.847576	12	0.3802

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	6.702926	12	0.8766

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	77.876915	12	0

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is significant as it is less than 5%. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying fixed effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	45.22567	12	0

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is significant as it is less than 5%. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying fixed effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	22.98052	12	0.0279

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is significant as it is less than 5%. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying fixed effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	17.397141	12	0.1353

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

4.4.4. Bangladesh

Total Risk

Measure: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	10.827683	12	0.5437

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	9.987553	13	0.695

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

Systematic Risk

Measure: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	10.061653	13	0.6889

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that random effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we accept the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

4.4.5. Vietnam

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	13.225727	12	0.3528

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating

that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	12.213032	13	0.5103

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is more appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	18.213998	12	0.1093

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is more appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	14.709995	13	0.3258

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	15.715105	12	0.2046

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	8.453972	13	0.8128

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

4.4.6. Malaysia

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	9.751087	12	0.6378

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	6.352595	12	0.8973

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	9.877309	12	0.6267

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	6.495629	12	0.8891

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is not significant as it is greater than 5%. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying random effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	47.098	12	0

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is significant as it is less than 5%. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying fixed effect model to analyze Narcissism Score.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	41.553123	12	0

In case of Hausman Test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is that the random effect model is more appropriate whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that fixed effect model is appropriate. If the probability value is less than 5% level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis. The table above shows that the probability value is significant as it is less than 5%. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis stating that fixed effect model is more appropriate. Hence, this research is applying fixed effect model to analyze Narcissism Signature.

4.5. Regression: Common, Fixed & Random Effect Model

Pakistan

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.069098	0.214999	0.107466
G_CEO	0.019822	-0.003999	0.001434
G_CFO	0.004242	-0.002867	-0.000471
IO	0.001437	-0.003583	0.001328
Pol_Affil	0.035109	-0.034022	-0.01317
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.001817	0.001682	0.001658
GR	0.000505	0.001383	0.000958
FS	-0.00162	-0.007597	-0.003297
LVRG	-0.000572	0.0000118	-0.000326
MTB	0.000118	-0.000233	-0.0000399
PROF	-0.001236	0.00561	0.008627
CH	-0.001291	-0.00144	-0.001264
FA	-4.23E-05	-0.000879	-0.000214
Adjusted R Square (Random)	2.05%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.860349		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.03699		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.731255		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 495

Cross-sections: 51

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.020471 which indicates that only 2.0471% changes in the dependent variable i.e. Total Risk is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk. The independent variables insider ownership and CFO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Whereas political affiliation, narcissism score and CEO gender shows a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. The control variables firm size, leverage, market-

to-book ratio, cash holdings and firm age show a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Growth and profitability show a positive and insignificant impact on total risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.066675	0.166635	0.095477
G_CEO	0.022453	-0.002602	0.003598
G_CFO	0.008035	-0.0014	0.001436
IO	0.002693	-0.002241	0.002763
Pol_Affil	0.033509	-0.038798	-0.018247
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.005824	0.016085	0.012456
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.006387	0.021878	0.015879
GR	0.000269	0.001667	0.001168
FS	-0.001541	-0.004053	-0.002814
LVRG	-0.000545	-0.00036	-0.000439
MTB	0.000167	-0.00024	-0.0000272
PROF	0.000315	0.0079	0.009607
CH	-0.000904	-0.00147	-0.001193
FA	-5.97E-05	-0.00153	-0.000284
Adjusted R Square (Random)	5.80%		
F-Statistics (Random)	3.350632		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.000061		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.807063		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 497

Cross-sections: 51

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.609583 which indicates that 60% changes in the dependent variable (Total Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk, except for narcissism signature of CEO and CFO. The independent variables CEO and CFO gender, political affiliation and insider ownership shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Whereas CEO and CFO narcissism shows a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. The

control variables leverage, Market-to-Book ratio, firm age and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Growth and profitability show a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. Narcissism signature of CEO (0.016085) and CFO (0.021878) shows a positive and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in narcissism signature leads to a 1.6% increase in total risk. While 1% change in narcissism signature leads to 2.18% increase in total risk.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-0.232089	-0.917766	-0.288274
G_CEO	-0.045879	-0.07868	-0.069031
G_CFO	0.371618	0.345197	0.36145
IO	-0.06441	-0.223095	-0.085263
Pol_Affil	0.37005	0.545115	0.372561
NAR_SCR_CEO	-0.007486	0.021523	0.003431
GR	-0.01044	-0.013416	-0.010342
FS	0.000392	-0.003611	0.002161
LVRG	-0.014164	-0.013059	-0.012814
MTB	0.002527	-0.003975	0.002099
PROF	-0.183675	0.000961	-0.110069
CH	-0.007437	-0.01144	-0.009258
FA	0.005028	0.021904	0.005238
Adjusted R Square (Random)	2.083%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.875897		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.035045		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.696846		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissism Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 495

Cross-sections: 51

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.020834 which indicates that only 2.08% changes in the dependent variable i.e. Idiosyncratic

Risk is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for insider ownership and CFO gender. The independent variables CEO gender and political affiliation shows a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Whereas insider ownership, narcissism score and CFO gender shows a positive and significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. The control variables growth, leverage, profitability and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Firm size, market to book ratio and firm age show a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. Insider ownership shows a positive and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in insider ownership leads to a 37% increase in idiosyncratic risk. CFO gender shows a significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. A 1% change in CFO gender leads to 36.145% increase in idiosyncratic risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-0.194657	-0.546102	-0.213984
G_CEO	-0.053454	-0.09755	-0.071154
G_CFO	0.301714	0.359831	0.318744
IO	-0.024778	0.004076	-0.023758
Pol_Affil	0.318804	0.53853	0.34001
NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.047741	-0.016494	-0.031179
NAR_SIGN_CFO	-0.031987	0.018456	-0.02271
GR	-0.011309	-0.011659	-0.010805
FS	-0.001432	-0.028901	-0.001168
LVRG	-0.00362	0.003186	-0.001075
MTB	0.001161	-0.000916	0.001149
PROF	-0.19677	-0.024804	-0.132481
CH	-0.01579	-0.016542	-0.015501
FA	0.004442	0.023997	0.004512
Adjusted R Square (Random)	0.74%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.284734		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.217985		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.742986		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 497

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of -0.007408 which indicates that only 0.7% changes in the dependent variable (Idiosyncratic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for CFO gender and Insider ownership. The independent variables political affiliation, CEO and CFO narcissism signature, and CEO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Whereas insider ownership and CFO gender shows a positive and significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. The control variables firm age and market to book ratio show a positive and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Growth, firm size, leverage, profitability and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. CFO gender (0.3187) and Insider ownership (0.34001) shows a positive and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in CFO gender leads to a 31.87% increase in idiosyncratic risk. While a 1% change in insider ownership leads to 34% increase in idiosyncratic risk.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.301187	1.132765	0.364838
G_CEO	0.065701	0.074682	0.082938
G_CFO	-0.367375	-0.348063	-0.358781
IO	0.065846	0.219511	0.087851
Pol_Affil	-0.334941	-0.579137	-0.352829
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.009303	-0.019841	-0.002168
GR	0.010945	0.014798	0.011035
FS	-0.002012	-0.003987	-0.004078
LVRG	0.013592	0.013071	0.012307
MTB	-0.002409	0.003741	-0.001955
PROF	0.18244	0.004649	0.111817
CH	0.006146	0.01	0.008014
FA	-0.00507	-0.022784	-0.005306
Adjusted R Square (Random)	1.99%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.83553		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.0403		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.701661		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 495

Cross-sections: 51

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.019893 which indicates that only 1.98% changes in the dependent variable i.e. Systemic Risk is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on systemic risk, except for CEO and CFO gender, insider ownership political affiliation and profitability. The independent variables CEO gender and narcissism score shows a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. The CFO gender and insider ownership shows a negative and significant impact on systemic risk. Whereas political affiliation and CEO gender shows a positive and significant impact on systemic risk. The control variables firm age, firm size and

market to book ratio show a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Growth, Leverage, profitability and cash holdings show a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. CEO gender shows a significant impact on systemic risk. A 1% change in CEO gender leads to 8.29% increase in systemic risk. . Political Affiliation has a positive and significant impact on systemic risk. A 1% increase in political affiliation leads to 8.78% change in systemic risk. Gender of CFO shows a significant impact on systemic risk. A 1% change in CFO gender leads to a 35.87% decrease in systemic risk. Insider ownership shows a negative and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in insider ownership leads to a 35.28% decrease in systemic risk. The control variable profitability also has a significant impact on systemic risk. A 1% change in profitability leads to 11.18% increase in systemic risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.261333	0.712737	0.284728
G_CEO	0.075908	0.094948	0.088991
G_CFO	-0.293679	-0.361231	-0.314
IO	0.027471	-0.006317	0.026572
Pol_Affil	-0.285295	-0.577328	-0.321982
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.053565	0.03258	0.037325
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.038373	0.003422	0.030034
GR	0.011577	0.013326	0.011319
FS	-0.000109	0.024848	-0.000526
LVRG	0.003075	-0.003545	0.000492
MTB	-0.000995	0.000676	-0.000973
PROF	0.197085	0.032703	0.134566
CH	0.014886	0.015073	0.014508
FA	-0.004502	-0.025527	-0.004594
Adjusted R Square (Random)	0.68%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.262179		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.232356		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.750961		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 497

Cross-sections: 51

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.006825 which indicates that 0.6% changes in the dependent variable Systemic Risk is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on systemic risk, except for gender of CEO and CFO, profitability and insider ownership. The independent variables CFO gender and insider ownership shows a negative and significant effect on systemic risk. Whereas, political affiliation and CEO and CFO narcissism signature score shows a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. The control variables firm size, Market-to-Book ratio and firm age show a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Growth, cash holdings

and leverage show a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. The independent variable of CEO gender (0.08891) shows a positive and significant impact on systemic risk. A 1% change in CEO gender leads to 8.89% increase in systemic risk. Gender of CFO (-0.314) and insider ownership (0.32198) shows a negative and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in CFO gender leads to 31% decrease in systemic risk. A 1% change in insider ownership leads to a 32% decrease in systemic risk. While 1% change in profitability leads to 13.45% increase in systemic risk.

India

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-19.6554	4.419787	-19.6554
G_CEO	-0.216772	0.62951	-0.216772
G_CFO	0.920136	-0.528796	0.920136
IO	0.018146	-0.003209	0.018146
Pol_Affil	-1.243475	0.313611	-1.243475
NAR_SCR_CEO	-0.645275	-0.39672	-0.645275
GR	0.004822	0.071446	0.004822
FS	0.625535	-0.404812	0.625535
LVRG	-0.469966	-0.128569	-0.469966
MTB	0.194935	-0.058741	0.194935
PROF	0.620836	-2.604557	0.620836
CH	-0.174385	-0.117328	-0.174385
FA	0.138738	0.195245	0.138738
Adjusted R Square (Random)	0.021%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.007244		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.44119		
Durbin Watson (Random)	2.317784		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissism Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 414

Cross-sections: 44

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.00021 which indicates that only 0.021% changes in the dependent variable (Total Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk, except for firm age. The independent variables political affiliation, CEO narcissism score and CEO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Whereas insider ownership and CFO gender shows a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. The control variables leverage and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Growth, profitability, firm size, and market to book ratio show a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. Firm age (0.138) shows a positive and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in firm age leads to a 14% increase in total risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-19.55986	2.438795	-19.55986
G_CEO	-0.349449	0.831498	-0.349449
G_CFO	0.291213	-0.289361	0.291213
IO	0.010702	0.001203	0.010702
Pol_Affil	-1.313574	0.268831	-1.313574
NAR_SIGN_CEO	-1.317007	0.483502	-1.317007
NAR_SIGN_CFO	-4.829115	1.01882	-4.829115
GR	0.013365	0.093047	0.013365
FS	0.658411	-0.364289	0.658411
LVRG	-0.612595	-0.140103	-0.612595
MTB	0.218884	-0.037614	0.218884
PROF	-0.630427	-4.785698	-0.630427
CH	-0.207483	-0.111608	-0.207483
FA	0.12877	0.216119	0.12877
Adjusted R Square (Random)	-0.25%		
F-Statistics (Random)	0.925177		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.526721		
Durbin Watson (Random)	2.310075		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 394

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of -0.002481 which indicates that only 0.25% changes in the dependent variable (Total Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk, except for firm age. The independent variables political affiliation, CEO and CFO narcissism signature, and CEO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Whereas insider ownership and CFO gender shows a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. The control variables leverage, profitability, and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Growth, firm size, and market to book ratio show a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. Firm age (0.128) shows a positive and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in firm age leads to a 13% increase in total risk.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-19.94394	3.741473	-19.94394
G_CEO	-0.345121	0.611048	-0.345121
G_CFO	0.558413	-0.708981	0.558413
IO	0.018213	-0.002145	0.018213
Pol_Affil	-1.316066	0.134118	-1.316066
NAR_SCR_CEO	-0.625487	-0.400064	-0.625487
GR	0.003763	0.073338	0.003763
FS	0.624835	-0.411069	0.624835
LVRG	-0.477419	-0.129333	-0.477419
MTB	0.190795	-0.064026	0.190795
PROF	0.620171	-2.943854	0.620171
CH	-0.186566	-0.117359	-0.186566
FA	0.139413	0.215276	0.139413
Adjusted R Square (Random)	0.087%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.029906		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.420084		
Durbin Watson (Random)	2.32029		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissism Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 414

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.000868 which indicates that only 0.09% changes in the dependent variable (Idiosyncratic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for firm age. The independent variables political affiliation, CEO narcissism score, and CEO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Whereas insider ownership and CFO gender shows a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. The control variables leverage and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Growth, firm size, profitability, and market to book ratio show a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. Firm age (0.139) shows a positive and significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. A 1% change in firm age leads to a 14% increase in idiosyncratic risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-19.77252	1.926629	-19.77252
G_CEO	-0.507991	0.795264	-0.507991
G_CFO	-0.090315	-0.498113	-0.090315
IO	0.010937	0.000992	0.010937
Pol_Affil	-1.381544	0.093814	-1.381544
NAR_SIGN_CEO	-1.39999	0.43865	-1.39999
NAR_SIGN_CFO	-5.080024	0.923947	-5.080024
GR	0.010688	0.096444	0.010688
FS	0.656051	-0.375868	0.656051
LVRG	-0.619441	-0.141913	-0.619441
MTB	0.215273	-0.044518	0.215273
PROF	-0.506535	-5.027843	-0.506535
CH	-0.220577	-0.11583	-0.220577
FA	0.129248	0.23416	0.129248
Adjusted R Square (Random)	-0.16%		
F-Statistics (Random)	0.950466		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.500434		
Durbin Watson (Random)	2.313518		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of -0.001641 which indicates that only 0.16% changes in the dependent variable (Idiosyncratic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for firm age. The independent variables political affiliation, CEO and CFO narcissism signature, and CEO and CFO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Whereas insider ownership shows a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. The control variables leverage, profitability, and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Growth, firm size, and market to book ratio show a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. Firm age (0.129) shows a positive and significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. A 1% change in firm age leads to a 13% increase in idiosyncratic risk.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.322493	0.721617	0.491462
G_CEO	0.129163	0.017169	0.106653
G_CFO	0.359306	0.18097	0.260115
IO	-0.0000919	-0.001092	-0.00047
Pol_Affil	0.075761	0.17784	0.113636
NAR_SCR_CEO	-0.017714	0.002047	-0.036965
GR	0.001567	-0.001585	0.00139
FS	-0.000798	0.004713	-0.00808
LVRG	0.00862	0.001805	0.012032
MTB	0.002988	0.003704	0.001141
PROF	0.010316	0.351199	0.139654
CH	0.012777	0.000578	0.009159
FA	-0.000666	-0.020296	-0.001456
Adjusted R Square (Fixed)	23.55%		
F-Statistics (Fixed)	3.312521		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Fixed)	0		
Durbin Watson (Fixed)	2.001943		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 414

The fixed effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.235452 which indicates that only 24% changes in the dependent variable (Systemic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on systemic risk, except for firm age, political affiliation and profitability. The independent variable insider ownership shows a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Whereas CEO and CFO gender, and CEO narcissism score shows a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. Political affiliation (0.1778) shows a positive and significant effect on systemic risk. This means that 1% change in political affiliation will increase systemic risk by 18%. The control variable growth shows a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Firm size, cash holding, leverage and market to book ratio show a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. Firm age (-0.02) shows a negative and significant impact on total risk. This means that 1% change in firm age leads to a 2% decrease in systemic risk. Political affiliation (0.351) shows a positive and significant impact on systemic risk. This means a 1% change in political affiliation will cause 35% increase in systemic risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.197825	0.503248	0.247576
G_CEO	0.158445	0.038199	0.144004
G_CFO	0.382361	0.21122	0.312979
IO	-0.000223	0.000214	-0.0000635
Pol_Affil	0.068042	0.175774	0.085205
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.085711	0.049259	0.090795
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.248789	0.094761	0.252309
GR	0.002674	-0.003267	0.001772
FS	0.002891	0.011221	0.00025
LVRG	0.006698	0.002054	0.008255
MTB	0.003725	0.006828	0.003295
PROF	-0.121769	0.249657	-0.049382
CH	0.013078	0.00425	0.011657
FA	-0.000452	-0.017583	-0.000572
Adjusted R Square (Random)	24.65%		
F-Statistics (Random)	3.472122		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.918606		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 394

Cross-sections: 40

The fixed effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.246477 which indicates that only 25% changes in the dependent variable (Systemic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on systemic risk, except for firm age and political affiliation. The independent variables insider ownership, CEO and CFO gender, and CEO and CFO narcissism signature shows a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. Whereas Political affiliation (0.175774) shows a positive and significant effect on systemic risk. This means that 1% change in political affiliation will increase systemic risk by 18%. The control variable growth shows a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Firm size, cash holding, leverage, market to book ratio and profitability show a positive

and insignificant impact on systemic risk. Firm age (-0.01758) shows a negative and significant impact on total risk. This means that 1% change in firm age leads to a 2% decrease in systemic risk.

China

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-0.186931	-0.406385	-0.335379
G_CEO	-0.006326	0.000207	-0.000297
G_CFO	-0.037447	0.000487	-0.012824
IO	0.005232	-0.012568	-0.001668
Pol_Affil	-0.001994	-0.009259	-0.008358
NAR_SCR_CEO	-0.026424	0.004065	-0.000188
GR	0.004989	-0.001727	-0.001729
FS	0.009223	0.015629	0.014951
LVRG	-0.003048	-0.008251	-0.007254
MTB	0.010417	0.013933	0.012812
PROF	0.0000935	-0.000111	-0.0000296
CH	-0.000203	-0.003215	-0.001426
FA	-0.000299	0.001395	-0.00000953
Adjusted R Square (Random)	1.91%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.749651		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.054206		
Durbin Watson (Random)	0.832612		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissism Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 463

Cross-sections: 49

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.0191 which indicates that only 2% changes in the dependent variable (Total Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk, except for firm size. The independent variables CEO narcissism score, political affiliation, insider ownership, and

CEO and CFO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. The control variables growth, leverage, cash holding, profitability and firm age show a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Market to book ratio shows a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. Firm size (0.0149) shows a positive and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in firm size leads to a 1% increase in total risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-0.054463	-0.323468	-0.237969
G_CEO	-0.007828	-0.012614	-0.009064
G_CFO	-0.016783	-0.000069	-0.005015
IO	-0.014314	-0.06007	-0.0221
Pol_Affil	-0.028565	-0.009905	-0.010742
NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.019617	0.009696	0.00673
GR	0.001716	-0.001921	-0.002116
FS	0.004574	0.012969	0.010963
LVRG	0.010887	-0.012361	-0.0069
MTB	0.00298	0.01117	0.008219
PROF	-0.000395	-0.0000935	-0.0000346
CH	-0.000768	-0.000367	0.000421
FA	-0.0000995	0.001317	0.000496
Adjusted R Square (Random)	-1.05%		
F-Statistics (Random)	0.733939		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.717842		
Durbin Watson (Random)	0.962314		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 308

Cross-sections: 31

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of -0.0105 which indicates that only 1% changes in the dependent variable (Total Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk, except for firm size and market to book value ratio. The independent variables political affiliation and CEO and

CFO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Whereas CEO narcissism signature and insider ownership shows a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. The control variables growth, leverage and profitability show a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Cash holdings and firm age show a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. Firm size (0.01096) and Market to book ratio (0.008219) shows a positive and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in firm age and market to book ratio leads to a 1% increase in total risk.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.523178	-1.749783	-0.26931
G_CEO	0.109899	0.108038	0.109108
G_CFO	0.057146	-0.031332	-0.016996
IO	-0.051959	0.109543	0.01267
Pol_Affil	0.028604	-0.051997	-0.00227
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.038253	0.052008	0.02926
GR	-0.017687	0.003575	-0.00701
FS	-0.0051	0.062058	0.027618
LVRG	-0.004921	-0.032801	-0.025931
MTB	-0.006006	0.053082	0.019975
PROF	-0.002409	-0.0000524	-0.000702
CH	-0.000853	-0.014685	-0.004511
FA	-0.0000717	0.019856	0.00134
Adjusted R Square (Fixed)	35.22%		
F-Statistics (Fixed)	5.186732		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Fixed)	0		
Durbin Watson (Fixed)	1.569623		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 463

Cross-sections: 49

The fixed effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.010152 which indicates that only 1% changes in the dependent variable (Idiosyncratic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on Idiosyncratic risk, except for firm size and profitability. The independent variables political affiliation and CFO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on Idiosyncratic risk. Whereas CEO gender, CEO narcissism score and insider ownership shows a positive and insignificant impact on Idiosyncratic risk. The control variables growth, and firm age show a positive and insignificant effect on Idiosyncratic risk. Leverage, profitability, and cash holding shows a negative and insignificant impact on Idiosyncratic risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.477853	-1.696568	-0.146131
G_CEO	0.102608	0.160873	0.189592
G_CFO	0.070418	-0.035788	-0.000536
IO	-0.050391	0.694552	0.151441
Pol_Affil	0.006854	-0.033121	0.004594
NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.019233	-0.013399	-0.057187
GR	-0.012145	0.009165	-0.001452
FS	0.001798	0.059673	0.022208
LVRG	-0.012189	-0.049473	-0.029365
MTB	-0.006618	0.062365	0.01636
PROF	-0.003408	0.000151	-0.000567
CH	-0.00544	-0.02889	-0.011534
FA	-0.00055	0.0156	0.001592
Adjusted R Square (Fixed)	37.52%		
F-Statistics (Fixed)	5.389001		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Fixed)	0		
Durbin Watson (Fixed)	1.554122		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 308

Cross-sections: 31

The fixed effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of -0.001641 which indicates that only 0.16% changes in the dependent variable (Idiosyncratic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for firm age, firm size, cash holdings and market to book ratio. The independent variables CFO gender, political affiliation, and CEO narcissism signature shows a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Whereas insider ownership and CEO gender shows a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. The control variables growth and profitability show a positive and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Leverage shows a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Firm age (0.0156), firm size (0.0596) and Market to book ratio (0.0624) shows a positive and significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. A 1% change in firm age, firm size and market to book ratio leads to a 2%, 6% and 6% increase respectively in idiosyncratic risk. Cash holding (-0.0289) has a negative and significant impact on idiosyncratic risk, meaning a 1% change in cash holdings leads to 3% decrease in idiosyncratic risk.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.162549	-0.72154	-0.193625
G_CEO	0.040108	-0.013533	0.009946
G_CFO	0.024227	-0.043455	-0.022721
IO	-0.05559	-0.030565	-0.03577
Pol_Affil	-0.008691	-0.041083	-0.024299
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.034249	0.03359	0.027663
GR	-0.003786	0.006593	0.002306
FS	-0.002476	0.026563	0.012901
LVRG	-0.001921	-0.019622	-0.013545
MTB	0.003577	0.025872	0.0148
PROF	-0.001441	-0.000245	-0.000645
CH	-0.01003	-0.015206	-0.012147
FA	0.000361	0.007668	0.001097
Adjusted R Square (Fixed)	32.61%		
F-Statistics (Fixed)	4.725685		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Fixed)	0		
Durbin Watson (Fixed)	1.745446		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 463

Cross-sections: 49

The fixed effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.32608 which indicates that only 33% changes in the dependent variable (Systemic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on systemic risk, except for firm age. The independent variable insider ownership, CEO and CFO gender, and political affiliation shows a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Whereas CEO narcissism score shows a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. The control variables growth, firm size, and market to book ratio shows a positive and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Leverage, profitably and cash holding show a negative and insignificant impact on systemic

risk. Firm age (0.007668) shows a positive and significant impact on systemic risk. This means that 1% change in firm age leads to a 1% increase in systemic risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.236372	-0.785802	-0.011751
G_CEO	0.031736	0.033867	0.064944
G_CFO	0.022623	-0.044482	-0.013641
IO	-0.073548	-0.075394	-0.031747
Pol_Affil	-0.019016	-0.033649	-0.022197
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.03328	-0.013666	-0.013915
GR	-0.003602	0.009043	0.003247
FS	-0.001761	0.029897	0.007013
LVRG	-0.00495	-0.040489	-0.01654
MTB	-0.001548	0.034431	0.008324
PROF	-0.002298	-0.00021	-0.000902
CH	-0.011713	-0.019317	-0.014154
FA	0.0002	0.006209	0.001157
Adjusted R Square (Random)	-1.02%		
F-Statistics (Random)	0.742397		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.709348		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.517339		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 308

Cross-sections: 31

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of -0.010172 which indicates that only 1% changes in the dependent variable (Systemic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on systemic risk. The independent variables insider ownership, CFO gender, and CEO and CFO narcissism signature shows a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. Whereas CEO gender show a positive and significant effect on systemic risk. The control variable growth, firm size, market

to book ratio, and firm age show a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Cash holding, leverage, and profitability show a negative and insignificant impact on systemic risk.

Bangladesh

Total Risk

Measure: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.088413	0.198284	0.100433
G_CEO	-0.004337	0.006567	-0.003865
G_CFO	-0.019946	0.008952	-0.016726
IO	-0.002204	-0.003407	-0.002417
Pol_Affil	-0.004496	-0.000144	-0.00263
NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.00211	0.0017	-0.000689
NAR_SIGN_CFO	-0.008063	0.002749	-0.008119
GR	-0.000288	-0.000146	-0.000211
FS	-0.002271	-0.007105	-0.002804
LVRG	-0.001084	0.00267	-0.000258
MTB	-0.000533	-0.005679	-0.001878
PROF	-0.00173	-0.001676	-0.001247
CH	0.001057	0.002185	0.001265
Adjusted R Square (Random)	-0.73%		
F-Statistics (Random)	0.712916		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.739318		
Durbin Watson (Random)	0.753223		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 479

Cross-sections: 50

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of – 0.00726 which indicates that -0.726% changes in the dependent variable i.e. Total Risk is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk, except for gender of CFO. The independent variables CEO gender, political affiliation, narcissism signature of CEO

and CFO and insider ownership shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. The control variables Growth, Firm size, leverage, Market-to-Book ratio and profitability show a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Cash holdings show a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. Gender of CFO (-0.01673) shows a negative and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in narcissism signature leads to a 1.6% decrease in total risk.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.59029	1.572526	0.597625
G_CEO	-0.021035	0.344986	0.003875
G_CFO	0.288566	0.364161	0.280821
IO	-0.041435	-0.062191	-0.047561
Pol_Affil	-0.110452	-0.073672	-0.100832
NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.010681	-0.072025	-0.026401
NAR_SIGN_CFO	-0.161519	-0.356842	-0.175837
GR	0.006909	0.007693	0.007057
FS	-0.031525	-0.075892	-0.030973
LVRG	0.007578	0.012678	0.009221
MTB	0.012778	0.013874	0.012922
PROF	0.009028	0.004873	0.010119
CH	-0.00739	0.00875	-0.003752
FA	-0.001693	0.00159	-0.001697
Adjusted R Square (Random)	4.60%		
F-Statistics (Random)	2.797584		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.000724		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.873896		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 486

Cross-sections: 50

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.045968 which indicates that only 4.5% changes in the dependent variable i.e. Idiosyncratic

Risk is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for CFO gender, political affiliation and narcissism signature of CEO. The independent variables CEO gender shows a positive and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Whereas insider ownership and narcissism signature of CFO shows a negative and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. The control variables growth, leverage, profitability, and market to book ratio show a positive and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Firm size, firm age and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. CFO gender (0.280821), political affiliation (-0.17584) and narcissism signature of CEO (-0.10083) shows a significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. A 1% change in CFO gender leads to a 28% increase in idiosyncratic risk. A 1% change in political affiliation leads to 17.58% decrease in idiosyncratic risk. While a 1% change in narcissism signature score of CEO leads to 10% decrease in idiosyncratic risk.

Systematic Risk

Measure: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-0.51424	-1.468673	-0.51034
G_CEO	0.019098	-0.30995	-0.011238
G_CFO	-0.313836	-0.355343	-0.30209
IO	0.038627	0.058077	0.045705
Pol_Affil	0.100779	0.065979	0.088491
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.008412	0.07724	0.028647
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.15123	0.334428	0.168085
GR	-0.007217	-0.007869	-0.007324
FS	0.029813	0.080492	0.028775
LVRG	-0.00995	-0.01223	-0.011923
MTB	-0.013536	-0.017655	-0.014244
PROF	-0.010589	-0.004453	-0.011554
CH	0.00871	-0.006305	0.004617
FA	0.001862	-0.006897	0.001781
Adjusted R Square (Random)	4.37%		
F-Statistics (Random)	2.682233		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.001195		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.878642		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.043662 which indicates that 4.36% changes in the dependent variable i.e. Systemic Risk is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on systemic risk, except for gender of CFO, political affiliation and narcissism signature of CEO. The independent variables CEO gender shows a negative and significant effect on systemic risk. Whereas, insider ownership and CFO narcissism signature score shows a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. The control variables firm size, cash holdings and firm age show a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Growth, market to book, profitability and leverage show a negative and insignificant impact on systemic risk. The variables of gender of CFO (-0.30209), political affiliation (0.168085) and narcissism signature of CEO (0.088491) show significant impact on systemic risk. A 1% change in CFO gender leads to 30% decrease in systemic risk. A 1% change in political affiliation leads to 16% increase in systemic risk. A 1% change in narcissism signature of CEO leads to an 8% increase in systemic risk.

Vietnam

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.14326	0.098688	0.144543
G_CEO	-0.009635	-0.002329	-0.00896
G_CFO	-0.01122	-0.009223	-0.010897
IO	0.026945	0.066249	0.044528
Pol_Affil	-0.003992	-0.001085	-0.001745
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.004128	0.003078	0.003032
GR	-0.000685	-0.002001	-0.001641
FS	-0.004134	-0.001649	-0.00421
LVRG	-0.000617	-0.000694	-0.000337
MTB	-0.002623	-0.000907	-0.002886
PROF	0.035465	0.019236	0.022505
CH	-0.001421	-0.001612	-0.001533
FA	0.0000762	-0.000932	-0.00000876
Adjusted R Square (Random)	12.30%		
F-Statistics (Random)	6.001361		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.607794		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 429

Cross-sections: 48

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.12298 which indicates that only 12% changes in the dependent variable (Total Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk, except for CFO gender, insider ownership profitability, firm size, and market to book ratio. The independent variables political affiliation and CEO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Whereas CFO narcissism score shows a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. The control variables growth, leverage, cash holdings and firm age show a negative and

insignificant effect on total risk. Firm size (-0.0042) and market to book ratio (-0.0029) shows a negative and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in firm size and market to book ratio leads to a 0.4% and 0.3% decrease respectively in total risk. The profitability (0.0225) shows a positive and significant impact on total risk, meaning 1% change in profitability will lead to 2% increase in total risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.147388	0.096148	0.149211
G_CEO	-0.011216	-0.006356	-0.011044
G_CFO	-0.010854	-0.005873	-0.009098
IO	0.031174	0.066574	0.047146
Pol_Affil	-0.00217	-0.001278	-0.000691
NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.001667	0.00000625	-0.000918
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.00898	0.009791	0.008372
GR	-0.000537	-0.001957	-0.001599
FS	-0.004328	-0.00156	-0.004482
LVRG	-0.000588	-0.000675	-0.000234
MTB	-0.002954	-0.000781	-0.003222
PROF	0.033723	0.017185	0.02085
CH	-0.001176	-0.001695	-0.001433
FA	0.000119	-0.00098	0.0000472
Adjusted R Square (Random)	11.94%		
F-Statistics (Random)	5.410158		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.590353		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 424

Cross-sections: 47

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.1194 which indicates that only 12% changes in the dependent variable (Total Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk, except for profitability,

market to book ratio, firm size, CFO narcissism signature, and insider ownership. The independent variables political affiliation, CEO narcissism signature, and CEO and CFO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. The control variables leverage, growth, and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Firm age shows a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. Firm size (-0.0045) and market to book ratio (-0.0032) show a negative and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in firm size and market to book ratio leads to a 0.4% and 0.3% decrease respectively in total risk. Insider ownership (0.047146), CFO narcissism signature (0.008372) and profitability (0.02085) show a positive and significant impact on total risk. This means that 1% change in Insider ownership, CFO narcissism signature and profitability will lead to a 5%, 1% and 2% increase in total risk.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	1.714992	0.5278	1.585458
G_CEO	-0.303137	-0.224665	-0.30536
G_CFO	-0.175307	-0.084208	-0.148789
IO	0.088357	-0.252693	-0.025097
Pol_Affil	0.061796	-0.04195	0.045544
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.033172	0.070697	0.054427
GR	0.003404	-0.004949	-0.001542
FS	-0.016553	0.029359	-0.012947
LVRG	0.013333	-0.055471	-0.015301
MTB	-0.015401	0.040799	-0.008822
PROF	-0.183747	-0.020633	-0.095059
CH	0.007737	0.029084	0.016337
FA	0.000403	-0.002069	0.00135
Adjusted R Square (Random)	5.328%		
F-Statistics (Random)	3.007293		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.000465		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.74467		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 429

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.053281 which indicates that only 5% changes in the dependent variable (Idiosyncratic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for CEO gender. The independent variables CFO gender and insider ownership shows a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Whereas political affiliation and CEO narcissism score shows a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. The control variables leverage, Growth, firm size, profitability, and market to book ratio show a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Cash holding and firm age show a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. CEO gender (-0.3053) shows a negative and significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. A 1% change in CEO gender leads to a 31% decrease in idiosyncratic risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	1.737874	0.356634	1.560397
G_CEO	-0.309422	-0.222145	-0.315982
G_CFO	-0.165264	-0.046509	-0.130787
IO	0.097872	-0.228543	-0.021641
Pol_Affil	0.065576	-0.032326	0.051094
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.003197	0.090166	0.048803
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.011968	0.056819	0.022712
GR	0.000691	-0.005063	-0.003655
FS	-0.01737	0.031915	-0.012798
LVRG	0.013404	-0.054488	-0.016089
MTB	-0.016051	0.042451	-0.008621
PROF	-0.18531	-0.043851	-0.097504
CH	0.009	0.035763	0.020416
FA	0.000582	0.001171	0.002324
Adjusted R Square (Random)	3.93%		
F-Statistics (Random)	2.329929		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.005356		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.815684		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.039268 which indicates that only 4% changes in the dependent variable (Idiosyncratic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for CEO gender. The independent variables CFO gender and insider ownership shows a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Whereas political affiliation, and CEO and CFO narcissism signature shows a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. The control variables growth, firm size, leverage, profitability and market to book ratio show a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Cash holding and firm size show a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. CEO gender (-0.315982) shows a negative and significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. A 1% change in CEO gender leads to a 32% decrease in idiosyncratic risk.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.615616	0.607752	0.612959
G_CEO	-0.103358	-0.004437	-0.103095
G_CFO	-0.027423	0.067537	-0.014983
IO	0.00891	-0.071102	0.00191
Pol_Affil	0.107948	0.066407	0.102093
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.009671	0.028487	0.015532
GR	0.012463	0.010431	0.011603
FS	-0.010022	-0.017712	-0.010285
LVRG	0.0157	0.00489	0.013192
MTB	-0.011583	-0.014693	-0.011547
PROF	0.304043	0.270481	0.29392
CH	0.011226	0.024448	0.013094
FA	0.003115	0.010052	0.003437
Adjusted R Square (Random)	10.64%		
F-Statistics (Random)	5.23808		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.843557		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.106427 which indicates that only 11% changes in the dependent variable (Systemic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on systemic risk, except for gender CEO, political affiliation, firm size, firm age, market to book ratio and profitability. The independent variable CFO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Whereas insider ownership and CEO narcissism score shows a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. Political affiliation (0.102093) shows a positive and significant effect on systemic risk. This means that 1% change in political affiliation will increase systemic risk by 10%. Insider ownership (-0.014983) shows a negative and significant effect on systemic risk. This means that 1% change in insider ownership will decrease systemic risk by 1%. The control variable growth, leverage and cash holdings shows a positive and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Firm size (-0.010285) and market to book ratio (-0.011547) shows a negative and significant impact on total risk. This means that 1% change in firm size and market to book ratio leads to a 1% decrease in systemic risk. Firm age (0.29392) and profitability (0.003437) shows a positive and significant impact on systemic risk. This means a 1% change in firm age and profitability will cause 0% and 29% increase respectively in systemic risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.636164	0.576063	0.634059
G_CEO	-0.10404	-0.044631	-0.107479
G_CFO	-0.032454	0.090133	-0.007183
IO	0.012145	-0.0838	0.004345
Pol_Affil	0.107145	0.067357	0.10061
NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.033597	-0.02628	-0.024879
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.016874	0.066134	0.026563
GR	0.012049	0.010147	0.010676
FS	-0.010069	-0.016328	-0.010841
LVRG	0.013504	0.004507	0.010906
MTB	-0.011436	-0.013442	-0.011938
PROF	0.295153	0.256273	0.282069
CH	0.011612	0.026487	0.014804
FA	0.002829	0.010056	0.003531
Adjusted R Square (Random)	8.52%		
F-Statistics (Random)	4.022862		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.000003		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.873002		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, FS: Firm Size, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 424

Cross-sections: 47

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.085188 which indicates that only 9% changes in the dependent variable (Systemic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on systemic risk, except for CEO gender firm age, market to book ratio, profitability, and political affiliation. The independent variables CFO gender and CEO narcissism signature shows a negative and insignificant impact on systemic risk. Whereas insider ownership and CFO narcissism signature shows a positive and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Political affiliation (0.10061) shows a positive and significant impact on systemic risk. This means that 1% change

in political affiliation will increase systemic risk by 10%. CEO gender (-0.107479) has a negative and significant impact on systemic risk. This means that 1% change in political affiliation will increase systemic risk by 11%. The control variable growth, leverage and cash holdings shows a positive and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Firm size shows a negative and insignificant impact on systemic risk. Firm age (0.003531) and profitability (0.282069) shows a positive and significant impact on total risk. This means that 1% change in firm age and profitability leads to a 0% and 28% increase in systemic risk. Market to book ratio (-0.011938) has a negative and significant impact on systemic risk, meaning 1% decrease in market to book ratio leads to a 1% decrease in systemic risk.

Malaysia

Total Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.04996	0.02909	0.045673
G_CEO	0.002764	0.003112	0.002695
G_CFO	-0.004	-0.001064	-0.00229
IO	-0.006386	-0.002067	-0.002151
Pol_Affil	-0.002025	-0.009588	-0.004948
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.064797	0.078772	0.070303
NAR_SCR_CFO	-0.047087	-0.031917	-0.035375
GR	0.000934	0.000599	0.000642
LVRG	0.000166	0.002542	0.000589
MTB	-0.000813	0.001029	-0.000468
PROF	0.000236	-0.000229	-0.000086
CH	0.0003	-0.002153	-0.000044
FA	-0.0000856	0.0000035	-0.000077
Adjusted R Square (Random)	-0.14%		
F-Statistics (Random)	0.943041		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.503309		
Durbin Watson (Random)	2.162152		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissism Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SCR_CFO: Narcissism Screenshot Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of -0.0014 which indicates that only 0.14% changes in the dependent variable i.e. Total Risk is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk. The independent variables insider ownership, political affiliation, narcissism signature of CFO and CFO gender shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Whereas narcissism score of CEO and CEO gender shows a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. The control variables market to book, profitability, cash holdings and firm age show a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Growth, and leverage show a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. Narcissism score of CEO (0.070303) has a positive and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in CFO gender leads to 7% increase in total risk of a firm.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.051495	0.027348	0.047444
G_CEO	0.002928	0.005016	0.002848
G_CFO	-0.003881	-0.001369	-0.002122
IO	-0.008109	0.000721	-0.004037
Pol_Affil	-0.001785	-0.008729	-0.004763
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.00014	0.006263	0.000749
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.000114	0.008441	0.0000509
GR	0.001098	0.000702	0.000753
LVRG	0.0002	0.001642	0.000494
MTB	-0.000843	0.001121	-0.00046
PROF	0.000286	-0.000209	-0.0000609
CH	0.000326	-0.001922	-0.000018
FA	-0.0000889	-0.000055	-0.0000805
Adjusted R Square (Random)	-1.26%		
F-Statistics (Random)	0.491039		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.920181		
Durbin Watson (Random)	2.193672		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 490

Cross-sections: 50

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of -0.012648 which indicates that 1.26% changes in the dependent variable (Total Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on total risk. The independent variables CFO gender, political affiliation, and insider ownership shows a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. The independent variables of CEO gender, narcissism signature of CEO and CFO show a positive and significant impact on total risk. The control variables market to book, firm age, profitability and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant effect on total risk. Growth and leverage show a positive and insignificant impact on total risk.

Idiosyncratic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-0.267683	-1.506046	-0.310688
G_CEO	0.040031	0.124009	0.092523
G_CFO	0.030003	-0.008564	0.050461
IO	-0.126411	-0.372351	-0.111309
Pol_Affil	-0.008535	-0.028776	-0.015457
NAR_SCR_CEO	-0.169967	-0.343244	-0.227338
NAR_SCR_CFO	0.065333	-0.394647	-0.168042
GR	-0.03971	-0.033642	-0.038043
LVRG	-0.006506	-0.013699	-0.011129
MTB	-0.008211	0.009734	-0.003271
PROF	0.008029	-0.000258	0.002121
CH	-0.006211	0.012093	-0.007758
FA	-0.000978	0.027984	-0.000439
Adjusted R Square (Random)	0.233%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.095347		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.361699		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.604222		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SCR_CFO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 490

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of -0.002334 which indicates that only 0.23% changes in the dependent variable i.e. Idiosyncratic Risk is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for insider ownership and narcissism score of CEO and CFO. The independent variable political affiliation show a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Whereas CEO and CFO gender shows a positive and insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk. The control variables leverage, growth, market to book ratio and profitability firm age and cash holdings show a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Insider ownership (-0.111309) and narcissism score of CEO (-0.227338) and CFO (-0.168042) shows a significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. Insider ownership shows a negative and significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in insider ownership leads to an 11% decrease in idiosyncratic risk. Narcissism score of CFO shows a significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. A 1% change in narcissism score of CEO leads to 22% decrease in idiosyncratic risk. Narcissism score of CFO shows a significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. A 1% change in narcissism score of CFO leads to 16% decrease in idiosyncratic risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	-0.27762	-1.579158	-0.332165
G_CEO	0.035021	0.141451	0.089953
G_CFO	0.031606	-0.006991	0.050999
IO	-0.093577	-0.38763	-0.085676
Pol_Affil	-0.014005	-0.028764	-0.017663
NAR_SIGN_CEO	0.015099	0.08518	0.016555
NAR_SIGN_CFO	-0.082076	0.025029	-0.079295
GR	-0.041033	-0.033301	-0.038819
LVRG	-0.003988	-0.012003	-0.008101
MTB	-0.004441	0.011121	-0.000144
PROF	0.005449	0.000212	0.000932
CH	-0.006454	0.010274	-0.008243
FA	-0.000935	0.027418	-0.000395
Adjusted R Square (Random)	0.66%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.270035		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.232884		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.61881		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 490

Cross-sections: 50

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of -0.006583 which indicates that only 0.658% changes in the dependent variable (Idiosyncratic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for CEO gender. The independent variables insider ownership, political affiliation, and narcissism signature of CFO shows a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. Whereas CFO gender and narcissism signature of CEO shows a positive and significant impact on idiosyncratic risk. The control variables leverage, firm age, cash holdings, growth, market to book ratio and profitability show a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk.

CEO gender (0.089953), shows a significant impact on total risk. A 1% change in CEO gender leads to an 8.9% increase in idiosyncratic risk.

Systematic Risk

Measure 1: Narcissism Score

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.318819	1.535944	0.359851
G_CEO	-0.038331	-0.121214	-0.091666
G_CFO	-0.033191	0.010395	-0.05128
IO	0.119051	0.371751	0.107761
Pol_Affil	0.006159	0.018021	0.009968
NAR_SCR_CEO	0.247792	0.42956	0.307883
NAR_SCR_CFO	-0.125826	0.353342	0.124914
GR	0.040955	0.034925	0.039139
LVRG	0.006473	0.015208	0.011563
MTB	0.007538	-0.00904	0.002708
PROF	-0.007807	-4.49E-05	-0.002147
CH	0.00628	-0.014104	0.007647
FA	0.000869	-0.02789	0.000331
Adjusted R Square (Random)	0.29%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.119874		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.341278		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.599476		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SCR_CEO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CEO, NAR_SCR_CFO: Narcissim Screenshot Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 490

Cross-sections: 50

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.2069 which indicates that only 20% changes in the dependent variable i.e. Systemic Risk is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on idiosyncratic risk, except for insider ownership, CEO gender, CEO and CFO narcissism score. The independent variables CEO gender shows a negative and significant effect on systemic risk. Whereas political affiliation and gender of CFO shows a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. The

control variables Market to book, firm age and cash holdings shows a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Growth, Leverage, and profitability show a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. The insider ownership (0.3718), CEO (0.4296) and CFO narcissism score (0.3533) shows a positive and significant impact on systemic risk. CEO gender shows a significant impact on systemic risk. A 1% change in insider ownership leads to 37.18% increase in systemic risk. A 1% change in CEO narcissism leads to 42.96% increase in systemic risk. A 1% increase in narcissism score of CFO leads to 35% change in systemic risk. Narcissism score of CFO shows a significant impact on systemic risk. The CEO gender shows a negative significant impact on systemic risk. A 1% change in CEO gender leads to 12.12% decrease in systemic risk.

Measure 2: Narcissism Signature

Variable	Common Effect Model	Fixed Effect Model	Random Effect Model
Constant	0.33075	1.608036	0.384741
G_CEO	-0.033202	-0.136892	-0.089694
G_CFO	-0.034707	0.008548	-0.051775
IO	0.084514	0.390053	0.080204
Pol_Affil	0.01206	0.018997	0.012533
NAR_SIGN_CEO	-0.015731	-0.079736	-0.016465
NAR_SIGN_CFO	0.081602	-0.016828	0.078623
GR	0.042423	0.034695	0.039999
LVRG	0.003994	0.012543	0.0085
MTB	0.003753	-0.010356	-0.000478
PROF	-0.005164	-0.00049	-0.000905
CH	0.006563	-0.011976	0.008248
FA	0.000823	-0.027382	0.000275
Adjusted R Square (Random)	0.68%		
F-Statistics (Random)	1.279356		
Prob. (F-Stats) (Random)	0.227108		
Durbin Watson (Random)	1.616455		

G_CEO: Gender CEO, G_CFO: Gender CFO, IO: Insider Ownership, Pol_Affil: Political Affiliation, NAR_SIGN_CEO: Narcissism Signature Score of CEO, NAR_SIGN_CFO: Narcissism Signature Score of CFO, GR: Growth Rate, LVRG: Leverage, MTB: Market-to-Book Ratio, PROF: Profitability, CH: Cash Holding, FA: Firm Age

*Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.05

**Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.01

***Coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001

Observations: 490

Cross-sections: 50

The random effect model, in *Table above*, shows that the Adjusted R Square has a value of 0.2041 which indicates that 20% changes in the dependent variable (Systemic Risk) is due to other variables. All variables show an insignificant impact on systemic risk except for insider ownership and CEO gender. The independent variables narcissism signature of CEO and CFO shows a negative and significant effect on systemic risk. Whereas, political affiliation and gender of CFO shows a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. The control variables Market-to-Book ratio, cash holdings, firm age and profitability show a negative and insignificant effect on systemic risk. Growth, and leverage show a positive and insignificant impact on systemic risk. The independent variables of CEO gender (-0.1369) and insider ownership (0.3901) have significant impact on systemic risk. A 1% change in CEO gender leads to 13.7% decrease in systemic risk. While a 1% increase in insider ownership leads to 39% increase in systemic risk.

Conclusion

The research provided mixed results for the impact of gender on total risk, idiosyncratic and systematic risk. However, some of the trends that were observed in our research shows that gender of both CEO and CFO had a negative impact on total risk for some countries that include Pakistan, China and Vietnam. In Malaysia, CFO gender had a positive and insignificant impact on total risk. CEOs in some countries had a negative and insignificant effect on idiosyncratic risk. These countries include Bangladesh, India and Vietnam. Apart from Malaysia, gender of CEOs and CFOs had a negative and insignificant impact on systematic risk.

Gender is related to systematic risk because it studies the impact the external factors that have an influence on market risk. While a weak relationship with idiosyncratic risk is present due to less influence of such factors on company's stakeholder decision. Our study proved that gender differences vary across different countries. The future direction for our research could be to study the relationship between risk management strategies and gender diversity of a firm.

The test results show that insider ownership has negative relationship with total risk but it was positive for India and Vietnam. We also found that insider ownership had positive impact on Idiosyncratic risk for Pakistan, India, and China but negative impact on Bangladesh, Vietnam, and Malaysia. Lastly, it negatively impacts a firm's systematic risk but the relationship is insignificant.

Insider ownership is related to idiosyncratic risk as any decisions or actions by any stakeholder of the company would directly impact idiosyncratic risk. It has negative relation with total risk suggesting the top executives avoid indulging in risky ventures to protect their holding. It is possible for the countrywide differences to be due to differing trend of portfolio of shares in different countries. If an executive has significant portion of shares of only one firm that he/she is working for in their portfolio, then they would be risk averse (Smith and Schulz, 1985). Hence to further look into the relation between insider ownership and risk, diversification of portfolios held by the executives could be studied.

The influence of political party affiliation on total, idiosyncratic, and systematic risks in Pakistan, India, China, Bangladesh, and Vietnam reveals some significant but largely low associations. Political affiliation of the CFO shows relatively significant positive associations in Pakistan. Political affiliation has a slightly positive association with insider ownership and firm size in India. Furthermore, political affiliation shows a slight positive significant association in Malaysia. Overall, the findings suggest that political party affiliation has some effect on total, idiosyncratic, and systematic risks in these nations, but the effect is often small. As a result, while political affiliation should be considered in risk management decisions, it should not be the primary determinant.

Based on our data and test results, executive narcissism positively effects total risk in Vietnam and Pakistan. On the other hand, executive narcissism has a negative effect on idiosyncratic risk and a positive effect on systemic risk in Bangladesh and Malaysia. There is no impact of executive narcissism on any risk measure in India and China.

Executive narcissism's positive impact on total risk in a country means that certain industries and companies of that country have more narcissistic executives that take on more riskier projects. Executive narcissism's positive impact on systemic risk in a country implies that only certain industries have more narcissistic executives in that country. Negative impact of executive narcissism on systemic risk in a country indicates that only certain firms in that country have narcissistic executives that don't pursue many risky projects. This variation in narcissistic executives across countries could be due to differences in culture and values. Further studies on how narcissistic executives impact firms across different countries can be conducted.

The end

References

- Aabo, T., & Eriksen, N. B. (2018). Corporate risk and the humpback of CEO narcissism. *Review of Behavioral Finance*, 1940-5979.
- Abu-Ghunmi, D., Bino, A., & Tayeh, M. (2015). Idiosyncratic risk and corporate governance: evidence from Jordan. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 51(sup4), S40-S50.
- Acemoglu, D. (2005). *The Form of Property Rights: Oligarchic vs. Demo.*
- Agnew, J. R., Anderson, L. R., Gerlach, J. R., & Szykman, L. R. (2008). Who chooses annuities? An experimental investigation of the role of gender, framing, and defaults. *American Economic Review*, 98(2), 418-422.
- Agrawal, A., & Knoeber, C. R. (2001a). Do some outside directors play a political role? *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 44(1), 179–198.
- Agrawal, A., & Knoeber, C. R. (2001b). Do some outside directors play a political role? *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 44(1), 179–198.
- Agrawal, A., & Mandelker, G. N. (1987). Managerial incentives and corporate investment and financing decisions. *The journal of finance*, 42(4), 823-837.
- Aktas, N., Bodt, E. d., & Bollaert, H. (2016). CEO Narcissism and the Takeover Process: From Private Initiation to Deal Completion. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 113-137.
- Alesina, A. F., & Sachs, J. D. (1986). *Political parties and the business cycle in the United States, 1948-1984.* National Bureau of Economic Research Cambridge, Mass., USA.
- Alesina, A., & Rosenthal, H. (1995). *Partisan politics, divided government, and the economy.* Cambridge University Press.
- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). 669-670.
- Amesa, D. R., Rose, P., & Andersonc, C. P. (2006). The NPI-16 as a short measure of narcissism. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 440-450.
- Amihud, Y., & Lev, B. (1981). Risk reduction as a managerial motive for conglomerate mergers. *The bell journal of economics*, 605-617.
- Ansolabehere, S., Snyder, J., & Ueda, M. (2004). Campaign finance regulations and the return on investment from campaign contributions. Unpublished Working Paper. Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Arano, K., Parker, C., & Terry, R. (2010). Gender-Based Risk Aversion and Retirement Asset Allocation. *Economic Inquiry*, 48(1), 147–155.

Arch, E. (1993). Risk-Taking: A Motivational Basis for Sex Differences. *Psychological Reports*, 73(3), 6-11.

Aren, S., & Hamamci, H. N. (2020). Relationship between risk aversion, risky investment intention, investment choices: Impact of personality traits and emotion. *Kybernetes*.

Arenson, S. J. (1978). Age and Sex Differences in the probability preferences of children. *Psychological Reports*, 43(3), 697-698.

Backman, M. (2001). *Asian eclipse: Exposing the dark side of business in Asia*. Wiley.

Bajtelsmit, V. L., & Bernasek, A. (1996). Why do women invest differently than men? *Financial counseling and planning*.

Barber, B., & Odean, T. (2000). Boys will be Boys: Gender, Overconfidence and Common Stock Investment. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 116(1), 261-292.

Barton, S. L., & Gordon, P. I. (1987). Corporate strategy: useful perspective for the study of capital structure? *Academy of Management Review*, 12(1), 67-75.

Barua, A., , L. F., Rama, D. V., & Thiruvadi, S. (2010). CFO gender and accruals quality. *Accounting Horizons*, 24(1), 25-39.

Bauer, R., Derwall, J., & Pankratz, N. (2021). Insider ownership, governance mechanisms, and corporate bond pricing around the world. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 117, 102423.

Belkhir, M. (2005). Additional evidence on insider ownership and bank risk-taking. *Bankers, Markets & Investors (Banques et Marche)*, 78, 34-43.

Berg, G., & Zia, B. (2013). *Harnessing Emotional Connections to Improve Financial Decisions Evaluating the Impact of Financial Education in Mainstream Media*. Policy Research Working Paper.

Bergman, S. M., Fearington, M. E., Davenport, S. W., & Bergman, J. Z. (2011). Millennials, narcissism, and social networking: What narcissists do on social networking sites and why. *Personality and Individual differences*, 706-711.

Bernasek, A., & Shwiff, S. (2001). Gender, Risk, and Retirement. *Journal of Economic Issues*, 35(2), 345-356.

Bertrand, M., & Schoar, A. (2003). Managing with style: The effect of managers on firm policies. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118(4), 1169–1208.

Bertrand, M., Kramarz, F., Schoar, A., & Thesmar, D. (2004). Politically connected CEOs and corporate outcomes: Evidence from France. Unpublished Manuscript.

Biais, B., & Perotti, E. (2002). Machiavellian privatization. *American Economic Review*, 92(1), 240–258.

Bitler, M. P., Moskowitz, T. J., & Vissing-Jørgensen, A. (2005). Testing agency theory with entrepreneur effort and wealth. *The journal of finance*, 60(2), 539-576.

Black, L., & Hazelwood, L. (2013). The Effect of TARP on Bank Risk-Taking. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 790-803.

Black, S. E., Devereux, P. J., Lundborg, P., & Majlesi, K. (2015). LEARNING TO TAKE RISKS? THE EFFECT OF EDUCATION ON RISK-TAKING IN FINANCIAL MARKETS. NATIONAL BUREAU OF ECONOMIC RESEARCH.

Blumentritt, T. P. (2003). Foreign subsidiaries' government affairs activities: The influence of managers and resources. *Business & Society*, 42(2), 202–233.

Bogart, L. M., Benotsch, E. G., & Pav, J. D. (2004). Feeling superior but threatened: the relation of narcissism to social comparison. *Basic and Applied Social Psychology*, 35-44.

Bogart, L. M., Benotsch, E. G., & Pavlovic, J. D. (2004). Feeling Superior but Threatened: The Relation of Narcissism to Social Comparison. *Basic and Applied Social Psychology*, 35–44.

Borghans, L., Heckman, J. J., Golsteyn, B. H., & Meijers, H. (2009). Gender differences in risk aversion and ambiguity aversion. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 7(2-3), 649-658.

Boubaker, S., Mansali, H., & Rjiba, H. (2014). Large controlling shareholders and stock price synchronicity. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 40, 80-96.

Boubakri, N., Cosset, J., & Saffar, W. (2012). THE IMPACT OF POLITICAL CONNECTIONS ON FIRMS' OPERATING PERFORMANCE AND FINANCING DECISIONS. *Journal of Financial Research*, 35(3), 397–423.

Boubakri, N., Cosset, J.-C., & Saffar, W. (2013). The role of state and foreign owners in corporate risk-taking: Evidence from privatization. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 108(3), 641–658.

Boubakri, N., Mansi, S. A., & Saffar, W. (2013). Political institutions, connectedness, and corporate risk-taking. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 44(3), 195–215.

Brouwer, P. (2018). CEO Narcissism and Firm Valuation.

Brown, A. D. (1997). Narcissism, Identity, and Legitimacy. *The Academy of Management Review*, 643-686 .

Brummelman, E., Thomaes, S., & Sedikides, C. (2016). Separating narcissism from self-esteem. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 8-13.

- Brunell, A. B., Gentry, W. A., Campbell, W. K., Hoffman, B. J., Kuhnert, K. W., & DeMarree, K. G. (2008). Leader Emergence: The Case of the Narcissistic Leader. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 1663-1676.
- Burris, V. (2001). The two faces of capital: Corporations and individual capitalists as political actors. *American Sociological Review*, 361–381.
- Buyl, T., Boone, C., & Wade, J. B. (2019). CEO Narcissism, Risk-Taking, and Resilience: An Empirical Analysis in U.S. Commercial Banks. *Journal of Management*, 1372–1400.
- Byrnes, J. P. (2013). *The Nature and Development of Decision-Making: A self-regulation model*. Psychology press.
- Campbell, J. Y., Lettau, M., Malkiel, B. G., & Xu, Y. (2001). Have individual stocks become more volatile? An empirical exploration of idiosyncratic risk. *The journal of finance*, 56(1), 1-43.
- Campbell, W. K. (1999). Narcissism and romantic attraction. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 1254–1270.
- Campbell, W. K., & Foster, J. D. (2007). The narcissistic self: Background, an extended agency model, and ongoing controversies. *Frontiers of Social Psychology*, 115–138.
- Campbell, W. K., Foster, J., & Goodie, A. S. (2004). Narcissism, confidence, and risk attitude. *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making*, 297–311.
- Campbell, W. K., Goodie, A. S., & Foster, J. D. (2004). Narcissism, Confidence, and Risk Attitude. *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making*, 1-15.
- Campbell, W. K., Hoffman, B. J., Campbell, S. M., & Marchisio, G. (2011). Narcissism in organizational contexts. *Human Resource Management Review*, 268-284.
- Campbell, W. K., Reeder, G. D., Sedikides, C., & Elliot, A. J. (2000). Narcissism and Comparative Self-Enhancement Strategies. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 329–347.
- Capalbo, F., Frino, A., Lim, M. Y., Mollica, V., & Palumbo, R. (2017). The Impact of CEO Narcissism on Earnings Management. *ABACUS*, 210-226.
- Caprio, L., Faccio, M., & McConnell, J. J. (2013). Sheltering corporate assets from political extraction. *The Journal of Law, Economics, & Organization*, 29(2), 332–354.
- Carlin, W., & Mayer, C. (2000). How do financial systems affect economic performance. *Corporate governance: theoretical and empirical perspectives*, 137-159.
- Carr, P. B., & Steele, C. M. (2010). Stereotype threat affects financial decision making. *Psychological Science*, 21(10), 1411-1416.

- Chaganti, R., & Damanpour, F. (1991). Institutional ownership, capital structure, and firm performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 12(7), 479-491.
- Chaney, P. K., Faccio, M., & Parsley, D. (2011). The quality of accounting information in politically connected firms. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 51(1-2), 58-76.
- Chappell, H. W. (1982). Campaign contributions and congressional voting: A simultaneous probit-tobit model. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 77-83.
- Charumilind, C., Kali, R., & Wiwattanakantang, Y. (2006). Connected lending: Thailand before the financial crisis. *The Journal of Business*, 79(1), 181-218.
- Chatterjee, A., & Hambrick, D. C. (2007). It's All about Me: Narcissistic Chief Executive Officers and Their Effects on Company Strategy and Performance. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 523-51.
- Chatterjee, A., & Hambrick, D. C. (2011). Executive personality, capability cues, and risk taking: how narcissistic CEOs react to their successes and stumbles. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 202-237.
- Chatterjee, A., & Pollock, T. G. (2017). Master of puppets: how narcissistic CEOs construct their professional worlds. *Academy of Management Review*, 703-725.
- Chen, C. R., & Steiner, T. L. (1999). Managerial ownership and agency conflicts: A nonlinear simultaneous equation analysis of managerial ownership, risk taking, debt policy, and dividend policy. *Financial review*, 34(1), 119-136.
- Chen, C. R., Steiner, T. L., & Whyte, A. M. (1998). Risk-taking behavior and management ownership in depository institutions. *Journal of Financial Research*, 21(1), 1-16.
- Chiang, R., & Venkatesh, P. (1988). Insider holdings and perceptions of information asymmetry: A note. *The journal of finance*, 43(4), 1041-1048.
- Chiodo, L. M., & Buss, D. M. (1991). Narcissistic Acts in Everyday Life. *Journal of Personality*, 179-215.
- Chun, S., & Lee, M. (2017). Corporate ownership structure and risk-taking: evidence from Japan. *Journal of Governance and Regulation*. https://doi.org/10.22495/jgr_v6_i4_p4.
- Claessens, S., Djankov, S., & Lang, L. H. P. (2000). The separation of ownership and control in East Asian corporations. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 58(1-2), 81-112.
- Coate, S. (2004). Pareto-improving campaign finance policy. *American Economic Review*, 94(3), 628-655.
- Cole, S. (2009). Fixing market failures or fixing elections? Agricultural credit in India. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 1(1), 219-250.

- Cook, R. G., & Barry, D. (1995). Shaping the external environment: A study of small firms' attempts to influence public policy. *Business & Society*, 34(3), 317–344.
- Croson, Rachel, & Gneezy, U. (2009). Gender Differences in Preferences. *Journal of Economic*, 448-474.
- Cup, A., Fessler, P., & Schneebaum, A. (2020). Gender differences in risky asset behavior: The importance of Self-Confidence and Financial Literacy. *Finance Research Letters*.
- Demaree, H. A., DeDonno, M. A., Burns, K. J., Feldman, P., & Everhart, D. E. (2009). Trait dominance predicts risk-taking. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 47(5), 419-422.
- Demsetz, H., & Lehn, K. (1985). The structure of corporate ownership: Causes and consequences. *Journal of Political Economy*, 93(6), 1155–1177.
- Demsetz, H., & Lehn, K. (1985). The structure of corporate ownership: Causes and consequences. *Journal of Political Economy*, 93(6), 1155-1177.
- Demsetz, H., & Villalonga, B. (2001). Ownership structure and corporate performance. *Journal of corporate finance*, 7(3), 209-233.
- Dhillon, A., & Rossetto, S. (2015). Ownership structure, voting, and risk. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 28(2), 521-560.
- Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-IV-TR. (2012). American Psychiatric Publishing, Inc. Retrieved from American Psychiatric Publishing, Inc.
- Dinç, I. S. (2005a). Politicians and banks: Political influences on government-owned banks in emerging markets. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 77(2), 453–479.
- Dinç, I. S. (2005b). Politicians and banks: Political influences on government-owned banks in emerging markets. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 77(2), 453–479.
- Ding, S., Jia, C., Qu, B., & Wu, Z. (2015). Corporate risk-taking: Exploring the effects of government affiliation and executives' incentives. *Journal of Business Research*, 68(6), 1196–1204.
- Downs, D. H., & Sommer, D. W. (1999). Monitoring, ownership, and risk-taking: the impact of guaranty funds. *Journal of Risk and Insurance*, 477-497.
- Du, J., & Girma, S. (2010). Red capitalists: Political connections and firm performance in China. *Kyklos*, 63(4), 530–545.
- Duppati, G., Kijkasiwat, P., Hunjra, A. I., & Liew, C. Y. (2022). Do institutional ownership and innovation influence idiosyncratic risk? *Global Finance Journal*, 100770.

Durnev, A., & Fauver, L. (2008). Stealing from thieves: Firm governance and performance when states are predatory. Center for Economic Institutions, Institute of Economic Research
....

Dwyer, P. D., Gilkeson, J. H., & List, J. A. (2002). Gender differences in revealed risk taking: evidence from mutual fund investors. *Economics Letters*, 76(2), 152-158.

Eckel, C. C., & Grossman, P. J. (2008). Men, Women and Risk Aversion: Experimental Evidence. *Handbook of experimental economics results*, 1, 1061-1073.

Eisenmann, T. R. (2002). The effects of CEO equity ownership and firm diversification on risk taking. *Strategic Management Journal*, 23(6), 513-534.

Emmons, R. A. (1987). Narcissism: Theory and measurement. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 11-17.

Erkaningrum, I. F. (2013). Interactions Among Insider Ownership, Dividend Policy, Debt Policy, Investment Decision, And Business Risk. *Journal of Indonesian Economy and Business: JIEB.*, 28(1), 132.

Ermer, E., Cosmides, L., & Tooby, J. (2008). Relative status regulates risky decision making about resources in men: Evidence for the co-evolution of motivation and cognition. *Evolution and Human Behavior*, 29(2), 106-118.

Estes, R., & Hosseini, J. (1988). The Gender Gap on Wall Street: an Empirical Analysis of Confidence in Investment Decision making. *The Journal of Psychology*, 122(6), 577-590.

Faccio, M. (2006). Politically connected firms. *American Economic Review*, 96(1), 369–386.

Faccio, M. (2007). The characteristics of politically connected firms.

Faccio, M. (2010). Differences between politically connected and nonconnected firms: A cross-country analysis. *Financial Management*, 39(3), 905–928.

Faccio, M., & Lang, L. H. P. (2002). The ultimate ownership of Western European corporations. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 65(3), 365–395.

Faccio, M., Masulis, R. W., & McConnell, J. J. (2006). Political connections and corporate bailouts. *The Journal of Finance*, 61(6), 2597–2635.

Fama, E. F. (1980). Agency problems and the theory of the firm. *Journal of Political Economy*, 88(2), 288-307.

Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 26(2), 301–325.

Fan, J. P. H., & Wong, T. J. (2002). Corporate ownership structure and the informativeness of accounting earnings in East Asia. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 33(3), 401–425.

Felton, J., Gibson, B., & Sanbonmatsu, D. M. (2003). Preference for risk in investing as a function of trait optimism and gender. *The journal of behavioral finance*, 4(1), 33-40.

Finkel, E. J., Campbell, W. K., Brunell, A. B., Dalton, A. N., Scarbeck, S. J., & Chartrand, T. L. (2006). High-maintenance interaction: Inefficient social coordination impairs self-regulation. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 456–475.

Finkelstein, S., & Hambrick, D. C. (1996). *Strategic Leadership: Top Executives and their Effects*. West Publishing, Minneapolis and St Paul, MN.

Fisman, D., Fisman, R. J., Galef, J., Khurana, R., & Wang, Y. (2012). Estimating the value of connections to Vice-President Cheney. *The BE Journal of Economic Analysis & Policy*, 13(3).

Fisman, R. (2001a). Estimating the value of political connections. *American Economic Review*, 91(4), 1095–1102.

Fisman, R. (2001b). Estimating the value of political connections. *American Economic Review*, 91(4), 1095–1102.

Florackis, C., Kanas, A., & Kostakis, A. (2014). Idiosyncratic risk, risk-taking incentives and the link between managerial ownership and firm value. Available at SSRN 2114391.

Florackis, C., Kanas, A., Kostakis, A., & Sainani, S. (2020). Idiosyncratic risk, risk-taking incentives and the relation between managerial ownership and firm value. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 283(2), 748-766.

Fogel, K., Morck, R., & Yeung, B. (2008). Big business stability and economic growth: Is what's good for General Motors good for America? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 89(1), 83–108.

Foster, J. D., Reidy, D. E., Misra, T. A., & Goff, J. S. (2011). Narcissism and stock market investing: Correlates and consequences of cocksure investing. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 816-821.

Foster, J., Reidy, D. E., & Misra, T. A. (2009). Narcissists are approach-oriented toward their money and their friends. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 764–769.

Francis, B., Hasan, I., Park, J. C., & Wu, Q. (2015). Gender differences in financial reporting decision making: Evidence from accounting conservatism. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 32(3), 1285-1318.

Francis, J., LaFond, R., Olsson, P., & Schipper, K. (2005). The market pricing of accruals quality. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 39(2), 295–327.

- Gadhoun, Y., & Ayadi, M. A. (2003). Ownership structure and risk: A Canadian empirical analysis. *Quarterly Journal of Business and Economics*, 19-39.
- Galasso, A., & Simcoe, T. S. (2011). CEO Overconfidence and Innovation. *Management Science*, 1469-1484.
- Ge, W., Matsumoto, D., & Zhang, J. L. (2011). "Do CFOs have style? An empirical investigation of the effect of individual CFOs on accounting practices. *Contemporary accounting research*, 28(4), 1141-1179.
- Geeta, R., & Prasanna, K. (2016). Impact of family ownership on idiosyncratic risk. *International Journal of Corporate Governance*, 7(4), 325-352.
- Gerstner, W. C., König, A., Enders, A., & Hambrick, D. C. (2013). CEO Narcissism, Audience Engagement, and Organizational Adoption of Technological Discontinuities. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 257-291.
- Ghafoor, S., Zulfiqar, M., & Khurshid, M. K. (2019). Role of Corporate Governance to Mitigate the Idiosyncratic Risk in Non-Financial Sector of Pakistan. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 8(2), pp. 224-238.
- Ghosh, A., Moon, D., & Tandon, K. (2007). CEO ownership and discretionary investments. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 34(5-6), 819-839.
- Glosten, L. R., & Harris, L. E. (1988). Estimating the components of the bid/ask spread. *Journal of financial economics*, 21(1), 123-142.
- Glover, B., & Levine, O. (2017). Idiosyncratic risk and the manager. *Journal of financial economics*, 126(2), 320-341.
- Goetzmann, W. N., & Kumar, A. (2008). Equity portfolio diversification. *Review of Finance*, 12(3), 433-463.
- Goldman, E., Rocholl, J., & So, J. (2009). Do politically connected boards affect firm value? *The Review of Financial Studies*, 22(6), 2331–2360.
- Graham, J. R., & Harvey, C. R. (2001). The theory and practice of corporate finance: evidence from the field. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 187-243.
- Graham, J. R., Harvey, C. R., & Puri, M. (2013). Managerial attitudes and corporate actions. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 109(1), 103–121.
- Graham, J. R., Harvey, C. R., & Puri, M. (2013). Managerial attitudes and corporate actions. *Journal of financial economics*, 109(1), 103-121.
- Grenzke, J. M. (1989). PACs and the congressional supermarket: The currency is complex. *American Journal of Political Science*, 1–24.

- Grijalva, E., Harms, P. D., Newman, D. A., Gaddis, B. H., & Fraley, R. C. (2015). Narcissism and Leadership: A Meta-Analytic Review of Linear and Nonlinear Relationships. *Personnel Psychology*, 1-47.
- Grossman, G. M., & Helpman, E. (1996). Electoral competition and special interest politics. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 63(2), 265–286.
- Grossman, S. J., & Hart, O. D. (1986). The costs and benefits of ownership: A theory of vertical and lateral integration. *Journal of Political Economy*, 94(4), 691–719.
- Gürsoy, G., & Aydoğan, K. (2002). Equity ownership structure, risk taking, and performance: an empirical investigation in Turkish listed companies. *Emerging Markets Finance & Trade*, 6-25.
- Habib, M., & Zurawicki, L. (2002). Corruption and foreign direct investment. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 33(2), 291–307.
- Haider, J., & Fang, H.-X. (2016). Board size, ownership concentration and future firm risk. *Chinese Management Studies*.
- Hambrick, D. C., & Mason, P. A. (1984). Upper Echelons: The Organization as a Reflection of Its Top Managers. *Academy of Management Review*, 193-206.
- Hambrick, D. C., & Mason, P. A. (1984). Upper echelons: The organization as a reflection of its top managers. *Academy of Management Review*, 9(2), 193–206.
- Han, K. C., & Suk, D. Y. (1998). The effect of ownership structure on firm performance: Additional evidence. *Review of Financial Economics*, 7(2), 143-155.
- Hariharan, G., Chapman, K. S., & Domian, D. L. (2000). Risk tolerance and asset allocation for investors nearing retirement. *Financial Services Review*, 9(2), 159-170.
- Harris, C. R., & Jenkins, M. (2006). Gender differences in risk assessment: Why do women take fewer risks than men? *Judgment and Decision Making Journal*, 1(1), 48-63.
- Harrison, G. W., Lau, M. I., & Rutström., E. E. (2007). "Estimating risk attitudes in Denmark: A field experiment." *scandinavian Journal of Economics* 109, no. 2 (2007): 341-368. *scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 109(2), 341-368.
- Hersch, J. (1996). Smoking, seat belts, and other risky consumer decisions: Differences by gender and race. *Managerial and decision economics*, 17(5), 471-481.
- Hibbert, A. M., Lawrence, E. R., & Prakash, A. J. (2013). Does knowledge of finance mitigate the gender difference in financial risk-aversion? *Global Finance Journal*, 24(2), 140-152.
- Higgs, M. (2009). The Good, the Bad and the Ugly: Leadership and Narcissism. *Journal of Change Management*, 165-178.

- Hill, C. W., & Snell, S. A. (1988). External control, corporate strategy, and firm performance in research-intensive industries. *Strategic Management Journal*, 9(6), 577-590.
- Hillman, A. J., Keim, G. D., & Schuler, D. (2004). Corporate political activity: A review and research agenda. *Journal of Management*, 30(6), 837–857.
- Himmelberg, C. P., Hubbard, R. G., & Love, I. (2000). Investment, protection, ownership, and the cost of capital. *National Bank of Belgium Working Paper*(25).
- Himmelberg, C. P., Hubbard, R. G., & Palia, D. (1999). Understanding the determinants of managerial ownership and the link between ownership and performance. *Journal of financial economics*, 53(3), 353-384.
- Hinz, R. P., McCarthy, D. D., & Turner, J. A. (1997). Are women conservative investors? Gender differences in participant-directed pension investments. Wharton Pension Research Council.
- Hrazdil, K., Novak, J., Rogo, R., Wiedman, C., & Zhang, R. (2020). Measuring executive personality using machine-learning algorithms: A new approach and audit fee-based validation tests. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 47(3–4), 519–544.
- Hu, J., Long, W., Tian, G. G., & Yao, D. (2020). CEOs' experience of the Great Chinese Famine and accounting conservatism. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 47(9–10), 1089–1112.
- Huang, J., & Kisgen, D. J. (2013). Gender and corporate finance: Are male executives overconfident relative to female executives? *Journal of financial Economics*, 108(3), 822-839.
- Infante, L., & Piazza, M. (2014). Political connections and preferential lending at local level: Some evidence from the Italian credit market. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 29, 246–262.
- Jahmani, Y., & Ansari, M. (2006). Managerial ownership, risk, and corporate performance. *International Journal of Commerce and Management*.
- James P. Byrnes, D. C., & Schafer, W. D. (1999). Gender differences in risk taking: A meta-analysis. *Psychological bulletin*, 125(3), 367-383.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (2019). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. In *Corporate Governance* (pp. 77-132). Gower.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (2019a). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. In *Corporate Governance* (pp. 77–132). Gower.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (2019b). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. In *Corporate Governance* (pp. 77–132). Gower.

Jianakoplos, Ammon, N., & Bernasek, A. (1998). Are Women More Risk Averse? *Economic Inquiry*, 36(4), 620-630.

John, O. P., & Robins, R. W. (1994). Accuracy and bias in self-perception: Individual differences in self-enhancement and the role of narcissism. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 206-219.

John, K., Litov, L., & Yeung, B. (2008). Corporate governance and risk-taking. *The Journal of Finance*, 63(4), 1679-1728.

John, K., Litov, L., & Yeung, B. (2008). Corporate governance and risk-taking. *The journal of finance*, 63(4), 1679-1728.

Johnson, J., & Powell, P. (1994). Decision Making, Risk and Gender: Are Managers Different? *British Journal of Management*, 5(2), 123-138.

Jones, S. L., Megginson, W. L., Nash, R. C., & Netter, J. M. (1999). Share issue privatizations as financial means to political and economic ends. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 53(2), 217-253.

Kausel, E. E., Culbertson, S. S., Slaughter, J., & Leiva, P. (2015). Too arrogant for their own good? Why and when narcissists dismiss advice. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 33-50.

Keloharju, M., Knüpfer, S., & Torstila, S. (2008). Do retail incentives work in privatizations? *The Review of Financial Studies*, 21(5), 2061-2095.

Kernis, M. H., & Sun, C. R. (1994). Narcissism and Reactions to Interpersonal Feedback. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 4-13.

Kets de Vries, M. (2004). Organizations on the Couch: A Clinical Perspective on Organizational Dynamics. *European Management Journal*, 183-200.

Khan, W. A., & Vieito, J. P. (2013). CEO gender and firm performance. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 67, 55-66.

Khawaja, A., & Mian, A. (2004). Corruption and Politicians: Rent-seeking in an Emerging Financial Market. Cambridge, United States: Harvard University, Kennedy School of Government. Mimeographed Document.

Khawaja, A. I., & Mian, A. (2005). Do lenders favor politically connected firms? Rent provision in an emerging financial market. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 120(4), 1371-1411.

Kim, E. H., & Lu, Y. (2011). CEO ownership, external governance, and risk-taking. *Journal of financial economics*, 102(2), 272-292.

Knight, B. (2006). Are policy platforms capitalized into equity prices? Evidence from the Bush/Gore 2000 presidential election. *Journal of Public Economics*, 90(4–5), 751–773.

Krishnan, G. V., & Parsons, L. M. (2008). Getting to the bottom line: An exploration of gender and earnings quality. *Journal of business ethics*, 78(1), 65-76.

Kroszner, R. S., & Stratmann, T. (1998a). Interest-group competition and the organization of congress: theory and evidence from financial services' political action committees. *American Economic Review*, 1163–1187.

Kroszner, R. S., & Stratmann, T. (1998b). Interest-group competition and the organization of congress: theory and evidence from financial services' political action committees. *American Economic Review*, 1163–1187.

Krueger, A. O. (1974). The political economy of the rent-seeking society. *The American Economic Review*, 64(3), 291–303.

La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., & Shleifer, A. (1999). Corporate ownership around the world. *The journal of finance*, 54(2), 471-517.

la Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. (2002). Investor protection and corporate valuation. *The Journal of Finance*, 57(3), 1147–1170.

Laeven, L., & Levine, R. (2009). Bank governance, regulation and risk taking. *Journal of financial economics*, 93(2), 259-275.

Lakey, C. E., Rose, P., & Goodie, A. S. (2008). Probing the link between narcissism and gambling: The mediating role of judgment and decision-making biases. *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making*, 113–137.

Lee, S. W. (2002). Insider ownership and risk-taking behaviour at bank holding companies. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 29(7-8), 989-1005.

Leuz, C., & Oberholzer-Gee, F. (2006). Political relationships, global financing, and corporate transparency: Evidence from Indonesia. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 81(2), 411–439.

Levin, I. P., Snyder, M. A., & Chapman, D. P. (1988). The Interaction of Experiential and Situational Factors and Gender in a Simulated Risky Decision-Making Task. *The Journal of Psychology*, 122(2), 173–181.

Lewellen, K. (2006). Financing decisions when managers are risk averse. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 551-589.

Li, H., Meng, L., Wang, Q., & Zhou, L.-A. (2008). Political connections, financing and firm performance: Evidence from Chinese private firms. *Journal of Development Economics*, 87(2), 283–299.

- Li, K., Lu, L., Mittoo, U. R., & Zhang, Z. (2015). Board independence, ownership concentration and corporate performance—Chinese evidence. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 41, 162-175.
- Li, Y., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Investor Sentiment, Idiosyncratic Risk, and Stock Price Premium: Evidence From Chinese Cross-Listed Companies. *SAGE Open*, 11(2), 21582440211024621.
- Lindbeck, A. (1976). Stabilization policy in open economies with endogenous politicians. *The American Economic Review*, 66(2), 1–19.
- Lintner, J. (1969). The valuation of risk assets and the selection of risky investments in stock portfolios and capital budgets: A reply. *The review of economics and statistics*, 222-224.
- Liu, Y., & Taffler, R. (2008). CEO narcissism in M&A decision-making and its impact on firm performance.
- Liu, Y., Wei, Z., & Xie, F. (2016). CFO gender and earnings management: Evidence from China. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*, 46(4), 881-905.
- Lubit, R. (2002). The Long-Term Organizational Impact of Destructively Narcissistic Managers. *Academy of Management Executive*, 127-138.
- Malmendier, U., & Tate, G. (2005). CEO overconfidence and corporate investment. *The Journal of Finance*, 60(6), 2661–2700.
- Malmendier, U., & Tate, G. (2005). Does Overconfidence Affect Corporate Investment? CEO Overconfidence Measures Revisited. *European Financial Management*, 649-659.
- Malmendier, U., & Tate, G. (2008). Who makes acquisitions? CEO overconfidence and the market's reaction. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 20-43.
- Malmendier, U., Tate, G., & Yan, J. (2011). Overconfidence and early-life experiences: the effect of managerial traits on corporate financial policies. *The Journal of Finance*, 66(5), 1687–1733.
- McConnell, J. J., & Servaes, H. (1990). Additional evidence on equity ownership and corporate value. *Journal of financial economics*, 27(2), 595-612.
- Means, G. (2017). *The modern corporation and private property*. Routledge.
- Meggison, W. L., & Netter, J. M. (2001). From state to market: A survey of empirical studies on privatization. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 39(2), 321–389.
- Meggison, W. L., Nash, R. C., Netter, J. M., & Poulsen, A. B. (2004). The choice of private versus public capital markets: Evidence from privatizations. *The Journal of Finance*, 59(6), 2835–2870.

- Metawa, N., Hassan, M. K., Metawa, S., & Safa, M. F. (2018). Impact of behavioral factors on investors' financial decisions: case of the Egyptian stock market. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 12(1), 30-55.
- Mohammadi, A., & Shafi, K. (2018). Gender differences in the contribution patterns. *Small Bus Econ*, 275–287.
- Monsen Jr, R. J., & Downs, A. (1965). A theory of large managerial firms. *Journal of Political Economy*, 73(3), 221-236.
- Monsen, R. J., Chitj, J. S., & Cooley, D. E. (1968). The effect of separation of ownership and control on the performance of the large firm. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 82(3), 435-451.
- Montgomery, G. T., & Landers, W. F. (1974). Transmission of risk-taking through modeling at two age levels. *Psychological Reports* .
- Morck, R., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1988). Management ownership and market valuation: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 20, 293–315.
- Morck, R., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1988). Management ownership and market valuation: An empirical analysis. *Journal of financial economics*, 20, 293-315.
- Morck, R., Wolfenzon, D., & Yeung, B. (2005). Corporate governance, economic entrenchment, and growth. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 43(3), 655–720.
- Moskowitz, T. J., & Benmelech, E. (2007). The Political Economy of Financial Regulation: Evidence from US State Usury Laws in the 19th Century. NBER Working Paper, w12851.
- Mukarram, S. S., Ajmal, T., & Saeed, A. (2018). Women directors' propensity towards risk in technology firms. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*.
- Müller, E. (2011). Returns to private equity-idiosyncratic risk does matter! *Review of Finance*, 15(3), 545-574.
- Myers, S. C. (1977). Determinants of corporate borrowing. *Journal of financial economics*, 5(2), 147-175.
- Nasution, D., & Jonnergård, K. (2017). Do auditor and CFO gender matter to earnings quality? Evidence from Sweden. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*.
- Nelson, J. A. (2014). The Power of Stereotyping and Confirmation Bias to Overwhelm Accurate Assessment: The Case of Economics, Gender, and Risk Aversion. *Journal of Economic Methodology*, 21(3), 211-231.

Nguyen, L., Le, D., Tran, T., & Dang, T. (2021). Financial Reporting Quality, Corporate Governance, and Idiosyncratic Risk: Evidence from a Frontier Market. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 15(4), 28-46.

Nordhaus, W. D. (1975). The political business cycle. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 42(2), 169–190.

North, D. C. (1990). *Institutions, institutional change and economic performance*. Cambridge university press.

Noussair, C. N., Trautmann, S. T., & Kuilen, G. v. (2014). Higher Order Risk Attitudes, Demographics, and Financial decisions. *Review of Economic Studies*, 81(1), 325-355.

Oehler, A., Wendt, S., Wedlich, F., & Horn, M. (2018). Investors' Personality Influences Investment Decisions: Experimental Evidence on Extraversion and Neuroticism. *Journal of Behavioral Finance*, 19(1), 30-48.

Oikonomou, I., Yin, C., & Zhao, L. (2020). Investment horizon and corporate social performance: the virtuous circle of long-term institutional ownership and responsible firm conduct. *The European Journal of Finance*, 26(1), 14-40.

Olsen, R. A., & Cox, C. M. (2001). The Influence of Gender on the perception and response to investment risk: The case of professional investors. *The journal of psychology and financial markets*, 2(1), 29-36.

Olson, M. (1993). Dictatorship, democracy, and development. *American Political Science Review*, 87(3), 567–576.

O'Reilly III, C. A., Doerr, B., Caldwell, D. F., & Chatman, J. A. (2014). Narcissistic CEOs and executive compensation. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 218-231.

Otchere, I., Senbet, L. W., & Zhu, P. (2020). Does political connection distort competition and encourage corporate risk taking? International evidence. *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 55, 21–42.

Pagano, M., & Volpin, P. F. (2005). The political economy of corporate governance. *American Economic Review*, 95(4), 1005–1030.

Paligorova, T. (2010). Corporate risk taking and ownership structure.

Palvia, A., Vähämaa, E., & Vähämaa, S. (2020). Female leadership and bank risk-taking: Evidence from the effects of real estate shocks on bank lending performance and default risk. *Journal of Business Research*, 117, 897-909.

Panousi, V., & Papanikolaou, D. (2012). Investment, idiosyncratic risk, and ownership. *The journal of finance*, 67(3), 1113-1148.

Park, S. H., Li, S., & Tse, D. K. (2006). Market liberalization and firm performance during China's economic transition. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 37(1), 127–147.

Patel, P. C., & Cooper, D. (2014). The harder they fall, the faster they rise: Approach and avoidance focus in narcissistic CEOs. *Strategic Management Journal*, 1528-1540.

Peltomäki, J., Sihvonen, J., Swidler, S., & Vähämaa, S. (2021). Age, gender, and risk-taking: Evidence from the S&P 1500 executives and market-based measures of firm risk. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 48(9-10), 1988-2014.

Peni, E., & Vähämaa, S. (2010). Female executives and earnings management. *Managerial finance* .

Perez, R. (2017). Individual Executive Characteristics and Firm Performance: Evidence from CEO Narcissism.

Perotti, E. C. (1995). Credible privatization. *The American Economic Review*, 847–859.

Powell, M., & Ansic, D. (1997). Gender differences in risk behaviour in financial decision-making: An experimental analysis. *Journal of economic psychology*, 18(6), 605-628.

Process: From Private Initiation to Deal Completion. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 37-113.

Rajagopalan, N., & Zhang, Y. (2008). Corporate governance reforms in China and India: Challenges and opportunities. *Business Horizons*, 51(1), 55–64.

Rajan, R. G., & Zingales, L. (2003). The great reversals: the politics of financial development in the twentieth century. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 69(1), 5–50.

Rajverma, A. K., Misra, A. K., Mohapatra, S., & Chandra, A. (2019). Impact of ownership structure and dividend on firm performance and firm risk. *Managerial Finance*.

Raskin, R., & Hal, C. S. (1979). A narcissistic personality inventory. *Psychological Reports*.

Raskin, R., & Novacek, J. (1991). Narcissism and the use of fantasy. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 490-499.

Raskin, R., & Shaw, R. (1988). Narcissism and the Use of Personal Pronouns. *Journal of Personality*, 393-404.

Raskin, R., Novacek, J., & Hogan, R. (1991). Narcissistic self-esteem management. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 911-918.

Reina, C. S., Zhang, Z., & Peterson, S. (2014). CEO grandiose narcissism and firm performance: The role of organizational identification. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 958-971.

Rhodewalt, F., & Morf, C. C. (1998). On self-aggrandizement and anger: a temporal analysis of narcissism and affective reactions to success and failure. *Journal of Personality and Social*, 672-685.

Rijsenbilt, A., & Commandeur, H. (2012). Narcissus Enters the Courtroom: CEO Narcissism and Fraud. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 413-429.

Roberts, B. E. (1990a). A dead senator tells no lies: Seniority and the distribution of federal benefits. *American Journal of Political Science*, 31-58.

Roberts, B. E. (1990b). A dead senator tells no lies: Seniority and the distribution of federal benefits. *American Journal of Political Science*, 31-58.

Roberts, R., Woodman, T., & Sedikides, C. (2018). Pass me the ball: narcissism in performance settings. *International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 190-213.

Rodriguez, P., Siegel, D. S., Hillman, A., & Eden, L. (2006). Three lenses on the multinational enterprise: Politics, corruption, and corporate social responsibility. In *Journal of international business studies* (Vol. 37, Issue 6, pp. 733-746). Springer.

Roe, M. J. (2005). *Corporate governance: Political and legal perspectives*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

Ronningstam, E., & Weinberg, I. (2013). Narcissistic Personality Disorder: Progress in Recognition and Treatment. *Focus*, 167-177.

Rosenthal, S. A., & Pittinsky, T. L. (2006). Narcissistic leadership. *Leadership Quarterly*, 617-633.

Rosenthal, S. A., & Pittinsky, T. L. (2006). Narcissistic leadership. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 617-633.

Rosenthal, S. A., & Pittinsky, T. L. (2006). Narcissistic leadership. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 617-633.

Saeed, A., Belghitar, Y., & Clark, E. (2015). Political connections and leverage: Firm-level evidence from Pakistan. *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 36(6), 364-383.

Saeed, A., Belghitar, Y., & Clark, E. (2019). Political connections and corporate performance: Evidence from Pakistan. *Economics of Transition and Institutional Change*, 27(4), 863-889.

Sah, N. B., Adhikari, H. P., Krolikowski, M. W., Malm, J., & Nguyen, T. T. (2022). CEO gender and risk aversion: Further evidence using the composition of firm's cash. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance*, 33, 100595.

Sakawa, H., Watanabel, N., Duppati, G., & Faff, R. (2021). Institutional ownership and corporate risk-taking in Japanese listed firms. *Applied Economics*, 53(16), 1899-1914.

Salancik, G. R., & Pfeffer, J. (1980). Effects of ownership and performance on executive tenure in US corporations. *Academy of Management journal*, 23(4), 653-664.

Sanders, W. G., & Hambrick, D. C. (2007). Swinging for the fences: The effects of CEO stock options on company risk taking and performance. *Academy of Management Journal* , 1055–1078.

Sarin, A., Shastri, K., & Shastri, K. (1996). Ownership structure and stock market liquidity. Available at SSRN 02652.

Sarin, R., & Wieland, A. (2015). Risk Aversion for Decisions under Uncertainty: Are there Gender Differences? *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics*, 60, 1-8.

Saunders, A., Strock, E., & Travlos, N. G. (1990). Ownership structure, deregulation, and bank risk taking. *The journal of finance*, 45(2), 643-654.

Sayim, M., & Rahman, H. (2015). An examination of US institutional and individual investor sentiment effect on the Turkish stock market. *Global Finance Journal*, 26, 1-17.

Scholes, M., & Williams, J. (1977). Estimating betas from nonsynchronous data. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 309-327.

Schooley, D. K., & Worden, D. D. (1996). Risk aversion measures: Comparing attitudes and asset allocation. *Financial services review*, 5(2), 87-99.

Sharpe, W. F. (1964). Capital asset prices: A theory of market equilibrium under conditions of risk. *The journal of finance*, 19(3), 425-442.

Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1986). Large shareholders and corporate control. *Journal of Political Economy*, 94(3, Part 1), 461-488.

Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1993). Corruption. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 108(3), 599–617.

Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1994a). Politicians and firms. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 109(4), 995–1025.

Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1994b). Politicians and firms. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 109(4), 995–1025.

Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1994c). Politicians and firms. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 109(4), 995–1025.

Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1997). A survey of corporate governance. *The Journal of Finance*, 52(2), 737–783.

Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1997). A survey of corporate governance. *The journal of finance*, 52(2), 737-783.

Shleifer, A., Boycko, M., & Vishny, R. W. (1996). A theory of privatization. *Economic Journal*, 106(435).

Shon, J. (2006a). Stock returns and campaign contributions: the Bush vs. Gore 2000 presidential elections. Working paper, City University of New York.

Shon, J. (2006b). Stock returns and campaign contributions: the Bush vs. Gore 2000 presidential elections. Working paper, City University of New York.

Silberman, J. I., & Durden, G. C. (1976). Determining legislative preferences on the minimum wage: An economic approach. *Journal of Political Economy*, 84(2), 317-329.

Simon, J. D. (1984). A theoretical perspective on political risk. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 15(3), 123-143.

Slovic, P. (1996). Risk Taking in Children: Age and Sex. *Child Development* , 169-176.

Smith, C. W., & Stulz, R. M. (1985). The determinants of firms' hedging policies. *Journal of financial and quantitative analysis*, 20(4), 391-405.

Smith-Hillman, A. V., & Omar, M. (2005). FDI, international business and regulation: The behaviour of UK multinational corporations. *European Business Review*.

Snyder Jr, J. M. (1990). Campaign contributions as investments: The US House of Representatives, 1980-1986. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(6), 1195-1227.

Srinidhi, B. I., Gul, F. A., & Tsui, J. (2011). Female directors and earnings quality. *Contemporary accounting research*, 1610-1644.

Stigler, G. J. (2021). The theory of economic regulation. In *The Political Economy* (pp. 67-81). Routledge.

Stinson, F. S., Dawson, D. A., Goldstein, R. B., Chou, S. P., Huang, B., Smith, S. M., . . . Grant, B. F. (2008). Prevalence, Correlates, Disability, and Comorbidity of DSM-IV Narcissistic Personality Disorder: Results from the Wave 2 National Epidemiologic Survey on Alcohol and Related Conditions. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 1033-1045.

Stratmann, T. (1995). Campaign contributions and congressional voting: does the timing of contributions matter? *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 127-136.

Stratmann, T., & Verret, J. W. (2015). How Does Corporate Political Activity Allowed by *Citizens United v. Federal Election Commission* Affect Shareholder Wealth? *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 58(3), 545-559.

- Stulz, R. M. (2005). The limits of financial globalization. *The Journal of Finance*, 60(4), 1595–1638.
- Sullivan, R. J., & Spong, K. R. (2007). Manager wealth concentration, ownership structure, and risk in commercial banks. *Journal of financial intermediation*, 16(2), 229-248.
- Sunden, A. E., & Surette, B. J. (1998). Gender differences in the allocation of assets in retirement savings plans. *The American Economic Review*, 88(2), 207-211.
- Tamborski, M., Brown, R. P., & Chowning, K. (2012). Self-Serving Bias or Simply Serving the Self? Evidence for a Dimensional Approach to Narcissism. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 942-946.
- Tuddenham, R. D. (1952). Studies in Reputation: I, Sex and Grade Differences in School Children's Evaluation of Their Peers. *Psychological Monographs: General and Applied*, 66(1), i-58.
- Twenge, J. M., & Campbell, W. K. (2009). *The Narcissism Epidemic: Living in the Age of Entitlement*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Twenge, J. M., Konrath, S., Foster, J. D., Campbell, W. K., & Bushman, B. J. (2008). Egos inflating over time: a cross-temporal meta-analysis of the Narcissistic Personality Inventory. *Journal of Personality*, 875-902.
- Vishny, S. A. (1988). Managerial Entrenchment: The Case of Manager Specific Investment. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 25(5), 42-67.
- Vlaev, I., Kusev, P., Stewart, N., Aldrovandi, S., & Chater, N. (2010). Domain effects and financial risk attitudes. *Risk Analysis: An International Journal*, 30(9), 1374-1386.
- Wales, W. J., Patel, P. C., & Lumpkin, G. T. (2013). In Pursuit of Greatness: CEO Narcissism, Entrepreneurial Orientation, and Firm Performance Variance. *Journal of Management Studies*, 1041-1069.
- Wallace, H. M., & Baumeister, R. F. (2002). The Performance of Narcissists Rises and Falls With Perceived Opportunity for Glory. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 819-834.
- Warfield, T. D., Wild, J. J., & Wild, K. L. (1995). Managerial ownership, accounting choices, and informativeness of earnings. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 20(1), 61–91.
- Watson, J., & McNaughton, M. (2007). Gender differences in risk aversion and expected retirement benefits. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 63(4), 52-62.
- Watson, J., & McNaughton, M. (2007). Gender differences in risk aversion and expected retirement benefits. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 63(4), 52-62.

- Watson, J., & Robinson, S. (2003). Adjusting for risk in comparing the performances of male- and female-controlled SMEs. *Journal of business venturing*, 18(6), 773–788.
- Whitley, R. (2000). The institutional structuring of innovation strategies: business systems, firm types and patterns of technical change in different market economies. *Organization Studies*, 21(5), 855-886.
- Wieland, A., Sundali, J., Kimmelmeier, M., & Sarin, R. (2014). Gender differences in the endowment effect: Women pay less, but won't accept less. *Judgment & Decision Making*, 9(6), 558-557.
- Wik, M., Kebede, T. A., Bergland, O., & Holden, S. T. (2004). On the measurement of risk aversion from experimental data. *Applied Economics*, 36(21), 2443-2451.
- Witt, J. L. (1994). The Gendered Division of Labor in Parental Caregiving: Biology or Socialization? *Journal of Women and Aging*, 6(1), 65-89.
- Wolfers, J. (2002). Are voters rational?: Evidence from gubernatorial elections. Graduate School of Business, Stanford University Stanford.
- Wright, P., Ferris, S. P., Sarin, A., & Awasthi, V. (1996). Impact of corporate insider, blockholder, and institutional equity ownership on firm risk taking. *Academy of Management Journal*, 39(2), 441–458.
- Wright, P., Ferris, S. P., Sarin, A., & Awasthi, V. (1996). Impact of corporate insider, blockholder, and institutional equity ownership on firm risk taking. *Academy of Management journal*, 39(2), 441-458.
- Wright, P., Kroll, M., Lado, A., & Van Ness, B. (2002). The structure of ownership and corporate acquisition strategies. *Strategic Management Journal*, 23(1), 41-53.
- Xu, Y., & Malkiel, B. G. (2003). Investigating the behavior of idiosyncratic volatility. *The Journal of Business*, 76(4), 613-645.
- Young, R. D., & Torna, G. (2013). Nontraditional banking activities and bank failures during the financial crisis. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 397-421.
- Zhang, H., Li, L., Zhou, D., & Zhou, P. (2014). Political connections, government subsidies and firm financial performance: Evidence from renewable energy manufacturing in China. *Renewable Energy*, 63, 330–336.
- Zhang, T., Sabherwal, S., Jayaraman, N., & Ferris, S. P. (2016). The young and the restless: A study of age and acquisition propensity of CEOs of UK firms. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 43(9-10), 1385-1419.
- Zhu, D. H., & Chen, G. (2015). Narcissism, director selection, and risk-taking spending. *Strategic Management Journal*, 2075-2098.

Zuckerman, M. (1994). Behavioral expressions and biosocial bases of sensation seeking. Cambridge university press.